

OPINION GLOSSARY

Integrating Theory and Methods
for Automatically Analyzing
Opinionated Communication

Edited by

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Working Group 1 Theory
COST Action CA21129 OPINION

TABLE OF CONTENTS

Introduction.....	9
Addressee.....	10
Affect/Affective Foundation of Opinion.....	11
Affordances/Affordance Theory.....	13
Agenda-setting.....	15
Algorithmisation.....	16
Ambivalence.....	17
Ambiguity.....	18
Anonymity.....	20
Arena.....	22
Argument.....	23
Attitude.....	24
Audience.....	25
Audience Segmentation.....	26
Authentic Opinions/Inauthentic Opinions.....	27
Belief.....	28
Bias.....	29
Cognition/Cognitive Linguistics.....	31
Cognitive Dissonance.....	32
Collectivisation.....	33
Communication.....	34
Computational Linguistics.....	35
Confirmation Bias.....	36
Conjecture.....	37

Context.....	38
Contextual Embedding/Transformers	39
Controversy.....	40
Cooperative Principle	41
Cotext	42
Critical Discourse Analysis	43
Culture	44
Data/Dataset	45
Discourse (1).....	46
Discourse (2).....	47
Disinformation.....	48
Echo Chamber	49
Emotions.....	50
Emotions in Political Opinion	51
Emotion Display Norms in Politics	52
Epistemic Community.....	53
Epistemic/Truth	55
Evaluative Language	56
Evidence	57
Evidentiality.....	58
Explicit/Explicitness	59
Expressive Language/Emotional Function of Language.....	60
Face.....	61
Face-saving Act	62
Face-threatening Act.....	63
Fact.....	64
Fact-checking.....	65

Fake News/Misinformation	66
Foundedness	67
Frames	68
Framing Theory	69
Hate Speech	71
Hedging	72
Identity	73
Ideology	74
Implicit	75
Implicitness	76
Implicit Bias	77
Impoliteness	78
Incivility (1)	80
Incivility (2)	81
Individualisation	83
Infographics/Data Visualisation	84
Insults	85
Intention	87
Interactivity	88
Interpretation	90
Intuition	91
Irony	92
Issue	94
Journalistic Interventionism	95
Judgement (1)	96
Judgement (2)	97
Lexical Embedding	98

Manipulation	99
Media Bias	100
Media Effects	102
Media Literacy	103
Metaphor	104
Modality	105
Mode	106
Multimodality/Semiotics	107
Multimodality/Sociotechnical Analysis	108
Networked Audiences	109
News Avoidance	111
Nomination	112
Objectivation	113
Objectivity	114
Opinion	115
Opinion (Speech) Event	116
Opinion Expression	117
Opinion Holder	118
Opinion Markers	120
Opinion Object	121
Opinion Types	122
Partisan Media Bias	124
Passivisation	126
Perspective	127
Persuasion	128
Platformivity/Platformisation/Platform	129
Polarisation	131

Political Expression.....	132
Politicisation.....	133
Polysemy.....	135
Power	136
Predication.....	137
Prejudice.....	138
Private/Public.....	140
Prototype.....	141
Public Opinion.....	142
Public Opinion as a Statistical Distribution.....	143
Public Opinion as a Discursive Process.....	144
Publics/Mainstream Publics/Counter-Publics.....	145
Relativism.....	146
Resonance	147
Sarcasm.....	148
Schema	150
Semantics	151
Sentiment	152
Sentiment Analysis.....	153
Slurs.....	154
Social Media.....	155
Sources of Opinion.....	157
Sourcing.....	158
Speech Act/Speech Event.....	159
Stance.....	160
Stereotype (1).....	161
Stereotype (2).....	163

Subjectivity.....	164
Thought.....	165
Trust.....	166
Truth	167
Types of Participants in Social Media Audience.....	168
Types of Public Opinion.....	169
View.....	171
Vulgarism	172
World Knowledge/Extralinguistic Knowledge	173
Worldview	174
About OPINION Network	175

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Introduction

One of the goals of the WG1 (THEORY) of this COST Action was an extensive literature review of existing theory and research on opinions and their textual/discursive expression that would allow us to develop a glossary of key definitions and terms. We aim in offering an interdisciplinary, still coherent, overview of key terms and definitions to scholars who have been conducting studies on opinion or are planning to start doing that.

This **Glossary** is an outcome of collaborative work of more than 30 scholars from 13 countries and regions. For the previous months, participants of the WG1 have been working in four subgroups, arranged around four areas of study, namely: (1) linguistics, (2) political communication & cultural studies, (3) public opinion, and (4) communication & media studies. Based on the **Literature Review**, we recognised terms and concepts employed in studies on opinionated communication across disciplines.

Both the **Literature Review** and the **Glossary** will serve us as a starting point for developing a joint manifesto on conceptual criteria and dimensions of textually expressed opinions and resulting research agenda (MoU, D1.2).

The Glossary contains over 140 entries, each providing a clear definition, highlighting the main features of the concept or phenomenon, and outlining its theoretical background. Each entry concludes with a selection of references for further reading. All entries have been peer-reviewed and edited into a standardised format.

We hope this Glossary will serve as a valuable resource for researchers and practitioners alike, fostering a shared understanding of key concepts and facilitating interdisciplinary dialogue on the study of opinions. By clarifying definitions and theoretical foundations, we aim to contribute to more rigorous, transparent, and collaborative research in the fields of linguistics, communication, and social sciences. We warmly thank all contributors and reviewers for their dedication to this collective effort.

Addressee

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An *addressee* is the immediate recipient or intended receiver of a communicative act, as understood within the frameworks of speech act theory, pragmatics, and discourse analysis. The addressee plays a central role in shaping communication, as language users continuously adapt their utterances to suit the perceived identity, knowledge, expectations, and emotional stance of their interlocutor. This process of adaptation underpins both everyday conversation and more structured forms of public discourse. Frame Semantics highlights the role of the addressee in meaning construction since linguistic expressions are interpreted in relation to background cognitive frames, structured sets of knowledge shared between speaker and addressee. Effective communication thus depends on the speaker's ability to anticipate the frame activated in the mind of the addressee and align their message accordingly. Building on this, and from a Gricean pragmatic perspective, the social dynamics between speaker and addressee are emphasized. Communicators deploy politeness strategies, indirectness, and conversational implicatures to navigate interpersonal relationships and manage social roles. Particularly in public discourse—such as political speeches, media commentary, and public opinion formation—addressing diverse audiences involves carefully balancing clarity, persuasion, and social sensitivity. In the context of public opinion, the notion of the addressee becomes crucial. Politicians, journalists, and institutions craft their messages in anticipation of how target audiences such as voters, readers, or constituents will interpret and emotionally respond to them. The framing of information, choice of tone, and use of inclusive or exclusive language all reflect strategic considerations about the addressee's values, identity, and likely reception. Understanding the concept of the addressee is thus essential for analysing how public discourse seeks to influence, align with, or challenge collective opinion.

Keywords: communication, language users, social dynamics

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Affect/Affective Foundation of Opinion

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Affect is a category employed by various (sub-)disciplines in the social sciences to refer to any form of subjective feeling or emotional state. Expressing one's affect, either directly towards a given object (person, object event, or process), or in relation to discussions about one, constitutes one common form of evaluative opinion. Appraisal theory groups affect as that part of an evaluative process that relies on emotion, and it is used to refer to emotions as part of the evaluative process. Moreover, typically affect ranges from positive to negative polar opposites. Although linguistically affect can be realised by many lexical and grammatical expressions, the appraisal theory groups emotions into three major sets linked to un/happiness (manifestations of sadness, hate, happiness, and love), in/security (references to anxiety, fear, confidence, and trust) and dis/satisfaction (references to ennui, displeasure, curiosity, and respect). Affect is considered as one part of sentiment in numerous approaches and tools that aim to detect evaluative tendencies based on lexical indicators.

The affective base of opinions has been argued to impact the depth of cognitive processing, persuasive force, and recall, and potentially also behavioral responses: Specifically, the expression of affect-based opinions appears to stimulate others to express their opinions, as well, and contributes to virality on social networking sites. Moreover, studies also suggest that affective content can create behavioral responses: Political communication research, for instance, demonstrates that affective statements can stimulate the expression of political opinions and can thus trigger virality on social networking sites.

Affective opinionated statements have been used in empirical research from two perspectives. On the one hand, experimental research has focused on the persuasive power of affect-based opinion expressions. One salient example is research on the effects of fear appeals, notably in the context of health communication and propaganda. In this, affective statements are constructed as stimulus material and used as independent variables.

On the other hand, there is a prevalence of affect-based opinion expressions across various forms of communication. Content analytic research investigates how affective different forms of communication are. For instance, scholars have compared the affective quality of opinionated statements by populist and non-populist politicians, or different types of media outlets. A specific concern of public opinion research is affective polarisation, wherein members of competing societal

groups or ideologies experience and potentially express their disdain toward one another and align their opinions with this ingroup/outgroup dichotomy. Similarly, affective publics has become a useful framework to define the state of publics where social media mediates public display of emotive reactions to a given phenomenon. Through such an effective process, audiences not only connect but also disrupt and mediate everyday politics.

Affect-based opinion expression is measured either using manual content analysis, or using automatic tools such as specialised dictionaries or sentiment analysis, which recognises affective expressions among other evaluative terms.

Keywords: affective polarisation, affective expressions, virality, affect as valence (positive/negative)

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Affordances/Affordance Theory

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Affordances refer to the perceived or actual functionalities and possibilities that a technology or platform offers to its users. The concept of affordances is rooted in Gibsonian ecological psychology, emphasising the relationship between an organism and its environment. Affordances in his theory refer to the possibilities for action that the environment offers to an individual. The term 'technological affordances' was later coined by Ian Hutchby as a reaction against social constructivism to describe the materially based constraints on what could be done with technological artifacts. Scholars often apply affordance theory to understand how features and design of certain technologies shape communication dynamics and users' activities, and how users perceive and interact with technologies. Communication researchers adopt relational approach on affordances acknowledging that while the material characteristics of technology shape user interactions, they do not solely dictate the range of possibilities available to users. Affordances thus empower users with a sense of agency, allowing them to perform specific actions. For instance, the 'like' button on social media platforms allows users to express approval or agreement with the content. Affordance theory hence examines users' perceptions of what they can do with a particular technology. In the case of social media, it could include the perceived possibilities for communication, self-presentation, sharing information, or connecting with others. The affordance theory has faced criticism for potential technological determinism and has undergone refinement to incorporate contextual factors, user agency, and the dynamic nature of technology use. However, the conceptualisation of 'affordances' and its application significantly differ across studies. Additionally, the theory plays a crucial role in design, where designers use affordances to predict user interactions with a product or platform.

Keywords: user agency, technological determinism

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Agenda-setting

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Agenda setting theory is addressed to what McCombs and Shaw determined in 1972 that it is the mass media that sets the agenda of electoral campaigns, shaping the political reality, influencing their readers not only on a specific issue presented by the media but also on the level of importance because of the amount of information in a news story and its position. The agenda setting theory holds that information is not a simple reflection of social reality, but its reconstruction - a product that is affected by various factors and mechanisms. Various actors participate in the process of creating the media agenda of everyday life, including in particular journalists, political leaders, groups of interest, and other opinion makers. By using multiple forms and strategies of manifesting specific issues and interests, actors who want to shape the public agenda influence the processes of prioritising, gatekeeping, and framing individual events, topics and issues on which the media should focus. Creating such an image of the public affairs agenda in the media is of fundamental importance for shaping public opinion. This theory places the mass media in the main role of selecting news and media content, and it is precisely the mass media that prioritise those contents that people should follow.

Keywords: mass media, public affairs

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Algorithmisation

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Algorithmisation refers to designing and defining a series of steps or instructions to solve a problem or perform a task. It is most often associated with the performance of breaking down a problem into smaller, more manageable parts and creating a set of procedures that a computer or a human can follow in order to achieve a specific goal. In computer science and programming, algorithms are sets of rules used to solve problems or perform computations. In social media, algorithms are used to sort endless content, determine how content is filtered, ranked, selected, matched to audiences with similar preferences, and recommended to users. The algorithmisation process is often seen to bring order in different data cultures by reducing their complexity. In academic scholarship, therefore, algorithms are seen as ‘the metaphor of modern culture’, especially in the context of information abundance, noise, and overload, where various information selection strategies, such as filtering on social media, work to direct feeds, control preferences, and drive social media experiences. There are many forms of algorithmisation, such as the Big Data model, data visualisation model, and others that work effectively for the purpose of data gathering and advertising. In comparison to other social media platforms, authors highlight TikTok as the most algorithm-centered one, because it has been particularly known for its explicit and unprecedented use of the ‘for you’ algorithm, which determines the users’ exposure to content. Algorithms drive users through overabundance of posts and endless content online, have control over what users see and get, connect them with others who like similar things, and recommend further exploration of data based on users’ behaviour.

Keywords: algorithm, media

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Ambivalence

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Ambivalence describes the simultaneous presence of both positive and negative affective or evaluative sentiment, experienced or expressed by the same subject or individual or collective author. It arises from the fact that evaluative and affective appraisals are multidimensional, such that the same object may evoke both positive and negative feelings and evaluations. For ambivalence to exist, there needs to be some intention to evaluate or relate one's feelings toward some object, while it remains unclear whether positive or negative tendencies prevail. Ambivalence is distinct from neutrality, which denotes the absence of strong evaluations or feelings. In opinion expression, ambivalence can take several distinct forms. Speakers may expressly refer to both positive and negative feelings or evaluations, or explicitly qualify these as polyvalent (e.g., 'mixed blessing'); similarly, they directly combine positively and negatively connoted terms ('poisoned praise', 'unbearable lightness') to express their sentiment. Ambivalence may also be expressed metaphorically or by analogy, referring to known-ambivalent cultural symbols (e.g., 'Pyrrhic victory'; 'stopgap'). Depending on the context, single evaluative or affective expressions may also suffice to express ambivalence, either through a collision between expressed sentiments and observed behavior (e.g., 'I hate saying it, but'), or with situational expectations (e.g., 'funny' may be ambivalent when evaluating a policy, which is not supposed to be funny; 'interesting' can be positive, ambivalent, or even negative, e.g., when evaluating a dish or a student's answer). Ambivalence can be explicated or arise from the ambiguity of expressions themselves, which may either fail to specify which out of multiple possible evaluative or affective tendencies is intended, or directly cue competing interpretations that raise contrasting appraisals. In borderline cases, one tendency may dominate while opposing affects or evaluative considerations remain salient (e.g., 'I know it is not healthy, but it is so tasty!'). Ambivalence may also arise when univalent appraisals are hedged or ironised to the point of casting doubt on the expressed dominant tendency, but not to the point of inverting the expressed meaning. Likewise, high degrees of uncertainty about one's feelings or evaluation may sometimes express ambivalence even if neither positive nor negative aspects are expressly cued. In practice, expressed opinions may contain greater or lesser degrees of ambivalence, from opinions that lean one way while upholding relevant second thoughts, to fully ambivalent expressions.

Keywords: evaluative sentiment; emotions; ambiguity

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Ambiguity

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Ambiguity refers to uncertainties in the meaning to be derived from a message or discursive situation, caused by the simultaneous co-presence of multiple competing interpretations. While there are also manifest, grammatical forms of ambiguity (e.g., ambiguous anaphora, such as in ‘the man played well with the dog, until he bit him’; answering ‘yes’ to ‘you don’t mind, do you?’), most ambiguity arises from the fundamental semantic openness of text. Characteristically, texts – including non-linguistic messages, such as symbols or communicative images – require reader’s or interlocutors’ active participation in their interpretation, and thus are subject to being read in different ways. While some textual genres tend to try and exclude ambiguity by narrowly guiding interpretation, other genres deliberately play with or strategically exploit ambiguity (e.g., ‘strategic ambiguity’, a practice in political speech that allows different audiences to read different preferred meanings into a message; innuendos, dog whistles, and other practices designed to permit the speaker to deny specific intended meanings if challenged). Two important drivers of ambiguity are underspecification and polysemy.

Regarding underspecification, messages conventionally focus on specifying any information that is needed to convey a specific communicative intent, while omitting all that is not deemed important or already available from context (e.g., prior turns; the situation; generic conventions). As a result, messages can be ambiguous if read to derive meaning other than what was intended (e.g., does ‘I don’t know her’ entail an invitation to elaborate?), or out of their original context. Messages may also be deliberately underspecified, so as to avoid commitment or permit varying interpretations. Linguistically encoded messages are primarily underspecified by omission (everything that is not mentioned), while visual communication tends to be underspecified in terms of the intended semantic concepts. Underspecification is particularly widespread in informal, interactive discourse, where contextual cues support interpretation, and least pronounced in formal genres addressing unknown audiences (e.g., manuals, legal documents).

Regarding polysemy, the cultural embedding of communication offers rich semiotic resources for creating a multiplicity of meaning potentials. Polysemy may arise accidentally (e.g., if a statement evokes connotations or associations that compete with or overlay the intended communication); it may be mobilised to offer additional, optional interpretations that add depth to a message; or it may be instrumental for conveying communicative intent (e.g., humor often relies on the co-presence of colliding meaning potentials). A key source of polysemy is intertextuality, where specific expressions, symbols, or scenes evoke culturally familiar texts or contexts that endow a message with additional meanings. Also language can be a source of polysemy, for instance, when homonyms refer to multiple relevant meanings, or via the use of linguistic symbols, analogical or figurative speech. Especially pop-cultural messages are often rich in polysemy.

Ambiguity can also be expressed directly by marking uncertainties in meaning or expressly presenting multiple, competing interpretations. In specific cases,

ambiguity can also result in ambivalence, if the multiplicity of available meanings cues competing evaluative or affective tendencies.

Keywords: polysemy, underspecification, strategic ambiguity

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Anonymity

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Anonymity typically refers to the condition of being anonymous or the intentional withholding of identity information in communication. It refers to the deliberate act of concealing or omitting personal identifiers, such as the speaker's or writer's name, in linguistic expressions. Anonymity plays a significant role in shaping communication dynamics and discourse, impacting the perceived authority, power relations, and social implications within language use. There exist implications of anonymity of opinions, particularly in online communication, which have significant implications for individuals, discourse, and societal dynamics. While it can offer a protective shield for free expression, it also introduces challenges related to credibility, accountability, and the potential for abuse.

1. **Enhanced Freedom of Expression:** Anonymity can empower individuals to express opinions freely without fear of personal repercussions, according to Citron and Franks. This can lead to the sharing of diverse perspectives and dissenting views, fostering a robust marketplace of ideas.
2. **Reduced Accountability and Responsibility:** The lack of personal identification may lead to a decline in accountability, claims Suler. Individuals may feel less restrained in spreading misinformation or engaging in harmful behavior, as they perceive a diminished risk of facing consequences for their opinions or actions.
3. **Impact on Online Discourse and Civility:** Anonymity can contribute to a decline in civility in online discussions, as individuals may engage in more aggressive or hostile behavior when shielded by anonymity, say Pennycook and Randm. This can affect the overall quality of discourse and hinder constructive dialogue.
4. **Potential for Trolling and Harassment:** Buckels et al. find that anonymity provides a breeding ground for online trolling and harassment, as individuals may exploit the lack of identification to engage in harmful activities without fear of personal repercussions.
5. **Challenges to Establishing Trust:** Metzger et al. find that online communication introduces challenges in establishing trust within online communities or platforms. Users may question the reliability and authenticity of opinions when the identity of the speaker is concealed.

Keywords: freedom, accountability, discourse

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The arena describes the configuration of visibility and access regimes that govern participation in the public debate. People may ‘enter the arena’ to publicly express their opinions and interact with other speakers; or they may participate as spectators who engage the unfolding debate without presenting their own views. Since the metaphor was originally conceived, digital communication platforms have massively expanded the range of speakers who can access the arena, while facilitating participants’ switching of roles, and creating new intermediate forms of participation (e.g., indicating support for/boosting the visibility of others’ opinions; posting public shout-outs without engagement with other contributions).

Different media environments raise different hurdles for entering to the arena, which may be more or less exclusive, and involve additional gatekeepers and selection criteria: While anyone can post on X (formerly Twitter), not every letter to the editor is printed, and few are invited to sit on talk shows; some arenas are only accessible to speakers presenting relevant credentials (e.g., expertise, public office), or pre-define differentiated speaker roles (e.g., anchors, stakeholders, opposition members). In addition, arenas govern participation by imposing discursive norms that participants are expected to respect (e.g., civility norms, argumentative norms). Arenas may be thematically open, permitting participants to insert and redefine issues, or restricted, marking unrelated contributions as off-topic. Arenas also differ in their capacity to carry multiple discussions at once (scope) and accommodate numerous voices and contributions (scale).

Regarding their accessibility to spectators, some arenas are capable of actively rendering issues salient to audiences, while others require some amount of audience activity to achieve exposure. In addition, arenas differ in their management of visibility of speakers’ contributions, ranging from more egalitarian spaces (e.g., townhall meetings, visibility allocated based on user engagement), to hierarchically pre-structured ones (e.g., visibility for purchase, privileged speaker roles).

Keywords: public discourse, public sphere, political participation

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Argument

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Argument is a reason or set of reasons given in support of an idea, action, or theory. Arguments are prototypically based on logical reasoning. In formal logic, the reasons offered within the argument are referred to as *premises*, and the proposition for which the premises are offered is called the *conclusion*. Copi and Cohen offer the following as an example:

- [1] Tom is happy only if he is playing guitar.
[2] Tom is not playing guitar.

∴ [3] Tom is not happy.

Arguments are commonly classified as deductive or inductive. A *deductive argument* is an argument that an arguer puts forward as valid. For example: 'All men are mortal (premise). Socrates is a man (premise). Therefore, Socrates is mortal (conclusion).' An *inductive argument* is an argument that an arguer puts forward as *inductively strong*. In an inductive argument, the premises are intended only to be so strong that, if they were true, then it would be *unlikely*, although possible, that the conclusion is false. For example: 'Every swan I have seen is white (premise). Therefore, all swans are white (conclusion).' The strength of an argument is assessed by its *validity* (for deductive arguments) and *soundness*, or its *strength* and *coGENCY* (for inductive arguments). A valid deductive argument is one where the conclusion necessarily follows from the premises. For inductive arguments, strength refers to the probability that the conclusion is true given the premises. According to Johnson, pragmatic definitions of arguments draw attention to the function of argument, such as Walton's seeing their use as tools of rational persuasion, originally proposed in Aristotle's *persuasive appeals*, which, when integrated as a *rhetorical triangle*, would make an argument optimally persuasive: *Ethos*, which focuses on the author's credibility, *Pathos*, which involves appealing to the audience's emotions, and *Logos*, which appeals to the audience's sense of logic and reason.

Keywords: conclusion, deductive/inductive argument, persuasive appeal, premise

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Attitude

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Allport defined attitude as a mental and neural state of readiness, organised through experience, and exerting a directive or dynamic influence upon the individual's response to all objects and situations with which it is related. In subsequent decades, the attitude concept has been narrowed down and was largely reduced to its evaluative component. Eagly and Chaiken defined attitudes as a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favor or disfavor. Vaughan & Hogg defined attitude as the organisation of beliefs, feelings, and behavioral tendencies towards socially significant objects, groups, events, or symbols. Nowadays, attitude is defined as a relatively enduring and general evaluation of an object, person, group, issue, or concept on a dimension ranging from negative to positive. Attitudes provide summary evaluations of target objects and are often assumed to be derived from specific beliefs, emotions, and past behaviors associated with those objects.

According to the Appraisal Theory by Martin and White, attitude is concerned with our feelings, judgments, and evaluation of aspects of the world in which we live. *Attitude* can be further divided into *affect*, *judgment*, and *appreciation*. *Affect* refers to emotional responses, *judgment* to evaluations of behaviors, and *appreciation* to the quality of processes and products (the aesthetics). Attitude is a subtype of evaluative language that conveys a positive or negative assessment of people, events, situations, actions, etc. Attitudes can be conveyed explicitly or implicitly. Sometimes, utterances can be classified as attitudinal if they invite readers to position themselves positively or negatively towards what is predicated.

Keywords: influence, evaluation, judgment, beliefs.

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Audience

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Audiences are defined in different ways: by place, by people, by the particular type of medium or channel involved, as well as by time. Several authors have carefully studied audiences, including Webster, Webster and Phalen, Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch, or Livingstone. Webster saw the audience as a mass, because of the media's effects on them, and as an agent, but he also talks about mixed models of how we define audiences. McQuail makes sure to advance in the division of the most specific typologies of audiences, to see the audience not only under the effect of media messages, so defining the audience as a group or as a public; audiences with their needs or preferences, the audience of the medium, audience defined by channel or content, but also the audience as a target, as a participant, as a spectator, etc.

Research in theories of use and gratifications emphasises how individuals use communications in their environment to satisfy their needs and achieve their goals. This model of studying audiences is centered on five elements, among which viewing audiences as active in the entire mass communication process, the need for gratification and the choice of media belongs to the audience member, and that many of the purposes of using mass media can be drawn from the data provided by individual audience members, where people are self-aware enough to be able to re- portray their interests and motives on particular occasions. The relationship between audiences and the public should be taken into consideration according to Livingstone as public refers to a common understanding or involvement in a common forum because public implies an orientation of collective and consensual. There is a contradiction in Livingstone's eyes regarding the fact that the importance of the media is increasing in many areas of life, but on the other hand, people's engagement with these media remains insignificant.

Keywords: interactivity, heterogeneous audience, mediated messages

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Audience Segmentation

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The basic idea of segmentation is simple, as Gruning stated, and is about dividing a population, market, or audience into groups whose members are more like each other than members of other segments.

The rationale is that by subdividing a large heterogeneous audience into smaller, more homogeneous segments, communication and social marketing planners can make informed decisions as to which audience(s) to target, and how to do so.

As Slater underlines, audience segmentation is the necessary prerequisite to creating messages that are responsive to the concerns, needs, and perspectives of specific populations. In other words, if one is to communicate, one must begin with an implicit or explicit definition of who one's audiences or interlocutors are. Segmentation is, at its core, a systematic and explicit process for arriving at such a definition.

One of the founding fathers of audience segmentation concept is John Dewey who introduced to us the notion of publics that share similar interests or values.

Smith studied the process in a market perspective. Market segmentation consists of viewing a heterogeneous market (one characterised by divergent demand) as a number of smaller homogeneous markets in response to differing product preferences among important market segments. It is attributable to the desires of consumers or users for more precise satisfaction of their varying wants.

Keywords: audience, personalised communication, targeted audience, market segmentation

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Authentic Opinions/Inauthentic Opinions

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There are at least two ways to consider authenticity. Authenticity and inauthenticity of opinions first stem from a broad definition of the concept: it can relate to authentic or (in)authentic intentions, sources, or messages, or content in general. With the rise of computational tools that automate dissemination of information online, not all opinions in an online public sphere are produced in an authentic way. Another way of thinking of (in)authenticity by media scholars stems from the perceptual framework, i.e., how we perceive the world through the media. Thus, mediated authenticity suggests that media presents people or things in a specific light, in which they can be perceived as more or less authentic.

However, both perspectives entail that authenticity can be constructed and in some cases orchestrated to achieve communicative goals of the message sender.

Inauthentic public opinions can be written with the help of the automated tools and/or are produced by groups of actors with the underlying agendas, e.g. to influence the discussion. In the scholarship on *coordinated inauthentic behaviors*, such behaviors can be mediated and amplified by synthetic agents such as online bots and further proliferated by algorithms that typically mediate online spaces.

Some scholars attribute inauthentic expression of opinions online as astroturfing. While scholars in various fields work on how to detect inauthentic coordinated behaviors, it poses challenges to authentic public opinions.

Keywords: authenticity, inauthentic public sphere, coordinated inauthentic behaviors, astroturfing

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Belief

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Belief is the feeling of certitude that someone or something exists or is true or trustworthy.

It is a conviction of the truth of some statement or the reality of some being or phenomenon, especially when based on examination of evidence. Belief can be connected with *credence*, i.e., intellectual assent without implying anything about grounds for assent. According to Ali and Fumerton, belief can be justified (it then constitutes *knowledge*, typically based on *evidence*, requiring *truth* and *justification*) or can be unjustified.

There are four theories of belief: the *intellectualist theory* that belief is a cognitive act related to evidence that the thing believed is probably true; *the dispositional theory* that we recognise our own beliefs by observing how we react to things; *the feeling theory* that belief is a particular feeling that comes to us and is a signal to us that we believe or think to be true the thing under consideration; and *eliminativism theories* that belief does not exist, but is an illusion of our language and culture.

Keywords: dispositional theory, eliminativist theory, feeling theory, intellectualist theory

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Bias

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Bias refers to a disproportionate inclination for or against an idea, person, thing, or group, often in a closed-minded, prejudicial, or unfair manner. Biases can be either innate or learned, and they influence how individuals think, feel, and behave toward others. They shape how people process, interpret, and recall information, and frequently reinforce existing beliefs rather than encouraging objective reasoning or openness to alternative perspectives.

A common example is confirmation bias, where individuals selectively seek out or interpret information in ways that support their pre-existing beliefs. Another related phenomenon is the narrative fallacy, in which people construct coherent but misleading stories from limited or incomplete information, often distorting reality in the process. These tendencies can lead to oversimplified or inaccurate understandings of complex issues.

Biases also manifest in the form of motivated reasoning or partisan bias, where new information is unconsciously filtered to align with one's prior political or ideological views. These psychological patterns are closely associated with cognitive heuristics—mental shortcuts that facilitate quick decision-making, particularly under conditions of time pressure or cognitive overload. While heuristics can be efficient, they may also contribute to flawed judgments and systematic misperceptions.

Importantly, biased individuals are not necessarily trying to mislead. Rather, they may present a skewed interpretation of reality that is shaped by subjective experiences and internalised cognitive patterns. Recognising these influences is essential for understanding how people form beliefs and make decisions. Therefore, a deeper understanding of the cognitive mechanisms underlying bias can enhance individuals' capacity for reflective information processing. This, in turn, supports more deliberate and informed decision-making across a range of social and political contexts.

Keywords: social psychology, heuristics, motivated reasoning

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Cognition/Cognitive Linguistics

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According to Von Eckardt, cognition refers to conscious mental action or process of acquiring *knowledge and understanding* through thought, experience, and the senses. Cognitive processes use existing knowledge and discover new knowledge. Cognitive linguistics is a school of linguistics and cognitive science which emerged from the early 1980s onwards; and Cognitive Linguistics places central importance on the role of meaning, conceptual processes and embodied experience in the study of language and the mind and the way in which they intersect. Cognitive linguistics is an enterprise or an approach to the study of language and the mind rather than a single articulated theoretical framework. It is informed by two overarching principles or commitments: the generalisation commitment and the cognitive commitment.

The two best developed sub-branches of cognitive linguistics are cognitive semantics and cognitive approaches to grammar. While cognitive linguistics began to emerge in the 1980s as a broadly grounded intellectual movement, it traces its roots to work that was taking place in the 1970s, particularly in the United States, which was reacting to formal linguistics. Early pioneers in the 1970s who were instrumental in formulating this new approach include Gilles Fauconnier, Charles Fillmore, George Lakoff, Ronald Langacker, and Leonard Talmy.

Keywords: cognitive commitment, formal linguistics, generalisation commitment, mind

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Cognitive Dissonance

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Cognitive dissonance theory developed in the late 1950s by US psychologist Leon Festinger refers to the psychological discomfort that arises from holding conflicting beliefs, attitudes, or behaviours simultaneously. It claims that people tend to avoid information and situations that are likely to increase dissonance. According to Festinger, pairs of cognitions (elements of knowledge) can be relevant or irrelevant to one another. If two cognitions are relevant to one another, they are either consonant or dissonant. Two cognitions are consonant if one follows from the other, and they are dissonant if the obverse (opposite) of one cognition follows from the other. To alleviate cognitive dissonance, individuals may engage in various cognitive and behavioural strategies, such as rationalisation, denial, or attitude change.

Festinger proposed strategies for dealing with a situation in which cognitive dissonance arises. First, when experiencing dissonance, and a feeling of psychological discomfort arises, the person will be motivated to try to reduce the dissonance and achieve consonance. For example, this underlying tension could motivate an individual to make an attitude change that would produce consistency between thoughts and behaviours.

Second, in addition to trying to reduce it, the person will actively avoid situations and information which would likely increase the dissonance for him/her.

Keywords: rationalisation, denial, attitude change

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Collectivisation

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Collectivisation is one of the types of representation of social actors proposed by van Leeuwen. It occurs when social actors are represented as part of the collective, a group with homogenous characteristic. Through de-emphasising heterogeneity of individuals, it helps to create a sense of solidarity, unity, or common cause through collective nouns (for example: 'our nation', 'our workers', 'our members'). It might contribute, however, to the discursive discrimination and exclusion by focusing on general, stereotypically represented features of individual aggregated as part of the larger group. Widely employed in the migration discourse ('bogus immigrants', 'illegal immigrants'), such representation might serve as a part of military or disaster metaphors emphasising external danger and eliciting fear.

From a Linguistics perspective, collectivisation refers to the process where languages and/or dialects fuse into a standardised form. This phenomenon usually occurs for socio-political reasons, such as part of nation-building efforts or language planning initiatives. The procedure may involve standardisation via a promotion of a certain linguistic/dialect variety through language policy that can result in language shift and a loss of linguistic diversity.

Note: The term collectivisation also has a different applied meaning frequently used by many as the process of organising individuals or resources into a collective or cooperative system. Russian collectivisation of its agricultural system under Stalin is often used as an example.

Keywords: collective, representation, homogeneity

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Communication

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Communication refers to the dynamic process through which information, meanings, and perspectives are exchanged and co-constructed among two or more participants. It encompasses verbal and non-verbal forms—including written, spoken, visual, and embodied modes such as gestures or symbolic cues—and is not limited to linguistic expression alone. As such, communication serves not only to transmit information but also to shape and negotiate social meanings and relationships according to Habermas. Communication is not limited to the exchange of information, but involves the construction of meaning and coordination of social behaviour. It presumes and constructs a system of shared semiotic codes, semantic constructs, and pragmatic behaviours that enable one participant to recognise the likely meaning of others' communicative behaviour. Rather than being a one-way channel, communication involves both the expression and reception of messages, enabling participants to align interpretations based on shared semiotic codes, pragmatic expectations, and contextual understanding. This alignment facilitates not only coordination of behaviour but also the evolution of individual and collective viewpoints. In the context of opinion expression, communication provides the primary mechanism through which individuals articulate, refine, and negotiate their perspectives. It creates opportunities for individuals to encounter alternative views, recognise disagreements, and, at times, arrive at shared or conflicting opinions. Communication thus plays a central role in both personal opinion formation and the collective negotiation of societal beliefs and attitudes.

From a sociocultural standpoint, scholars have long emphasised the role of mass communication in shaping public opinion. Lippmann as well as McCombs and Shaw, for instance, demonstrated how media structures public perception by framing agendas and influencing salience. With the rise of digital and interactive platforms, communication has become increasingly complex, blending mass and interpersonal elements. In sum, communication is not merely a tool for sharing opinions—it is a foundational mechanism through which opinions are formed, validated, and transformed within social contexts.

Keywords: information, meanings, semantic constructs

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Computational Linguistics

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Computational linguistics is a multidisciplinary field that integrates concepts from linguistics and computer science to create computational models and algorithms for comprehending, manipulating, and generating human language. Natural language processing encompasses the utilisation of computational techniques to examine, represent, and imitate different facets of language, such as syntax, semantics, pragmatics, and discourse. Computational linguistics is essential for enhancing our comprehension of language and developing useful applications related to human-computer interaction, language translation, information retrieval, and other domains. Professionals in this field frequently work together with specialists in linguistics, computer science, cognitive science, and related fields to tackle the intricate difficulties linked to the understanding and processing of natural language by machines.

Computational linguistics not only facilitates the development of practical applications but also improves our comprehension of language by tackling the numerous challenges and complexities inherent in the field of natural language processing. The difficulties encompass resolving ambiguity, managing linguistic variations and dialects, ensuring interpretation is context-sensitive, and incorporating domain-specific expertise into language processing systems. In addition, computational linguistics undergoes constant development to accommodate the ever-changing characteristics of language. This is achieved by integrating knowledge from cognitive science, corpus linguistics, and machine learning into language processing algorithms to improve their efficacy and flexibility. In light of the increasing need for intelligent language technologies, computational linguistics continues to be a leading area of study and advancement, influencing the development of artificial intelligence and enabling more intricate dialogues between humans and machines.

Keywords: word representation, static embeddings, contextual embeddings

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Confirmation Bias

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Confirmation bias is the tendency to seek, interpret, and remember information that supports existing beliefs while ignoring or minimising contradictory evidence. This bias is strongest in emotionally charged issues, desired outcomes, and deeply held beliefs. It manifests through selective information search—actively seeking only information that aligns with one’s views—biased interpretation, where ambiguous or mixed information is interpreted in a way that supports pre-existing beliefs, and memory bias, in which information confirming prior beliefs is better recalled while conflicting data is forgotten or downplayed.

Confirmation bias contributes to several cognitive and social phenomena, including attitude polarisation, where people become more extreme in their beliefs even when presented with the same evidence as others, and belief perseverance, in which individuals continue to believe something even after it has been clearly disproven. It also plays a role in the primacy effect, where early information is weighted more heavily than later evidence, and in the perception of false patterns, where individuals perceive relationships between unrelated events—for example, linking specific behaviors to group stereotypes without valid evidence.

This bias can lead to flawed decisions in everyday life, foster overconfidence, and increase resistance to corrective information. In research, it contributes to systematic errors by favoring supportive data while dismissing anomalies. On social media, algorithms amplify this bias by filtering content to match users’ preferences, creating echo chambers. The term was refined by psychologist Peter Wason, who demonstrated how individuals prefer confirming over disconfirming evidence. Unlike self-fulfilling prophecies that affect behavior, confirmation bias influences how information is processed—often automatically and unconsciously—making it difficult to recognise or overcome.

Keywords: beliefs, evidence, information

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Conjecture

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Conjecture is an opinion, judgment, or conclusion formed on the basis of incomplete information, through intuition or educated guessing. In other words, conjecture is a guess about something based on how it seems to be rather than on proof. Although it can serve as a starting point for further investigation and is formed through observation, pattern recognition, or logical reasoning, conjectures typically lack rigorous evidence or proof. Therefore, Deamer finds that contrasted with, for example, hypothesis, which refers to proposed explanation made on the basis of limited evidence as a starting point for further investigation, conjecture is more speculative and lacks evidence or proof. While Popper as well as Lakatos view conjectures, being speculative in nature, lack concrete evidence or proof, nevertheless, they can be valid in science (e.g., in the field of mathematics) and lead to new insights and discoveries when considered tentative solutions to a problem, and controlled by criticism, i.e., by attempted refutations, which include severely critical tests.

Keywords: evidence, guessing, intuition, pattern recognition, reasoning

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Context

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Context refers to the circumstances, background, or environment in which something exists or occurs. It provides additional information and helps to understand the meaning, relevance, or interpretation of a particular situation, event, or statement. The analysis of context forms part of most Critical Discourse Analysis and Pragmatic approaches. Van Dijk makes a distinction between *local contexts* which are 'properties of the immediate interactional situation in which a communicative event takes place' and *global contexts* which are 'defined by the social, political, cultural and historical structures in which a communicative event takes place'. Wodak identifies four levels of context that are used in the Discourse-Historical approach: 1. the immediate, language or text internal co-text; 2. the intertextual and interdiscursive relationship between utterances, texts, genres, and discourses; 3. the extralinguistic social/sociological variables and institutional frames of a specific 'context of situation' (middle-range theories); 4. the broader sociopolitical and historical contexts, in which the discursive practices are embedded in and related to (grand theories).

In Pragmatics, the *context* of an utterance is often thought of as everything that is available to be brought to bear on the utterance's interpretation, except the form and content of the phrase or sentence uttered (and any conventional meaning attached to gestures used). The context must also include facts about the speaker's and hearer's beliefs, opinions, habits, etc. This can be seen clearly in the recovery of implicatures, although it applies elsewhere too.

Referring to Sperber and Wilson's relevance-theoretic approach to pragmatics, 'context' refers to the cognitive environment in which communication takes place. It encompasses the shared knowledge, beliefs, assumptions, and expectations between the speaker and the hearer that are relevant to interpreting the meaning of an utterance.

Keywords: pragmatics, discourse analysis, cognitive.

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Contextual Embedding/Transformers

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Contextual embeddings, as opposed to context-free embeddings, consider the positioning of a word within a specific sentence or document. Transformers, a type of deep learning model, emerged as powerful tools in the creation of contextual embeddings. By employing the attention mechanism, transformers enable the model to assess the significance of distinct terms within a given sequence, thereby capturing complex contextual information. According to Devlin et al., the ability to comprehend context allows transformers, including BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) and GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer), to generate representations of words that are more comprehensive and subtle, taking into account their diverse meanings in various contexts (for example, the same sentence: 'The king smiled proudly.') A transformer would examine not only the co-occurrence of words, but also their order and relationships within the sentence. It could be inferred that 'smiled proudly' modifies 'king,' implying a positive, triumphant smile, putting 'king' in a different vector location than when used in a different context, such as 'The king ruled with an iron fist.' Transformers have made substantial strides in the field of natural language processing (NLP) by enabling models to comprehend intricate linguistic connections and interdependencies. As a result, they have proven to be exceptionally efficient in a vast array of applications, including question answering and text summarisation.

Keywords: attention mechanism, word representations, deep learning, NLP

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Controversy

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Controversy describes a discursive situation wherein multiple participants express divergent opinions toward a common object, resulting in sustained disagreement. At its core, controversy focuses on which out of multiple incompatible views can be regarded as valid.

Classically, controversies focus on divergent evaluations of a common object, wherein positive and negative stances are expressed by different participants. Controversies can also revolve around divergent interpretations, or discrepant priorities for addressing a common issue. Controversies can involve direct disagreement (i.e., one opinion affirms what another denies), or divergent frames applied to the same object (i.e., foregrounding different aspects, which point toward contrasting conclusions). Controversies may be limited to binary disagreement, or involve a multiplicity of incompatible stances. For controversy to exist, it is usually sufficient that competing opinions are constructed as incompatible, even if they may not be formally irreconcilable. In borderline cases, one side constructs a controversy by opposing a position that is not actually advocated by anyone, reinterpreting others' statements as if these presented an opposing view.

Controversy requires some degree of discursive interaction within a common arena, which may be indirect: Participants may dialogically address one another (e.g., face-to-face, tagged/threaded replies on digital media) or merely react to other participants' prior statements or broader positions (e.g., expressing dissenting views in the same public, with or without explicit reference to contested claims), without need for temporal synchronisation or co-presence.

Controversy is enacted before an audience, enabling third parties to observe and potentially designate the controversy as such. Moreover, controversy implies that disagreement persists and is neither resolved nor otherwise settled (e.g., via compromise, or by excluding dissenters from the debate). Controversy ends when a resolution is found (by compromise, one side winning), or when participants disengage, ceding their efforts to convert or defeat dissenters (e.g., agreeing to disagree, ceasing to acknowledge disagreement).

Keywords: disagreement, public discourse, issues

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Cooperative Principle

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In linguistics and the social sciences, the *Cooperative Principle* refers to the idea that conversational participants generally work together to achieve mutual understanding. That is, they engage in conversation in such a way that participants can arrive at a common understanding of what each is trying to communicate. To this end, it is necessary that speakers say (and listeners can trust them to say) things that are relevant, informative without being redundant, truthful, and clear. Listeners, in turn, should (and speakers can trust them to) try to interpret the speaker's meaning in a similarly cooperative manner.

In its formulation by Paul Grice, the Cooperative Principle involves four Conversational Maxims—concerning the quantity, quality, relevance, and manner of speech—that cannot be reduced to mere etiquette or politeness, but can be understood as expectations that govern rational, cooperative communication: 1. Maxim of Quantity - Say as much as is needed, but not more. 2. Maxim of Quality - Do not say what you believe to be false or lack sufficient evidence for. 3. Maxim of Relevance - Be relevant to the exchange (distinct from the separate *Principle of Relevance* in relevance theory). 4. Maxim of Manner - Be clear, brief, and orderly; avoid obscurity or ambiguity. According to the Cooperative Principle, speakers and listeners are assumed to contribute meaningfully to the exchange, enabling communication to be efficient and effective.

While each maxim can be flouted for various rhetorical or pragmatic reasons—such as irony, sarcasm, or indirect speech—effective communication breaks down when it becomes clear that the Cooperative Principle is being systematically violated. Speakers may also opt out of a maxim or face a clash of maxims when different conversational expectations compete.

To account for cultural variation in conversational norms, Mey introduces the more inclusive term Communicative Principle, which encompasses both the Cooperative Principle and the Principle of Relevance. He argues that Grice's maxims cannot be universally applied, as different cultures may adhere to different conceptions of what cooperation in communication entails.

Keywords: conversational maxims, communication, relevance

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Cotext

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The term cotext does not always appear as a standalone entry in general dictionaries, but its meaning is closely related to commonly accepted definitions of context. These typically include: (1) 'the situation in which something happens and that helps you to understand it,' and (2) 'the words that come just before and after a word, phrase or statement and help you to understand its meaning.' Although there is no consensus on its definition, cotext refers to the linguistic part of the context that plays an essential role in interpreting statements. The field of linguistics known as pragmatics studies the interaction between language and the context in which it is used.

There are two types of cotext. The strict cotext consists of the other elements of the proposition and is used to resolve syntactic ambiguities. This is particularly important for determining the grammatical relationships between words, as it can clarify issues such as subject-verb agreement, reference, and word sense disambiguation. Collocations, which refer to the frequent use of two or more words together, are studied within this field. The interphrasal cotext comprises the other utterances produced in the conversation and plays a crucial role in interpreting intentions. For example, the sentence 'I didn't say she stole the money' can be interpreted in different ways depending on which part is emphasised, a distinction that can only be understood through co(n)text. Understanding intentions is the cornerstone of interpreting any utterance, as Grice points out. Grice's theory of implicature emphasises that speakers often convey more than is explicitly stated, and that the co(n)text is crucial for inferring these additional meanings.

Keywords: collocation, intentions, discourse analysis

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Critical Discourse Analysis

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Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is an already well-established transdisciplinary, heterogenous, discourse-analytical approach to discourse which views language in terms of social practice. It combines research conducted in linguistics, social sciences, and political and media sciences. The goal of CDA is to seek, raise awareness, and de/legitimise social issues of discrimination, patterns of dominance, power imbalance, or ideology with the view to improve social injustice by analysing language used in opinionated, persuasive, and manipulative texts, primarily in the media. Media discourse, on the one hand, reflects the social structures, political situations, and institutions and, on the other, invokes changes in this sphere. The language thus reflects social reality; but at the same time, it moulds it and can impose patterns of power and dominance. While uncovering social issues, CDA is not confined to language, as it also explores semiotic symbols and multimodal resources (visual and auditory elements). There are several CDA schools, which rely on distinct theoretical frameworks and resort to various methodologies. Within the main approaches, there are also: Discourse-Historical Approach by Reisigl and Wodak, socio-cognitive by van Dijk, cognitive science by Chilton, or the dialectical-relational approach by Fairclough. Van Leeuwen proposed a schema of various so-called social actors, which situate subjects in the social-political-economic reality and label them according to the role they play in society, e.g., genericisation, functionalisation, nomination, predication (the last two are also elaborated by Reisigl and Wodak), etc.

Keywords: discourse-analytical approach, media discourse, multimodal

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Culture

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Culture can be broadly defined as the set of shared knowledge, beliefs, customs, values, norms, symbols, and practices that are transmitted socially within a group. According to Edward B. Tylor, culture is that complex whole which includes knowledge, belief, art, morals, law, custom, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a member of society. Pierre Bourdieu expanded on this by demonstrating that culture is not neutral but is deeply embedded in systems of power. Through the concept of 'habitus', he explained how individuals internalise cultural norms in relation to their social position. Culture thus becomes a tool of social reproduction, whereby dominant groups impose their tastes, languages, and forms of legitimacy, often rendering other expressions invisible or illegitimate. In digital contexts, culture appears to be more open and participatory, with social media enabling a wide range of users to express themselves. However, this apparent horizontality hides underlying asymmetries. While some voices gain visibility and influence, others — particularly marginalised or minoritised groups — are silenced, overlooked, or subjected to platform-specific forms of algorithmic invisibility. Furthermore, the digital realm introduces a new top-down logic where cultural production is shaped not only by traditional institutions such as the media, education, and government, but also increasingly by commercial platforms. This dual pressure, from both institutions and commerce, reconfigures the production, distribution, and valuation of culture online. As Bourdieu might suggest, in the digital age, symbolic power is maintained not only through social distinction, but also through algorithmic and market-driven mechanisms that reinforce certain norms while excluding others.

Keywords: power relations, user-generated content, algorithmic governance.

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Data/Dataset

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Data encompasses individual pieces of information, such as factual details and numerical values, which are gathered, analysed, and interpreted to convey meaning or comprehension. It can be expressed in different formats, such as numbers, text, images, sounds, symbols, or any other measurable or descriptive value.

A dataset is a systematically compiled set of associated data that is generally acquired for a particular intent, such as research, machine learning model training, or analysis. By organising data elements in a predetermined format, such as matrices, tables, or records, dataset facilitates identification, interpretation, and investigation of patterns and connections with greater efficiency. Datasets frequently comprise supplementary information, known as metadata, which furnishes contextual details regarding the sources of the data, methods of collection, definitions of variables, and limitations on usage.

Datasets are crucial in multiple domains, since they form the basis for empirical investigations, algorithmic advancements, and decision-making procedures. They exist in various forms and quantities, ranging from modest, carefully selected collections to extensive reservoirs of information obtained from multiple sources. Aside from conventional organised datasets that conform to a predetermined schema, unstructured datasets including text documents, pictures, and multimedia files are becoming more widespread. The presence of extensive datasets, commonly known as 'big data', offers both advantages and difficulties, as academics and professionals strive to derive significant observations while confronting concerns regarding data accuracy, privacy, and scalability. Furthermore, the continuous progress in data collection technologies, including sensors, IoT devices, and web scraping techniques, consistently broaden the range and complexity of accessible information, fostering innovation and influencing the field of data-driven decision-making.

Keywords: information, metadata

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Discourse (1)

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Discourse serves as both an area and a mechanism for the formation of diverse opinions. It is the entirety of messages in social circulation, thus both the area of communication in everyday life, i.e. colloquial discourse (e.g. conversations at the family table, phone conversations of friends), and the area of communication within institutions, that is, various institutional discourses (e.g. a court hearing, a teacher's council meeting), the areas of communication specific to certain 'social worlds' (e.g. literary evenings, business meetings, conversations of members of the punk subculture), as well as the area of mass media (e.g. daily newspaper or TV talk-show). Discourse encompasses broad areas and thematic fields that make up this overall phenomenon. There are different types of discourse. Public discourse contains all messages available to the public, including institutional discourse, discourse of specific 'social worlds', or mass media discourse. Media discourse comprises media-mediated discourses (they are characterised by specific traits and communicative behaviour of message senders). Political discourse relates to politicians' speeches in the framework of the roles to which they were assigned within political institutions, and statements made by individuals of the power elite, if related to their political roles and functions. Elite discourse relates to the discourse of authorities in the so-called symbolic sphere (journalists, writers, scholars, civil servants, intellectuals, experts, business representatives, and politicians - that are present in the media), to the cultural-normative control of public discourse.

Keywords: communication, conversations, media-mediated

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Discourse (2)

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Studying discourse in linguistics is essential because it helps us understand language as a social tool, not just as a system of rules. It bridges language, meaning, culture and communication, making it one of the most dynamic areas of linguistics today. Discourse is generally defined as written or spoken communication or debate on a particular topic. As such, it includes conversations, discussions, and dialogues where ideas are exchanged.

As a formal and orderly expression of thought, discourse refers to a connected series of utterances or writings on a particular subject or a conversation or discussion, especially one of a serious or intellectual nature, that delves into a specific topic. Additionally, it involves organising knowledge, ideas, or experience based on language and its concrete contexts such as political discourse, media discourse, or environmental discourse.

In Discourse Analysis, Brown and Yule refer to discourse as any form of 'language in use' or naturally occurring language. Stubbs conceives discourse as 'language above the sentence or above the clause' and makes a distinction between discourse, which is interactive, and text, which is a non-interactive monologue. Some scholars have conceived of discourse as related to particular topics, such as environmental discourse or colonial discourse (which may occur in many different genres). Foucault defines discourse more ideologically as 'practices which systematically form the objects of which they speak'.

Potter and Wetherell have shown that people often appear to voice conflicting opinions around a topic, which they argue is due to them accessing a range of competing discourses in their talk. Discourses are therefore contradictory and shifting, and their identification is necessarily interpretative and open to contestation, particularly as it is difficult to 'step outside' discourse and view it with complete objectivity.

In Pragmatics, 'Discourse' can be defined as a series of connected utterances, producing either a written text or a spoken exchange; although on some conceptions it is more global, and also includes other texts in the same genre as the one being studied, previous conversations, etc.

Keywords: utterances, language, interaction

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Disinformation

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Disinformation refers to the spread of fabricated or misleading information that poses a serious concern in the digital age where content can be disseminated quickly and widely. It is a form of information disorder that refers to the intentional spread of fabricated or misleading information to influence and shape people's perceptions and viewpoints. Disinformation can take various forms, including false articles, manipulated images or videos, misleading narratives, and deceptive social media campaigns. It tends to accomplish particular objectives, such as influencing public opinion, eroding institutional confidence, or even causing strife within society. The deliberate dissemination of false or misleading information has the potential to skew public perceptions of events, problems, and people in the digital age, as information is shared quickly through a variety of online platforms. Disinformation operations deliberately aim to sway the beliefs of their target audiences, frequently for ideological, social, economic or political reasons. This information manipulation can distort reality and cause people to establish beliefs based on false premises. The ease of creating or modifying information is increased by digital technology. Text-generating models and deepfakes are two examples of AI-generated content that might further blur the distinction between truth and falsity. It takes a team effort to combat disinformation in opinion formation, including critical thinking techniques, media literacy, and steps to assure the validity and dependability of information sources. As the landscape evolves, efforts to address disinformation must also consider the role of AI and explore technological solutions that can enhance the resilience of societies against the manipulative impact of AI-driven disinformation. Moreover, collaborative efforts among different actors, such as educators, platforms, professional organisations, and civil society are crucial to building societal resilience.

Keywords: manipulation, AI, propaganda

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Echo Chamber

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A space, including the media space, in which individuals with similar political or social beliefs gather in strongly connected and isolated groups. In such communities, individuals strengthen their beliefs by exchanging information and views only with people who share their position (e.g., people on the right not coming across centrist or left-wing perspectives that challenge their pre-existing opinions). This leads to the mutual reinforcement and maintenance of the same beliefs, regardless of the diversity of the views within the broader society.

The term echo chamber is sometimes used interchangeably with the term filter bubble. However, one needs to distinguish between these two. An echo chamber is a form of bubble, but the term does not prejudge why some people might live in such bubbles. For example, some people actively avoid cross-cutting exposure. Therefore, the situation is a result of demand more than distribution or supply. A filter bubble, on the other hand, is an echo chamber primarily produced by ranking algorithms engaged in passive personalization without any active choice on the part of the media users. For example, AI-based systems generate content tailored to user preferences (echo chambers), which in turn affects the dynamics of information flow. Hence, it is a possible outcome of specific aspects of how news and information are distributed online. The partisan echo chambers are one of the drivers of both policy and affective polarization. By surrounding ourselves, both in real life and online, with others who share similar perspectives and opinions about the world, we amplify tribalism and exacerbate societal and political polarization.

Keywords: filter bubble, news avoidance, polarization

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Emotions

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Various academic fields have approached the study of emotions in different ways. We will focus here on philosophy and psychology. Traditionally, philosophers have focused on the subjective experience of emotions. This perspective is exemplified in the definition of emotions as all those things through which people change and evolve in their judgments, accompanied by pain (e.g., pity, fear, terror) or pleasure (e.g., desire, hope). In the Cartesian tradition, emotions are naturally good, and they incline the soul to desire the things that benefit the body. In contrast, Spinoza views negative emotions as signs of human passivity and diminished power, considering them problematic when they result from external causes that limit our rational autonomy. Hochschild argues that emotions are not merely private experiences but are shaped by 'feeling rules' reflecting cultural norms and institutional expectations. Psychologists have studied the physiological and behavioural components of emotions. William James defined emotion as the 'consciousness by the subject of bodily modifications triggered by the apprehension of certain objects or facts.' In other words, crying does not stem from sadness but rather generates it. Ekman posits that emotions are subjective experiences, physiologically driven states, and expressive behaviours resulting from internal or external stimuli. Ekman's research has demonstrated that humans from all cultures express six fundamental emotions - joy, sadness, anger, fear, surprise, and disgust - in similar ways. Plutchik expanded this theory by identifying four primary emotions (fear, anger, joy, and sadness), which can combine with cognitive processes such as memory and reflection to generate secondary emotions.

Keywords: emotional theory; physiological response; cognitive appraisal

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Emotions in Political Opinion

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Emotions play a major role in shaping people's views on specific policies as well as their perceptions of political processes and systems. For instance, empathy may lead to support for social welfare policies, but fear or mistrust may spur opposition to particular proposals. In contrast to fearful citizens who perceive more risks and anticipate a greater need for precautionary measures, angry citizens see fewer risks and feel less urgency for precautions. People who are angry often vent their frustrations and assign blame, which can weaken their trust in political figures and institutions. Angry citizens are more likely to favour punitive measures, whereas afraid citizens are more likely to favour policies that are accommodating and protective. Similarly, anxiety can make people more reluctant to compromise on policies, while anger can make people less open to considering alternative viewpoints. Emotions also have an impact on how message framing influences political communication. Anxiety makes people more sensitive to environmental cues, which increases the effects of framing, whereas excitement and rage reduce context awareness, which lessens the effects of framing.

Emotions cause different cognitive processing styles. Anger encourages heuristic processing, whereas sadness encourages systematic processing of information. In order to directly and indirectly influence public opinion, political leaders and organisations deliberately use emotions in their communications. The purpose of emotional appeals in political speeches, campaign ads, and debates is to connect with the voters and strengthen efforts at mobilisation and persuasion. This deliberate use of emotion illustrates how the emotional terrain of the electorate affects political structures and procedures in addition to interests and compromises.

Keywords: emotions, emotional appeals, persuasion

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Emotion Display Norms in Politics

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Emotion display norms are the socially acceptable ways that members of a particular culture or society express their emotions and control them when voicing their opinions. Expectations about the appropriateness and intensity of emotional displays vary among cultures; for example, some value restraint, while others promote openness. Additionally, context affects how acceptable it is to express emotions. In contrast to casual settings with friends or family, formal events such as public gatherings or workplaces usually require more controlled displays. Through their interactions with family, peers, and larger cultural influences, people internalise emotional display norms, learning early on what is considered rewarding and socially acceptable. Political groups may have different standards for displaying emotions. Conservatives may differ from what is considered an appropriate emotional opinion expression in progressive circles. Politicians need to be mindful of these differences because public opinion is frequently influenced by emotional authenticity. Voters connect with genuine emotion, but displays that are viewed as fake might be harmful for the candidate's credibility. Strategic emotional expressions are frequent in political communication, especially during public speeches and debates. Political leaders are under pressure to show compassion, sorrow, or thankfulness during emergencies or trying times. On the other hand, underexpressing emotions can be perceived as cold, while overexpressing them can give the impression that one lacks self-control. Adherence to emotion norms is made more difficult by gender stereotypes. While men might be perceived as weak for displaying vulnerability, women may find it difficult to overcome stereotypes that characterise them as being too emotional or lacking in authority. Effective communication requires navigating the conventions surrounding the display of emotions. Politicians frequently work with communication specialists to adjust their tactics to changing public expectations while striking a balance between cultural norms and authenticity.

Keywords: emotions, norms, gender

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Epistemic Community

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Two basic theoretical stances can help one approach the idea of an epistemic community: the soft constructivist approach in international relations and the interpretive-constructivist tradition. Although their emphasis and disciplinary roots differ, both points of view stress the central part that common knowledge, norms, and interpretive frameworks play in forming collective understanding, guiding social activities, and so affecting political results.

Inspired by cultural studies and the sociology of knowledge, the interpretive-constructivist approach sees epistemic communities as interpretive communities—groups bound together by common cultural texts, symbolic codes, belief systems, and interpretive practices. Scholars like Stanley Fish and Clifford Geertz stress that, using common symbolic resources, meaning is co-created inside communities rather than fixed or universal. Epistemic communities are essential in building, copying, and justifying particular ontological domains or worldviews. These readings eventually become naturalised, accepted as self-evident facts, so supporting the internal standards and epistemic power of the society.

On the other hand, the soft constructivist approach in international relations emphasises the agency of expert players in negotiating world complexity and uncertainty. This viewpoint looks at how professional networks and knowledgeable people create and spread ideas that influence policy decisions, transcending discursive structures. In this context, Peter M. Haas defines epistemic communities as networks of professionals with acknowledged expertise who share a set of principled and causal beliefs, standards for validating knowledge, and a common policy enterprise orientated towards practical problem-solving. Both causal reasoning and normative frameworks in public policymaking are greatly informed by these communities. Modern media studies draw on both of these points of view. On social media platforms, people group around common interests, co-create meaning, and distribute policy-relevant information. These digital environments show how epistemic influence now functions via both interpretive and strategic processes, so bridging cultural sense-making with expert-driven intervention in public discourse.

Keywords: constructivism, discourse, interpretation

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Epistemic/Truth

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Opinions can be differentiated based on a variety of qualities, with one aspect being their epistemic quality. The epistemic quality refers to the certainty with which a person believes that a statement about the past, present, or a potential future is true. The epistemic status of opinions thus distinguishes what people believe to be facts from what they see as speculations.

A central point of departure for research on the epistemic quality of opinions is the philosophical tradition of epistemology. This field is concerned with theorising whether and how individuals can access reality to construct knowledge and beliefs. Scholars working on epistemology can be placed on a continuum between extreme skepticism (e.g., constructivism), which claims that knowledge is entirely mediated and that objective reality is inaccessible, and everyday realism that is certain about our access to the factual world.

One focus of empirical research on the epistemic quality of statements revolves around their potential impact on recipients. In this context, prospect theory has provided valuable insights into the behavioural consequences of diverse epistemic outlooks on potential loss and gain. It highlights that individuals tend to prefer a certain outcome with a lower expected gain over a risky choice with a higher expected gain.

Research on the epistemic quality of public discourse is focused on what has been termed an 'epistemic crisis' in democratic debate. This is grounded in the observation that the traditional linear knowledge-order process, where journalism served as the primary intermediary between elites and audiences, has changed into a more dynamic process, in which elites can directly engage with the audience. Combined with substantial changes in the political and societal environment, this has led to what is often referred to as a 'post-truth society' where the epistemic status of statements is more contested than ever before.

Keywords: epistemic quality, post-truth society, epistemology, knowledge, opinion formation

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Evaluative Language

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Thompson and Hunston state that evaluative language expresses the speaker's personal, evaluative opinions (viewpoint or feelings) on an entity (e.g., some objects, events, behaviour, people, etc) in terms of being good or bad, by ascribing some value to the entity described. There are two more functions of evaluative language: constructing relations between the sender and the receiver and organising discourse. The former are realised, for example, by means of manipulation, hedging, and politeness. The three necessary conditions for evaluative language comprise presence of the object of description in a sentence, value-laden words (emotivity), and subjectivity. Two approaches to evaluative language can be distinguished: attitudinal (encoded by adjectives, morphological affixes, words, and phrases) and modality-oriented (grammaticalised, encoding likelihood). According to Bednarek, evaluative language comprises, inter alia, such categories of description as: comprehensibility (*clear, complicated*), expectedness (*surprisingly, obviously*), emotivity (*anger, praise*), importance (*crucial, insignificant*), im/possibility (*could*), necessity (*must*), reliability (*fake, genuine*), and evidentiality (*proof that, he said it was*). Evaluative language is also elaborated by the Appraisal Theory, which was one of the sources from which Bednarek's evaluative language evolved. The term evaluative language is sometimes used interchangeably with the term stance, which is, however, more often applied to corpus-informed studies revolving around lexicogrammatical structures that encode evaluation. Two most common structures have been identified to signal stance: adverbials and complement clause constructions.

Keywords: appraisal theory, subjectivity, emotivity

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Evidence

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Evidence describes one out of a range of potential foundations of an opinion. More specifically, evidence refers to the available facts that indicate whether a belief or statement is valid, true, or credible. As such, opinions founded in evidence can be understood as statements about social reality that are backed up by some form of evidential reference. These references can be differentiated in diverse types, including empirical evidence, statistical evidence, anecdotal evidence, and testimonial evidence. As such, sources can be understood as a specific type of evidence.

In general, research on the effects of evidence-based communication suggests that evidence-based statements tend to have stronger persuasive effects compared to evidence-free information since they are perceived as more credible. Moreover, the credibility and persuasiveness of evidence-based opinions also depend on both the characteristics of the associated type of evidence and individual predispositions towards the provided information and the specific type of evidence.

Content analytical research focuses on how different actors in public discourse apply evidence in their communication to convince the public or more specific societal subgroups (i.e. journalists) of their grievances. Scholars have conceptualised the public sphere as a competitive evidence environment in which a variety of societal actors or groups compete over epistemic authority.

Lately, there is a growing concern about the so-called post factual age in which manufactured, false, or manipulated forms of evidence are used to back up misinformation. These ‘alternative facts’ are provided to construct an alternative version of reality that can oftentimes hardly be supported by existing conventional evidence.

Keywords: evidence-based communication, epistemic authority, post-factual age

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Evidentiality

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Evidentiality is the foundation upon which speakers present information—more especially, how they mark the source or dependability of what they say. It is different from evidentials, the language signals indicating how knowledge was obtained—direct observation, inference, or hearsay. These markers affect not only the apparent power of a statement but also how speakers express responsibility, authority, and certainty.

Understanding how speakers control credibility and stance in communication depends on knowing evidentiality. In social and institutional settings, as well as in meaning-making and persuasion, it is central. Two well-known methods assist to define this idea. The functional-pragmatic approach emphasises clear evidentials as discourse aids to support assertions. Such markers, as Bednarek notes, comprise references to sources, mental-state verbs like ‘I believe’, and sensory verbs like ‘I saw.’ This point of view tightly connects epistemic responsibility and evidentiality to speaker posture.

By contrast, connected with Aikhenvald, the typological-semantic approach sees evidentiality as a grammatical and semantic category. It arranges evidentials according to the kind of evidence offered—direct visual perception, non-visual sensory input, inference, assumption, hearsay, or quotation—each reflecting a different way of grounding knowledge in language.

Beyond classification, one should also be able to separate informational value from evidential value. While evidential value relates to the capacity of material to be proof or justification, informational value relates to its relevance or novelty. In investigative journalism, for instance, information is assessed not only on what it exposes but also on how consistently it is obtained and how successfully it supports assertions or questions authority. Thus, both linguistic study and the larger dynamics of knowledge and persuasion depend on evidentiality as fundamental.

Keywords: evidentiality markers, semantic dimensions, epistemic stance

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Explicit/Explicitness

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The term ‘explicit’ is frequently employed in a technical sense, especially within the fields of linguistics and pragmatics. Grice defines the notion of ‘what is said’, a concept especially relevant within the fields of linguistics and pragmatics. This is distinct from ‘what is implied’, which encompasses implicit information that is not directly stated but is instead inferred by the listener through contextual cues and background knowledge. Specifically, Carston posits that explicitness is a semantic matter, directly tied to the linguistic content of an utterance, while implicitness deals with pragmatics, relying on context and shared knowledge for interpretation. Carston further introduces the concept of explicature, a key notion in pragmatics, which refers to an enriched interpretation of an utterance that goes beyond its literal linguistic form but remains part of the explicitly communicated content. This enrichment is achieved through context-dependent inferences that complete or clarify what is directly expressed. Building on this distinction, Sperber and Wilson emphasise that explicitness is not an absolute concept but rather a matter of degree. According to them, the more a linguistic code contributes to the interpretation of an utterance, the higher the degree of explicitness. An explicit utterance, such as ‘*The Earth revolves around the Sun*’, presents all the necessary information for understanding, without requiring any additional contextual information. By contrast, an utterance like ‘It’s getting chilly’ requires the listener to rely on contextual clues to fully grasp its meaning. Depending on the situation, it could imply a desire to close a window, an invitation to move indoors, or simply an observation about the temperature.

Keywords: clues, meaning, information

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Expressive Language/Emotional Function of Language

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Roman Jakobson's 1960 theory of language functions identifies six types of communication. They are: expressive, conative, phatic, referential, metalinguistic, and poetic. The expressive function, also called the emotive function, is about expressing the speaker's emotions, feelings, or attitudes. This can be seen in statements like 'I am tired', where the speaker is expressing a personal state. John Searle also looked at the expressive function in the context of speech acts. He says that expressions like apologies, congratulations, and praise are categorised as expressive acts. These acts may not necessarily reflect sincere emotions but convey the speaker's feelings or reactions towards an event, behaviour, or situation.

Emotions play a crucial role in communication, as they allow individuals to adjust their interactions with others. Primary emotions like joy, anger, sadness, disgust, surprise, and fear are experienced the same way across different cultures. Secondary emotions are formed from primary emotions. But different cultures and languages suggest different interpretations of emotional experiences, which means that emotional expressions may differ based on context and societal norms.

When we communicate digitally, we often must find new ways to express emotions, because we do not have the non-verbal cues that we are used to in face-to-face conversation. This might be emoticons, punctuation, or special words like acronyms or interjections which shows how important it is to be able to express emotions in digital communication, even when there are limits to the medium.

Keywords: emotions, non-verbal communication, communication adjustment

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Face

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The concept of ‘face’ was introduced by Erving Goffman and later developed by Brown and Levinson to refer to the positive public image an individual seeks to establish in a given social interaction. In linguistics, it is associated with the concepts of ‘face theory’, ‘politeness theory’, and especially with the approach of pragmatics. Face represents a person’s sense of self-esteem, dignity, and social value, which is a dynamic category. Face can be maintained, threatened, lost, or enhanced in a social interaction through different face-saving strategies. For instance, hedges, indirectness, and tag questions are used to reduce imposition and thus face-threatening behaviour. Face involves two related aspects: positive face and negative face. Positive face refers to the person’s need that their self-image is appreciated and approved of by interlocutors. Negative face refers to the person’s need not to be impeded or imposed by other interactants and the need to maintain their freedom of action.

Because maintaining face is a collaborative effort between interlocutors, this concern for mutual understanding and social harmony is also reflected in broader theories of conversation. One such framework is the Cooperative Principle, proposed by Paul Grice, which suggests that participants in a conversation need to cooperate to maintain the face of both the speaker and the hearer. However, this principle has been critiqued in later theories suggesting that cooperation is not strictly necessary. Instead, it is proposed that coordination, perceived as some rational adjustments to the interlocutors’ needs and goals, is sufficient for successful communication.

Face management strategies vary across cultures and languages, making the concept especially relevant in cross-cultural pragmatics. For example, cultures that prioritise group harmony may favor indirect speech acts and deferential language to preserve both positive and negative face. More individualistic cultures, meanwhile, might permit more direct communication.

Keywords: positive face, negative face, politeness theory

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Face-saving Act

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In communication, people are constantly involved in face-work, understood as the speakers' attempts to have or maintain a certain image of themselves or other participants of the interaction. The aim of engaging in face-work is to address potential incidents or occurrences that pose a potential threat to one's social image. To avoid harm for one's face, face-saving acts are performed to mitigate the potential effect on one's self-image or the hearer's image. Different individuals, subcultures and societies have different means for face saving.

The repertoire of face-saving resources also depends on the type of face speakers aim to protect. To protect or appeal to someone's positive face, speakers may resort to such strategies as exaggerating (interest, approval, sympathy with the hearer), being optimistic, intensifying interest to the hearer (exaggerating facts, telling stories in present tense), using in-group identity markers (e.g. in-group address forms), making offers and promises, complimenting the hearer, agreeing with the hearer's point of view, or giving gifts.

Typical face-saving strategies used to protect one's negative face include such negative politeness strategies as hedging and indirectness, using nominalisations, minimising or avoiding imposition on the hearer, apologising, and being pessimistic. In intercultural communication, face-saving strategies vary significantly. In high-context cultures (e.g. Japan, Korea) indirectness, silence, deference, and avoidance can function as powerful face-saving mechanisms; whereas in low-context cultures (e.g. the U.S., Germany), verbal elaboration and a higher degree of directness are more typical. Additionally, digital communication introduces new modalities for face-saving, as users often rely on emojis, hedges, or humour to reduce face threat and maintain politeness in the absence of tone or body language.

Keywords: face-work, positive face, negative face

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Face-threatening Act

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Face threatening acts (FTAs) are a focus of politeness theory developed by Brown and Levinson. When speakers communicate with others in a crude or offensive way or impede their personal freedoms, they commit face-threatening acts. A face-threatening act is defined as an act that challenges or damages a person's face wants. Face-threatening acts may threaten either the speaker's or the listener's face, and either positive or negative face. When speakers admit and apologise for their own shortcomings, they commit face-threatening acts directed at themselves. When speakers criticise, disagree with the hearer, or impose on their freedom, they threaten the hearer's face.

Acts that threaten the listener's negative face include such acts as making a request or making a threat. Damage to the speaker's negative face can be caused in interaction when the speaker is obliged to perform such acts as apologising, confessing a fault, or expressing gratitude. Acts that can harm the listener's positive face include criticism, disapproval, complaints, accusations, disagreements, taboo topics, interruptions, insults, etc. FTAs threatening the speaker's positive face include apologies, loss of emotional control, self-criticism, confession, etc.

Such face-work suggests that during social interaction cooperation is needed between interlocutors to maintain the face of both the speaker and of the listener(s). Face-threatening acts can be verbal (the content of the message, word choices, and linguistic patterns used), paraverbal (the tone, pacing, and volume of the speaker's voice), or non-verbal (facial expressions or body language). In digital communication, FTAs may also be conveyed through written tone, punctuation, emojis, or the absence of a response, which is often interpreted as intentional silence and thus can pose a threat to the interlocutor's face.

Keywords: face, politeness, cooperation

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Fact

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Facts are assumed to be the objects of mental states and acts. There is often a question of a relationship between facts and truth. There are numerous scholars juxtaposing these two concepts. A fact is, for Russell, for example, a part of reality. Russell holds that 'humanism unconsciously admits the objective sense of truth, the sense which may be called fact. For it must be the fact that our purposes are furthered by entertaining the belief' (1907/2014: 462). Frege proposes that facts are true truth-bearers. He writes in 1918 that a 'fact is a thought that is true'. A fact is thus a statement that can be proven or verified, though it is not logically disputed or rejected, while truth is a broader concept that can include subjective beliefs and experiences. Facts are objective and based on evidence, while truth can be subjective and based on personal perspective. Facts are concrete and verifiable, while truth can be abstract and open to interpretation.

A fact is a statement that can be proven true or false based on empirical evidence or objective reality. Truth is a broader, more philosophical concept, referring to the state or quality of being in accord with fact or reality; and it can be subjective or intersubjective based on perception or belief systems. Truth is more of a subjective situation that depends on current issues and challenges. A fact is a confirmed observation situation while truth is related to beliefs. While facts are proven identities, truths are based on values and beliefs. For example, Ten Hagen considers both truth and fact to be fluid concepts, inviting different interpretations and roles of facts in different contexts.

Keywords: belief, truth, verification

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Fact-checking

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Verification through systematic methods serves to check the accuracy and truthfulness of official statements made by public figures, politicians, or the media. The practice of fact-checking began to take shape in the United States during the early 1990s, emerging in response to political television advertisements that proliferated during election periods. At the initial stage fact-checkers dedicated their efforts to analysing deliberate exaggerations within television broadcast political announcements, particularly those intended to influence voters during election campaigns. By the mid-2020s, fact-checking organisations had expanded globally, and 170 organisations addressed both official statements and online misinformation and disinformation across many countries. The groups now actively engage with information coming from various unofficial sources, including social media posts and viral content, because these forms of unverified content spread quickly before people can validate or counter them. There are two basic steps that need to be followed in the factual verification process: identification of claims to be evaluated and gathering credible evidence for claims to be measured for accuracy. Some facts may consist of government documents or speeches, or expert-driven reports; in this regard the facts are taken as acceptable evidence in the fact checking process. Fact-checking has dual functions which include fact correction but also functions to counter the false information that result from intentional disinformation as well as by accident through misinformation. In a world flooded with misinformation and disinformation, fact checking is one of main solutions, ensuring that the debate is taken out of the situations and a decision is made on the basis of info available to people in the era of information overload.

Keywords: verification, truth

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Fake News/Misinformation

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The issue of fake news has become a critical topic in contemporary media studies, encompassing a variety of forms of misinformation. According to the Urban Dictionary, fake news refers to content disseminated by news organisations that contains dishonesty, often to promote a political agenda. Fake news can manifest itself in several categories, such as outright lies, omission of critical information, manipulation of emotional appeals, and selective outrage, all of which are intended to mislead or manipulate the audience.

Scholars have emphasised the growing importance of language in the realm of fake news. As noted by Doutreix and Barbe, traditional media actors use normative tools to identify reliable sources, highlighting the need for professional practices in the face of rising misinformation. According to Oustinoff, the political context of fake news is particularly relevant as leaders such as Trump, Bolsonaro, Orban, and Salvini use language not only to communicate but also to manipulate narratives, positioning misinformation as 'fake news' to obscure the truth. This marks a shift in which language becomes a tool of deception, rather than a transparent communicator.

Social media platforms also play a significant role in the spread of fake news, especially in political contexts. According to Allcott and Gentzkow, fake news supporting Donald Trump was widely shared on Facebook during the 2016 US election, influencing public opinion. Furthermore, selective belief in fake news aligns with political preferences, especially on ideologically segregated social media networks.

Finally, machine learning models have been used to detect fake news, but they face challenges such as limited accuracy and generalisation, claim Singh et al. These difficulties highlight the complexity of the issue, as combating fake news requires not only technological solutions, but also linguistic and communicative strategies.

Keywords: language manipulation, political agenda, social media

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Foundedness

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Opinions can be differentiated on the basis of a variety of qualities which describe how they are embedded or justified by the opinion holders. While there is no existing umbrella term for these qualities, we refer to them as the ‘foundedness’ of an opinion. The foundedness of an opinion describes why people believe something to be true and how certain they are that something is true. Common types of foundedness are the epistemological status of an opinion, the affective status of an opinion, sources that support an opinion, or provided evidence in support of an opinion.

The concept of foundedness of opinions is crucial for researching opinion discourses, as it aims to analyse how individuals justify their positions and attempt to persuade others. Research, for instance, is interested in unraveling how communicators use evidence to support their claims or how propagandists can use affective language to mobilise sympathisers.

Similarly, the concept of foundedness of opinions is also of interest in research on the effects of opinionated statements, as it strives to uncover how statements with different types of foundedness vary in their impact. For instance, this research is interested in unraveling how information supported by evidence differs in impact from information without evidence, or how the persuasiveness of opinions with different epistemological statuses—such as the certainty of claims or the reliability of a prognosis—might shape audience reactions.

Keywords: epistemological status, affective status, sources, evidence

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Frames

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Frames are cognitive structures or interpretive lenses through which individuals perceive, organise, and evaluate information about an issue or event. Communicators such as media outlets and political actors employ frames to emphasise specific aspects of a topic while downplaying others, thereby shaping how audiences understand and respond to issues. In the context of opinion formation, Entman finds that frames influence public attitudes by making certain considerations more salient. In linguistics, Fillmore defines frames as mental structures that organise conceptual knowledge, guiding interpretation and enabling comprehension of ambiguous or unspecified language. These structures support our ability to process information by activating relevant expectations and associations. Sociologist Goffman introduced the idea of frame analysis to explain how individuals structure their experiences to make sense of the world. He argues that people rely on social frameworks—collectively constructed patterns of interpretation—to organise events and assign meaning to them.

Scheufele presents that the *media framing approach* extends these ideas to mass communication, focusing on how media shape public understanding through frame-building and frame-setting processes. Journalists select certain aspects of reality and emphasise them through thematic or episodic angles, influencing how audiences interpret events. Framing thus plays a central role in the construction of news and political discourse. Media frames affect audiences in multiple ways: they can activate existing schemas (*activation effect*), reshape them (*transformation effect*), create new interpretive structures (*structuring effect*), or influence opinion formation (*thought formation effect*) claim Cappella and Jamieson.

Keywords: framing, frame analysis, media effects

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Framing Theory

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Framing Theory explains how individuals interpret reality based on the way information is presented in communication, particularly through media. A frame is a cognitive structure that organises perception and simplifies complex information, allowing audiences to make sense of the world. By selecting, emphasising, and excluding elements, media shape how issues are defined, understood, and discussed. The theory was introduced by Erving Goffman, who defined frames as ‘schemata of interpretation’ that help individuals locate, perceive, identify, and label events and occurrences. Goffman argued that frames guide how people understand and respond to social situations by structuring experience and subjective involvement. Robert Entman refined this concept in the context of mass communication, stating that frames ‘select some aspects of a perceived reality and make them more salient in a communicating text.’ According to Entman, frames perform four key functions: they define problems, diagnose causes, make moral evaluations, and suggest solutions. There is a difference between framing in communication—how issues are presented by speakers or the media—and framing in thought, which refers to how individuals internalise and interpret these frames. In media research, framing is typically analysed through two interconnected processes: frame-building, which examines how frames are constructed within journalistic practices and influenced by internal (e.g. editorial policies) and external factors; and frame-setting, which explores how these frames shape audience interpretation. Together, these processes influence how people evaluate information, form opinions, and develop political attitudes and beliefs.

Visual framing also plays a powerful role on four levels: (1) composition and layout, (2) symbolism and connotation, (3) contextual use, and (4) perceptual impact. Visual elements like photographs, graphics, or videos can evoke emotional reactions and subtly reinforce narrative frames.

Keywords: frames, frame-building, frame-setting

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Hate Speech

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Hate speech refers to any form of communication—spoken, written, or symbolic—that disparages or incites hostility against individuals or groups based on characteristics such as race, ethnicity, nationality, religion, gender, sexual orientation, language, disability, health status, or social origin. Its primary function is to stigmatise, dehumanise, and marginalise its targets, often fostering a hostile social environment. Despite frequent usage in public discourse and regulation, the term lacks a universally agreed-upon definition. Brown applies *ordinary language analysis* to explore how hate speech is used in everyday contexts. He outlines a set of widely held assumptions or ‘folk platitudes’, including the beliefs that hate speech conveys moral condemnation, targets protected groups, is harmful, and is potentially subject to legal restriction. Although often thought to express hatred, Brown argues that hate speech is not necessarily motivated by hatred itself.

This ordinary language perspective echoes Wittgenstein’s idea that the meaning of a word lies in its public use rather than any fixed essence. Accordingly, hate speech should be understood as a ‘family resemblance’ concept—one with overlapping but not identical features across contexts. Parekh identifies three core features of hate speech: it targets protected characteristics, stigmatises the group, and marginalises its members from full societal participation. Meanwhile, Moran adds emphasis on the *intent* behind hate speech, particularly its function in promoting hostility against socially vulnerable groups. The term is also used interchangeably with ‘intolerance’ or ‘discriminatory language’ in both academic and media settings, underscoring the need for careful, context-aware analysis when identifying or regulating such speech.

Keywords: discrimination, ordinary language analysis, harm, intent.

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Hedging

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Hedging is a common linguistic strategy used in both spoken and written communication to express uncertainty, reduce directness, or soften the impact of a statement. Rather than stating something in an absolute or assertive way, speakers use hedges to present ideas more tentatively, making statements sound less blunt, confrontational, or imposing. For example, expressions such as *sort of*, *I think*, or *maybe* reduce the force or certainty of what is being said.

The term *hedge* was introduced by George Lakoff, who described hedges as linguistic devices that make meanings ‘fuzzier’ or less definitive. He noted that some hedges attenuate meaning (e.g., *a little bit*), while others intensify it (e.g., *very*, *really*). However, later scholars, such as Wright and Hosman, distinguished clearly between hedges and intensifiers, emphasizing their opposing functions—hedges soften meaning, while intensifiers strengthen it.

Brown and Levinson examined hedging within the framework of politeness theory. They linked hedging to strategies for managing ‘face-threatening acts,’ where speakers aim to maintain social harmony by showing respect, solidarity, or deference.

Other distinctions have also emerged in the literature. Hübler contrasted hedging with understatement, arguing that while understatement alters the truth value of a proposition, hedging reflects the speaker’s stance. Caffi extended this view through her theory of mitigation, proposing a typology that includes *bushes*, *hedges*, and *shields*, each addressing different aspects of communicative softening.

The use of hedging is highly genre-dependent and plays a significant role in academic writing, political discourse, legal argumentation, and everyday conversation.

Keywords: meaning, mitigation, politeness

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Identity

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Identity provides a sense of continuity within the self and in interaction with others (*self-sameness*), as well as a frame to differentiate between self and others (*uniqueness*) which allows the individual to function autonomously from others. A latest definition by the American Psychological Association defines Identity as an individual's sense of self that is structured by (a) a set of physical, psychological, and interpersonal characteristics that is not wholly shared with any other person and (b) a range of affiliations (e.g., ethnicity) and social roles. Social identity theory proposed that identity is constructed by distinction between personal Identity and social identity, which together make up the complete identity of the individual. Another key theory that emphasises the connection between identity and the social surrounding is The Communication Theory of Identity. The researchers explain that identity is multi-layered and situated in communication. According to the theory, identity includes four different frames: personal (i.e., how people see themselves), enacted (i.e., how identity is expressed in interactions), relational (i.e., relational roles), and communal (i.e., group memberships). Layers can overlap and also contradict, creating identity gaps. Above and beyond the emphases of different theories, Identity involves a sense of continuity, or the feeling that one is the same person today that one was yesterday or last year (despite physical or other changes). Such a sense is derived from one's body sensations; one's body image; and the feeling that one's memories, goals, values, expectations, and beliefs belong to the self. Both personal and social identity plays a key role in shaping and expressing opinions. Groups to which individuals belong and members of socially defined identity groups have both conscious and unconscious influence on shaping an individual's opinions.

Keywords: social identity theory, communication theory of identity, social identity

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Ideology

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Ideology refers to a system of socio-cognitively shared ideas that shape the identity, actions, values, and goals of social groups, as well as their relations to other groups. Ideologies are acquired and reproduced through discourse and social practices, providing coherence to group beliefs and embedding cultural values such as equality, freedom, or tradition. In discourse, ideology functions as a framing device: it influences how individuals and groups represent, interpret, and understand social reality. For example, media representations of migration may reflect ideological positions by emphasising threat, victimhood, or resilience, each shaping public perception in different ways. Ideological content can be conveyed both explicitly and implicitly, through presuppositions, lexical choices, and narrative structures. In opinionated discourse—such as editorials, political speeches, or social media commentary—ideology plays a central role in shaping evaluative language, argument structures, and stance-taking. Language users strategically employ ideologically charged expressions to align with or challenge group values. These expressions do not merely communicate opinions; they position speakers within ideological frameworks and work to persuade, justify, or mobilise audiences. Even the selection or omission of information reflects ideological positioning. This is particularly evident in polarised discourse, where competing narratives highlight how language encodes value-led assumptions and activates emotional responses. Ideologies are closely tied to politics, underpinning party platforms, policy debates, and public discourse on social issues such as justice, identity, and power. They provide the cognitive basis for how social actors understand their roles and responsibilities within wider structures of authority and inequality.

Keywords: discourse and social practice, framing, ideas

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Implicit

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Implicit language is non-literal, usually based on presupposition and/or implicature, and is cancellable. By cancellability we mean the option of withdrawing from what the speaker has said without negative consequences. The fact that one can deny what s/he said is particularly important in offensive language, and especially in the case of irony. In order to avoid being judged for criticising and/or ridiculing the receiver in case the latter reacts stronger to the offensive language than expected, the speaker can renounce his/her negative intentions as the way s/he expressed thoughts were not straightforward and left some room for doubt whether the speaker actually meant what s/he said or not. Traditionally, implicitness encompasses figurative language, such as: metaphors, similes, understatements, overstatements, irony. They stem from Grice's typology of implicitness that comprises: irony, metaphor, hyperbole, and meiosis. Sometimes non-figurative language, which however is not fully literal such as rhetorical questions, are also included in implicitness, in particular examples of the Searlian indirect speech act (such as *Can you pass me the salt* wherein a question is in fact a request).

Keywords: non-literalness, cancellability

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Implicitness

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In linguistics, Grice distinguishes between presuppositions and understatements. Presuppositions are a conventional form of implicitness triggered by the presence of indicators in a proposition. They are ubiquitous and heterogeneous, as they pertain to both relational and referential aspects. Presuppositions can be found in syntax and lexicon, as well as in language register. For communication to continue, presuppositions are generally taken for granted by all interlocutors. These presuppositions often remain unnoticed during conversation, yet they form a crucial foundation for mutual understanding and coherence in discourse. Understatements are implicit statements characterised by indirect anchoring. They add extra meaning to part or all of the utterance, yet no element of the propositional content explicitly signals this implicitness. Therefore, their implicature can only be derived once the proposition has been stated and contextualised. The recognition of an understatement often relies on shared knowledge, contextual cues, and pragmatic competence on the part of the listener. Inference may be possible, but is not obligatory. This means that the implied meaning does not necessarily have to be accepted as true by all interlocutors. Sperber and Wilson develop the theory of relevance, which complements these notions by explaining that interlocutors evaluate utterances based on their contextual relevance. According to this theory, understatements are examples of implicatures that acquire meaning only within a specific context, where listeners must make inferences to achieve a coherent interpretation. Implicit statements, such as understatements, thus rely on a balance between cognitive processing effort and contextual effects obtained. According to Searle, understatements are indirect speech acts, in which one speech act is performed indirectly through another. Certain figures of classical rhetoric, such as irony as well as illocutionary tropes, are part of implicitness.

Keywords: implicature, illocution, interpretation

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Implicit Bias

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Implicit bias is a form of bias that occurs automatically and unintentionally, that nevertheless affects judgments, decisions, and behaviours. Research on implicit bias suggests that individuals may express opinions or make judgments shaped by prejudice and stereotypes, even without conscious intent. In opinion formation, implicit bias affects how individuals interpret information and form attitudes toward others or issues, even when these biases contradict their consciously held beliefs or values. These biases can also shape personal and societal opinions, often reinforcing existing stereotypes and influencing attitudes toward social and political issues without conscious awareness. Research has shown implicit bias can pose a barrier to recruiting and retaining diverse workers in the workforce, to interpersonal relationships, and affect discriminatory behavior in education systems, healthcare, police, social work, and more. While the field of implicit bias encompasses studies on topics such as consumer preferences, food, alcohol, and political opinions, the most impactful and widely cited research has examined implicit opinions and attitudes toward members of socially stigmatised groups, including African Americans, members of religious groups, women, and the LGBTQ community. A significant part of the research dealing with implicit biases concerns ways to avoid these biases. In the case of implicit biases, the matter is even more challenging because people are often not aware that they hold these biases. The unconscious influence of biases can lead to systematic errors in judgment and inconsistent decision-making. Studies have shown, for example, that implicit racial biases can influence hiring decisions and medical diagnoses, even among individuals who consciously reject prejudice. As a result, researchers have explored interventions such as counter-stereotypic training, increased intergroup contact, and mindfulness practices to reduce the effects of implicit biases over time.

Keywords: socially stigmatised groups, discriminatory behaviour, unconscious influence

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Impoliteness

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Opinions can be expressed in polite and impolite ways, with the latter being best understood from the perspective of impoliteness theory. Regarding impoliteness, an important shift occurred in the mid-1990s and later when, instead of being viewed as a politeness failure, it began to be regarded as a strategic and deliberate use of impolite forms. In this framework, impoliteness is defined as the use of conventionalised impoliteness formulae that are typically employed to cause social disruption instead of promoting social harmony.

The roots of impoliteness theories can be traced back to politeness theories, which assumed that impoliteness is a result of a failure to be polite (rather than a consequence of intentional measures) and that politeness is universal (that is unified across cultures and languages). As a reaction to this approach to politeness, a group of scholars dealing with impolite verbal behaviour launched a new approach, a discursive analysis of impoliteness, which assumes (1) that impoliteness may be intentional or non-intentional, (2) that it is community-specific and guided by social norms, (3) it is based on internal perspectives of the interlocutors (rather than filtered through the researcher's/observer's perspective), i.e. the interlocutors decide themselves, through a 'discursive struggle', what is and what is not impolite in a situated discourse in which they participate, and thus (3) impoliteness is negotiable.

Impoliteness includes interactive strategies aimed at attacking face, and those deliberately leading to conflictive communication. Being directly related to conflict, language aggression, and intentionally disruptive behaviour, impoliteness is associated with hate speech and can serve as a useful category in hate speech identification.

The following types of conventional impoliteness formulae are distinguished: insults (personalised negative vocatives, personalised negative assertions, personalised negative references, and personalised third-person negative references), pointed criticism, challenging or unpalatable questions and/or presuppositions, condescensions, message enforcers, dismissals, silencers, threats, and negative expressives.

Keywords: conventionalised impoliteness formulae, face, politeness theory

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Incivility (1)

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A distinction made by Andersson and Pearson (452) between *incivility* and *impoliteness* (see *Impoliteness*) is often dubbed as a distinction between ‘deep’ and ‘surface’ civility, with politeness and good manners being the superficial/surface behavioural manifestations, while deep or genuine civility refers to acting with others in mind. As proposed in Calhoun (253), civility refers to kindness, respect, tolerance, and consideration of feelings of others, while incivility encompasses a wide range of actions, from minor rudeness to more serious disrespect. Essentially, it is about a lack of regard for others and a violation of norms of respectful conduct. As suggested by Sifianou, such an understanding of the distinction is reminiscent of Goffman’s (55) distinction between ceremonial (etiquette) and substantive (morality and ethics) rules of conduct.

Incivility is a broader concept than impoliteness, as it extends to behaviors that can have more significant and lasting negative consequences, particularly in public or professional spheres. One can argue that incivility goes beyond mere rudeness to threaten democratic discourse, undermine collective well-being, or violate fundamental principles of a civil society. Incivility is often seen as having a clearer intent to harm or disrupt. It can be characterised by a dismissive, aggressive, or hostile tone that goes beyond simply lacking good manners. Incivility is frequently discussed in broader contexts like workplace dynamics, political discourse, or online communication, where its impact can affect larger groups or societal functions. It is also argued by Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk that negative emotions underlying incivility function as a stronger driving force than positive emotionality towards a unity of group identification.

Keywords: ethics, etiquette, impoliteness, morality

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Incivility (2)

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Incivility in digital communication refers to discourse practices that undermine democratic values, restrict individual freedoms, or perpetuate harmful stereotypes. From a normative perspective, incivility includes hate speech, profanity, personal insults, and offensive language, while politeness is often conceptualised as the absence of such expressions. Contextual approaches stress that incivility is shaped by the sociocultural norms of specific online environments, where community standards influence what is deemed acceptable or offensive. Incivility may also be understood as a discursive tone that exhibits unnecessary hostility or disrespect toward individuals, ideas, or groups. While incivility denotes aggressive and confrontational speech, intolerance reflects deeper moral contempt toward particular identities or viewpoints.

On the individual level, incivility is typically understood as a form of impoliteness in interpersonal communication. This includes behaviors such as stereotyping people or groups and violating their rights, which are generally perceived as both disrespectful and uncivil. Incivility may also be understood as a discursive tone that exhibits unnecessary hostility or disrespect toward individuals, ideas, or groups. While incivility denotes aggressive and confrontational speech, intolerance reflects deeper moral contempt toward particular identities or viewpoints. At the public level, incivility is often regarded as fundamentally opposed to democratic norms and the principles underpinning political discourse and engagement. Incivility can be defined as communicative behavior deliberately intended to provoke, offend, or demean others. It manifests through name-calling, character attacks, derogatory remarks, and vulgar expressions. Politeness, conversely, entails respectful dialogue devoid of personal attacks or inflammatory rhetoric. However, the boundaries between civility and incivility are fluid and context-dependent, influenced by participants' cultural backgrounds, ethnicity, and levels of education.

Keywords: digital discourse, democratic communication, online incivility

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Individualisation

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Individualisation is one of the types of representation of social actors proposed by van Leeuwen. It occurs when the social actor is represented individually by name, specific features, personal characteristics, etc. Typically, it is a discursive device which allows creation of a sense of proximity/closeness which might contribute to the positive feelings of humanisation, empathy, or sympathy. It is the process of creating something different to fit the desires of a specific individual, location, etc.

From a linguistics perspective it may include individual linguistic variation regarding the unique way language is used; language acquisition and individual differences in the way some people attain language skills more easily or faster than others; lexical individualisation on the way speakers construct new terms or phrases such as slang or even academic terms to express themselves; pragmatic individualisation on contextual adaptation such as the communicative setting; or the impact of the individual on language evolution.

The concept is also used in other disciplines such as business where it focuses on tailoring services or products to specific needs. Socially, it involves one's responsibility for their life.

Keywords: social actors, individuals, language

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Infographics/Data Visualisation

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Opinions can be communicated not only verbally, but also graphically. The visual forms of presenting various types of data (usually complex information expressing facts or opinions) in a systematic form is known as infographics. Visualisations of textual or numerical information enhance data interpretation as they present a bird's eye view of the data at hand, make them more transparent, meaningful, and readable. Infographics are operationalised, inter alia, through maps, lists, line graphs, bubble plots, scatter plots, bar charts, pie charts, and time intelligence. They are often interactive, offering an overview of the data together with tools to drill them down, which empower users to explore the data on their own and enhance data comprehensibility. Lewis and Westlund find infographics based on big data (huge volumes of data counted in tera- and petabytes) are increasingly popular in data journalism, and have a big impact on media industry . And Veglus et al see that infographics are often used in media organisations to visualise user-generated content, which expresses opinion polls or facts, published on social media. Popular software tools used to convert complex data into graphic form comprise Tableau, MS Power BI.

Keywords: interactive graphics, user-generated content

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Insults

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Insults are words which contain some personal characteristics or behaviour description of the target addressee. For example, they make reference to what the insultee possesses, e.g., beliefs, achievement, bodily features, job, family, etc. They may aim at damaging someone's reputation by mainly using false statements (calumnies); they may be based on truth by stressing one's defects (e.g. You're a cripple) (put downs); or they may exploit the inferior status of the target or encode what no one can believe to be true (e.g. name-calling, abusive invectives, etc.: *You son of a bitch*). Insults assert dominance, either intentionally claiming superiority or unintentionally revealing lack of regard. Insults may be offensive by the very fact that the speaker's intention was to offend the target, or it may be sanctioned by their perlocutionary force.

Insults often violate socially accepted norms of politeness and respect; thus, in linguistics, they are often examined from the perspective of Impoliteness Theory, which considers insults to be one type of conventional impoliteness formulae. From a pragmatic perspective, insults are typically seen as face-threatening acts that undermine the hearer's positive or negative face, either through direct means (e.g. explicit name-calling) or indirect strategies such as irony or sarcasm. The form, frequency, and acceptability of insults vary across cultural and social group contexts. For instance, ritualised or playful insults can serve to reinforce social bonds within peer groups, while in other settings, the same expressions can function as tools of exclusion or domination. In the context of opinion research, insults can reveal underlying power relations, social attitudes, and emotional investments, which makes them a valuable resource for analysing the language of disagreement and hostility, or, more specifically, hate speech. They may appear in isolation or reinforce broader discursive strategies such as dehumanisation, racial criminalisation, and negative stereotyping—particularly in anti-immigrant rhetoric.

Keywords: face-threat, impoliteness, name-calling, hate speech

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Intention

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The concept of intention is present in the work of many pioneering pragmatic researchers. Grice's Cooperative principle states that interlocutors who intend to carry out an exchange should adhere to the maxims of conversation. (1) The maxim of quality requires stating only what is believed to be true. Intention is central here, as speakers are expected to have the intention of being honest and to avoid saying anything they know to be false or for which they lack sufficient evidence. (2) The maxim of quantity requires that we give neither too much nor too little information. This maxim is guided by the speaker's intention to be adequately informative, providing enough details for understanding without overwhelming the listener with unnecessary information. (3) The maxim of relation requires that an utterance must be relevant. This reflects the speaker's intention to deliberately choose information that directly connects to the topic of conversation, ensuring that their contribution is purposeful and meaningful to the ongoing exchange. Finally, (4) the maxim of manner requires that an utterances should be as clear as possible. The speaker's intention is to communicate in a way that minimises ambiguity, confusion, or unnecessary complexity, allowing the listener to easily grasp the intended meaning.

Intention is also a key aspect of Speech Act theories, as developed by Austin and later elaborated by Searle, which view communication as a form of action performed in the world with a specific intention (see Speech Act). As Nunberg notes, correctly understanding the speaker's intention is crucial for correct referring and interpretation.

Keywords: maxims of conversation, meaning, speech act

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Interactivity

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From the macro perspective, interactivity entails larger theoretical constructs such as power of control where the power is shifted to users to express opinions, especially through online spaces that allow for user-generated content to circulate.

Interactivity has been conceptualised through the web 2.0 paradigm where users were given a possibility to not only passively create and consume content but also to engage with the content and each other.

Interactivity, thus, has been through various lenses; typically a mix of the following: it encompasses technological properties that enable interactivity to take place, communication contexts, and user perceptions and experiences. Others, such as McMillan, proposed similar approaches that include a mixed human and technology approach that has been summarised as the following three traditions of interactivity research: human-to-human interaction, human-to-document interaction, and human-to-system interaction.

For Jensen, typology approach of interactivity includes elements that pertain to information traffic: transmission, registration, consultation, and conversation.

And for Rafaeli, conversation approach to interactivity includes the following elements: interactivity is viewed as a property of message exchange, where the ideal circle is completed when two messages are synthesised by a third message.

In the mass media contexts, four broad conceptualisations of interactivity with regard to space and time have been proposed by Van Dijk. Spatial dimension is based on the mere availability of interactive applications; as such they allow for reaction. Temporal aspects entail synchronicity and response time becomes a variable that defines the success of interaction where the lag is perceived as creating damaging consequences to communication. The level of control in which communicative actors exercise to choose types and amount of contents to be exchanged is another dimension of interactivity. The last dimension is the highest abstract dimension that deals with understanding of contexts in which interaction of content takes place.

All these approaches suggest a multifaceted meaning of interactivity that shapes the way opinions are created and circulated, especially in online contexts, mediated by technological affordances through social construction of technology.

Keywords: asynchronous communication, technological affordances, synchronicity, social construction of technology

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Interpretation

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Interpretation is an explanation of something hinged on analysis and factual evidence. Due to the presence of subjective elements, it could be misunderstood as opinion; however, an opinion is a personal view, perspective, or attitude that does not need to be supported by factual evidence. An opinion could entail some degree of interpretation, but an interpretation does not necessarily contain opinionated views, as it could be an analysis of facts and evidence based on pre-existing frames or schemes.

Although the notion that opinions are subjective claims and interpretations are based on evidence makes sense theoretically, the distinction is not always straightforward in practice, particularly in the absence of references to the underlying facts. Opinions express beliefs and feelings and therefore cannot be deemed false or true. Interpretations may be true or false because they result from attempts to explain the why and/or how of facts, events, statements, etc. Opinion and interpretation are thus both evaluations, but they are not synonyms: interpretation is the expression of an understanding of something that is backed by facts and is subject to verification; opinion does not enter the realm of verification and therefore is not amenable to proof. In politics, one could refer to personal views about actors and issues as opinions, and to the analysis of the proposals and statements of political actors by journalists and pundits as interpretation. Such political coverage, commonly featured in media outlets, could be linked to a disbelief in value-free facts and interest-free sources, which makes it necessary to explain the context and interpret the relevance and impact of facts, events, and statements. In journalism, interpretation may take the form of explanations, evaluations, contextualisations, or speculations by the journalist, differing from simple descriptions of facts and events.

Keywords: evidence, subjective claims, verification

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Intuition

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Intuition is commonly defined as the rapid, automatic, and often subconscious processing of information that enables individuals to make quick judgments without deliberate reasoning. It plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' opinions by influencing their immediate reactions and judgments. Intuition can also be viewed as an accumulation of attitudes—encompassing beliefs and opinions—formed through both individual and cultural experiences. These intuitive impressions often guide people's initial responses, especially in uncertain or emotionally charged situations. Kahneman frames intuition within his dual-system theory of thinking, describing it as System 1—a fast, heuristic-driven process that contrasts with the slower, more analytical System 2. While intuitive judgments are efficient and often useful, they are also prone to cognitive biases and errors due to their reliance on mental shortcuts. Gigerenzer, however, offers a more optimistic perspective, suggesting that intuition relies on 'fast and frugal heuristics' that can be highly effective, especially in real-world environments where decisions must be made quickly. He contends that intuition is often based on implicit knowledge and can outperform analytical reasoning in specific contexts. Hogarth adds that the accuracy of intuitive decisions depends greatly on the environment in which they are formed. In settings that provide reliable feedback and repeated patterns, intuition can become increasingly refined and reliable—a process he refers to as 'educated intuition.'

Thus, intuition is a fundamental cognitive process that influences how people form opinions, assess situations, and make decisions, balancing efficiency with the potential for error.

Keywords: cognitive bias, decision-making, heuristics

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Irony

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Irony is a figure of speech which is used to intentionally manifest a hostile or derogatory judgement of the addressee. It is based on creating a clash between the intended meaning that is implied (the implicatum) and the meaning of what is actually said (the dictum). This clash is usually realised by resorting to the reverse of the speaker's intended meaning, which can rely on the use of antonyms, as in *You are a genius* meaning 'you are stupid'; antithetical meaning, wherein the whole utterance is contradicted, as in *Thank you very much* or *Wow*; a partial contradiction, as in *You are tipsy* said to somebody who is drunk; or absurd false comparisons, as in *And I am the President of the USA*. While in the traditional understanding of irony the meaning reversal relies on untruthful statements, in the neo-Gricean approaches, truthful statements are allowed (in verisimilar irony) as long as there is a clash between what the speaker says (a truthful statement) and what the described reality is like (the opposite), as in *I love children who keep their rooms clean* uttered by a mother to her child while inspecting the child's room (that is in a mess).

Importantly, the use of irony extends well beyond isolated utterances. It is a discursive phenomenon that goes beyond a simple opposition between apparent and implicit messages, engaging contextual and social cues. It includes false advice, false praise, or feigned naivety to mock. Another form, turning 'the world upside down', creates incongruity through contextual clash.

In online opinionated discourse, irony plays a strategic role, allowing users to critique, distance themselves from or highlight contradictions in opinions and social norms without direct confrontation. This fosters subtle forms of dissent and reflection.

Keywords: implicature, online discourse, strategic communication

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Issue

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Issues are the subject matters on which opinions are formed. In their broadest sense, issues can be understood as overarching themes or topics of concern. They bind together a range of similar events, facts, or concepts to broader categories of meaning and can touch various areas of social life, including politics, economics, culture, etc. In public discourse and political communication, issues are understood as social problems or matters of contention, often playing out as conflicts between different groups. Thus, in a narrower sense, the term issue is used for a topic that is problematised and politicised.

The process of issue definition is the first important step of political agenda building. It includes identifying a social problem as such, raising awareness for it, and acknowledging that it needs attention and action from policymakers. In agenda setting studies, issues are the main object of scientific inquiry. Scholars study how salient issues are among the public using surveys or analysing media coverage.

Issues can be contested to different degrees. Generally, valence issues are distinguished from position issues. For valence issues, there is broad consensus on the desired goal, and debate primarily focuses on how to achieve it, and who is more competent in doing so (e.g., economic prosperity, national security). Position issues, in contrast, are divisive issues where actors disagree on the goals and take divergent stances (e.g., immigration, abortion rights).

Keywords: agenda, salience, topic

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Journalistic Interventionism

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Journalistic Interventionism is the active engagement of journalists in shaping public opinion, influencing policy, and steering socio-political discourse. It is commonly expressed through three core functions: setting the political agenda, influencing public perception, and advocating social change. In setting the political agenda, journalists frame and emphasise specific themes to guide public and political attention. To shape public opinion, they often use human interest or conflict-oriented frames, influencing how audiences interpret events. Additionally, journalists promote social change by spotlighting key issues, leveraging editorial tools such as headline selection and story placement. Accordingly, emotional framing (such as the use of evocative language or personal stories) is used to elicit empathy and mobilise public sentiment. In some cases, journalists align with advocacy networks or organisations to broaden the reach and impact of their message. Journalistic interventionism approach enhances journalism's transformative potential and also raises ethical concerns. For example, presenting information in alignment with a particular viewpoint blurs the line between reporting and advocacy. This persistent coverage of certain topics can create a sense of urgency and call to action, but it challenges traditional norms of objectivity. Thus, journalistic interventionism reflects a complex and evolving role of media in society, one that must balance influence with responsibility.

Keywords: media advocacy, political agenda setting, opinion framing, public opinion influence

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Judgement (1)

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Judgement is the capacity to recognise relationships, evaluate information, and make informed decisions or critical evaluations regarding events, situations, or people. Judgement involves drawing conclusions from evidence and forming assessments that guide behavior and thought. In both psychology and philosophy, judgement is viewed as a complex cognitive process that integrates perception, reasoning, and experience. Kant emphasised the foundational role of judgment in the synthesis of sensory information, arguing that judgement is essential for organising perceptions into coherent knowledge, a necessary bridge between understanding and reasoning. Daniel Kahneman offers a contemporary psychological perspective in *Thinking, Fast and Slow*, distinguishing between System 1 (fast, intuitive, automatic thinking) and System 2 (slow, deliberate, effortful thinking). Judgement derived from System 1 tends to rely on heuristics and is prone to biases, while System 2 supports more reflective, analytic judgment. This dual-system model helps explain why people often make snap decisions that deviate from rational norms.

From a linguistic perspective, scholars such as Chomsky and Levi examine how individuals make judgements about grammaticality, revealing innate cognitive structures that underlie language competence and acquisition. Importantly, moral and social judgments—such as evaluating right and wrong or fairness—are central to both psychological research and philosophical ethics. These forms of judgement involve not only cognition but also emotion, cultural norms, and values, reflecting the broader human need to navigate interpersonal and societal complexities.

Judgement plays a central role in the formation of opinions by shaping how individuals evaluate people, objects, and events. Through cognitive appraisal, individuals assess information based on prior knowledge, beliefs, and emotions, which in turn influences their attitudes. Quick, intuitive judgments (System 1) may lead to implicit attitudes, while deliberate, reflective judgements (System 2) contribute to more stable, explicit opinions. Thus, judgement serves as the cognitive mechanism through which evaluative positions are developed, maintained, or changed over time.

Keywords: attitudes, cognition, system

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Judgement (2)

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The term ‘judgment’ has been well-defined in linguistics by the so-called Appraisal Theory, which rests on the theoretical foundations of Systemic Functional Linguistics. The Appraisal Theory is often used in various disciplines; apart from linguistics, it is also popular among scholars representing media studies, social and political sciences, or working on the intersection thereof. In line with the Appraisal Theory, judgment is the act of evaluating a subject with regard to their moral behaviour, i.e., in terms of ethics. Judgment can be positive (admiration) or negative (criticism), and it can assess social esteem and social sanction. Social esteem deals with normality of behaviour (e.g., standard, avant-garde; eccentric, unfashionable); capacity, i.e., a person’s skills and competencies (e.g., strong, clever; stupid, clumsy); and tenacity, i.e., it signals whether a person is dependable and/or well-disposed (e.g., brave, reliable; lazy, cowardly, unreliable). Social sanction encompasses a person’s truthfulness and honesty (veracity) and a person’s, ethical behaviour (propriety). Examples of veracity comprise honest, frank, and credible for positive assessments; and deceitful, dishonest, and fake for negative assessments. On the other hand, propriety involves the following examples: moral, just, considerate, etc. for the positive assessment; and cruel, brutal, corrupt, etc. for the negative assessment. Judgment is one of three subcategories of Attitude, which, along with judgment also distinguishes affect (emotional responses) and appreciation (the aesthetics). Attitude in turn is one of the three sub-types of Appraisal. Judgment is a crucial device in expressing opinions, and due to its strong focus on ethical behaviour evaluation, it is vital in the analysis of political discourse.

Keywords: appraisal theory, social esteem, veracity

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Lexical Embedding

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Lexical embedding is the process of representing words or lexical items in a continuous vector space to capture their semantic relationships and contextual associations. This enables semantically similar words to appear near one another in the space and is essential in natural language processing (NLP) tasks such as sentiment analysis, machine translation, and information retrieval. There are two main types of lexical embedding: context-free and contextual.

Context-free embeddings, also known as static word embeddings, assign a fixed vector to each word based on its general usage across large text corpora. A widely used technique for generating such embeddings is Word2Vec, which learns distributed word representations by analysing patterns of word co-occurrence. For example, in the sentence 'The king smiled proudly,' the word 'king' frequently appears with terms like 'smiled' and 'proudly,' leading the model to associate it with royalty and positive sentiment. The resulting vector places 'king' near other related words. However, since the vector is fixed, it cannot adapt to different contexts in which the same word appears.

Contextual embeddings, in contrast, generate word vectors that depend on the word's position and role in a specific sentence. Transformers, deep learning models based on attention mechanisms, produce these dynamic embeddings by modeling how each word relates to others in its context. For instance, in 'The king smiled proudly,' the model interprets 'smiled proudly' as reflecting a triumphant tone. But in 'The king ruled with an iron fist,' the tone becomes harsh or authoritarian, and the embedding for 'king' changes accordingly. Models like BERT and GPT excel at capturing such subtleties, enabling more accurate performance in tasks such as question answering, summarisation, and nuanced language understanding.

Keywords: contextual embeddings, word representation, static embeddings

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Manipulation

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Manipulation refers to the act of influencing or controlling individuals or situations through indirect, deceptive, or coercive means. It involves a calculated effort to shape another person's thoughts, emotions, or actions to serve the manipulator's interests, often without the target's full awareness. Manipulation typically operates within asymmetrical power dynamics, where the manipulator possesses greater authority, access to information, or control over communicative channels.

In Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), manipulation is conceptualised as a covert strategy used by dominant groups to preserve power and perpetuate social inequality. It is defined as 'a devious way to control others', involving the illegitimate exercise of influence. Scholars in this field aim to expose how discourse is strategically employed to legitimise domination and maintain ideological hegemony. Teun A. van Dijk offers a cognitive approach to manipulation, placing it within a triangular model of discourse, cognition, and society. He highlights how linguistic choices—such as presuppositions, implicatures, and framing—affect mental models and enable subtle control of beliefs and interpretations. A theory that neglects cognition risks missing how individuals are (often unwittingly) persuaded and led to comply.

Manipulation is also closely linked to the shaping of public opinion. Media platforms, political institutions, and digital algorithms play a significant role in influencing societal attitudes through disinformation, emotional appeals, and selective exposure. These strategies exploit cognitive vulnerabilities, such as confirmation bias and motivated reasoning, reinforcing polarised views and limiting critical engagement. In this way, manipulation becomes a powerful force in controlling narratives, manufacturing consent, and guiding collective behaviour.

Keywords: cognitive discourse analysis, public opinion

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Media Bias

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The study of media bias remains a dynamic field characterised by ongoing investigations into its nature, impact, and strategies for mitigation. Scholars from diverse disciplines such as media studies, political science, and communication aim at better explaining the intricate interplay between media bias, public opinion, and civic engagement.

The advent of advanced computational tools has facilitated large-scale studies, enabling researchers to analyse extensive amounts of textual and visual data, revealing nuanced patterns of bias. Investigating the influence of media bias on public opinion and political behaviour remains a central focus. Researchers delve into how various forms of bias, whether partisan, cultural, or economic, shape individuals' attitudes, beliefs, and voting behaviour. Understanding these dynamics is essential for comprehending the role of media in shaping democratic societies and informing policy decisions.

Studies also scrutinise the role of emerging technologies in either amplifying or mitigating media bias. The proliferation of algorithmic curation and personalised content delivery on digital platforms has led to discussions on filter bubbles and echo chambers, where individuals predominantly encounter information aligning with their pre-existing beliefs. Conversely, researchers explore how technologies like machine learning and natural language processing can be utilised to detect and counteract bias in news reporting.

Addressing media bias goes beyond academic research, with initiatives focusing on media literacy and educational interventions. Scholars investigate the effectiveness of interventions designed to enhance critical media literacy skills, enabling individuals to navigate and discern biased information effectively.

In the realms of policy and regulation, researchers examine also the roles of governmental and self-regulatory measures in mitigating media bias. The complex challenge of balancing journalistic freedom with preventing the dissemination of misleading or intentionally skewed information requires careful consideration of legal, ethical, and technological solutions.

Keywords: biased information, public opinion, political behaviour

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Media Effects

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Media effects can be referred to as the deliberative and nondeliberative short- and long-term within-person changes in cognitions, emotions, attitudes, beliefs, physiology, and behavior that result from media use.

McQuail and Deuze pointed out that we should give due weight to the fact that the effects are determined at least as much by the receiver as by the sender; the media are rarely likely to be the only necessary or sufficient cause of an effect; their relative contribution is hard to assess; and it makes little sense to speak of 'the media' as if they were one thing rather than the carriers of an enormously diverse set of messages, images, and ideas that in turn are shaped by the affordances of particular technologies. Four distinct ways of making sense of media effects can be found and traced as influential across media and mass communication scholarship: from 'all-powerful' to 'limited' via 'negotiated' to 'complex reciprocal' effects.

Challenges for researching Media Effects remains in measuring the extent to which people encounter specific media messages and a recognition that media effects are conditional, based on someone's level of susceptibility to using and responding to certain media.

Media effects theories include Agenda-Settings Theory by McCombs & Shaw in 1972, Cultivation Theory by Gerbner in 1973, Hypodermic Needle Theory by Lasswell in 1927, Two Step Flow Theory by Lazarsfeld et al. in 1948, Framing by Bateson in 1972, Priming Theory by Iyengar et al. in 1982, Uses and Gratification Theory by Blummer & Katz in 1974, Spiral of Silence Theory by Noelle-Neumann in 1974, etc.

Keywords: media use, media effects theories

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Media Literacy

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Media literacy is a set of perspectives that we actively use when we expose ourselves to the mass media to process and interpret the meaning of the messages we encounter. As Potter stated, to build our knowledge structures we need tools (our skills) and raw material (information from the media and from the real world). Media literacy is a multidimensional concept with development taking place cognitively, emotionally, aesthetically, and morally; and is a continuum, not a category, similar to a thermometer—where there are degrees.

Today studies are being conducted on the influence conspiracy theories have and what post-Truth is. In this case McIntyre points out that ‘post-Truth’ is about a form of ideological supremacy where practitioners try to force someone to believe in something whether or not there is evidence for it.

The founding fathers of Media Literacy concept are Marshall McLuhan and Stuart Hall. McLuhan’s work is clear on the point that the first most vital step of all is understanding media and its revolutionary effects because we gain a measure of control over them.

Stuart Hall’s Reception Theory describes how a media text has different meaning to different audiences. Hall talks about encoding and decoding and the importance of the social and cultural context behind the discourse.

Keywords: media effects, encoding, and decoding

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Metaphor

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Semino considers metaphors to be important in communication and cognition because they express, reflect, and reinforce different ways of making sense of particular aspects of our lives. (They involve the conceptualisation of more abstract notions in terms of more concrete ones. More specifically, conceptual metaphors are defined as the understanding of one more abstract domain of experience in terms of a more concrete domain of experience. Thus, the metaphor is considered a process and a product simultaneously. Kovecses sees the process aspect as related to the cognitive process of understanding a domain and the conceptual pattern that results from such an understanding is recognised as the product aspect. Lakoff feels that this process allows for the image of a familiar topic to replace the image of an unfamiliar topic in the auditor's mind.

Another distinction for Kovecses embodied in the metaphor is the one between the 'source domain' and 'target domain'. The source domain is a concrete domain, whereas the target domain is an abstract one. In the case of the LIFE IS A JOURNEY conceptual metaphor, the domain of journey is concrete as opposed to the domain of life. In general, concrete physical domains typically serve as source domains for more abstract targets, as in the case of LIFE IS A JOURNEY metaphor. This reasoning suggests that conceptual metaphors reside not only in language but also in cognition. Metaphors are connected to public opinion because they shape how people conceptualise, evaluate, and respond to various topics and issues. They activate specific knowledge structures and analogies, guiding thought and action in line with the metaphor's framing. As such, metaphors are powerful tools for shaping public discourse, policy preferences, and societal attitudes.

Keywords: analogy, conceptualisation, cognition

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Modality

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Modality is a linguistic feature that enables speakers and writers to express varying degrees of certainty, obligation, or attitude toward the proposition conveyed in an utterance. It plays a crucial role in shaping the interpersonal and epistemic stance of the speaker.

Statham identifies four modal stances that can be adopted by opinion holders: probability, frequency, obligation, and inclination. Probability refers to the degree of belief an opinion sender holds regarding the likelihood of an event occurring. This stance can be conveyed through modal auxiliary verbs such as shall, should, can, could, will, would, may, must, and might. It may also be expressed through quasi-modals like ought to, need to, and has to; or through modal adverbs such as probably, possibly, certainly, and maybe. Example: She will probably arrive late. Frequency denotes how often an event or action is perceived to occur. This can be indicated using adverbs such as usually, sometimes, always, never, seldom, and rarely, often in combination with modal expressions (61). Example: They rarely agree on political issues. Obligation concerns the degree to which the speaker believes a certain action should be carried out. It is typically expressed through modal adverbs like definitely, absolutely, and possibly, reflecting various levels of assertiveness. Example: We definitely need to submit the paper today. Inclination reflects the speaker's perception of a subject's willingness or tendency to act. Examples include adverbs such as willingly, readily, gladly, and easily. Example: She readily agreed to help. In broader linguistic theory, scholars also distinguish between epistemic modality, which conveys the speaker's judgment about the truth or certainty of a proposition, and deontic modality, which expresses obligation, necessity, or permission regarding actions or states of affairs.

Keywords: epistemic modality, deontic modality, linguistics

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Mode

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The term *mode* denotes a set of socially and culturally shaped resources for creating meaning. It is a central concept in systemic functional linguistics, social semiotics, and multimodal discourse analysis. Instances of modes encompass written and visual elements on a page, extending to dynamic visuals and audio on a screen, as well as spoken words, gestures, gazes, and postures in embodied interactions. While other communication modes had been previously recognised and studied, the comprehensive investigation of various communicational means contests the previous dominance of spoken and written language in linguistics. This approach offers a new framework for analysing the diverse ways individuals create meaning and how these meanings are interconnected through multiple modes.

Modes are not static or independent; rather, they are fluid and subject to change as products of social processes. Additionally, modes are not universally applicable but are specific to communities where there is a shared knowledge of their semiotic characteristics.

Though the concept has become a central term in research on multimodal communication, it is still debated what constitutes a mode. For instance, some researchers view colour and layout as distinct modes and thus consider writing as multimodal, but this is not unanimously agreed upon. In some research, a distinction is often made between ‘mode’ from ‘medium’. Media are conceived as resources that both materialise and produce meaning, referring to platforms or channels of communication. These include traditional forms like television, newspapers, and radio, as well as digital platforms like websites, social media, and apps. A mode, meanwhile, refers to the different forms or resources used to create meaning within these media (e.g. written text, images, sounds) and is understood as a realisation of Hallidayan metafunctions, including the ideational, interpersonal, and textual meanings.

Keywords: multimodality, media, semiotics

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Multimodality/Semiotics

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According to Kress and van Leeuwen, multimodality is the use of multiple modes of communication, including but not limited to language, image, gesture, sound, and spatial arrangement to construct meaning and convey messages. From their perspective, communication is not solely reliant on linguistic elements but encompasses a diverse range of semiotic resources that interact and combine to shape how meaning is produced and interpreted. Each mode provides its own affordances and constraints, influencing the ways information is represented and understood. The combination of different modes within a communicative act allows for a richer, more nuanced form of expression.

Multimodality extends beyond the mere co-occurrence of different modes; it encompasses the interplay and integration of these modes to create coherent and meaningful communication. Kress and van Leeuwen emphasise the importance of understanding how modes interact within multimodal texts, analysing their relationships, hierarchies, and contributions to overall meaning-making processes. Kress and van Leeuwen also highlight the role of social and cultural factors in shaping multimodal practices. They argue that meanings are not inherent in modes themselves but are socially constructed and negotiated within specific cultural contexts. Therefore, multimodal analysis involves not only the identification of formal properties of different modes but also examining the ideological, institutional, and contextual factors that inform their use and interpretation.

Keywords: interplay, semiotic resources, meaning making

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Multimodality/Sociotechnical Analysis

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Today, social media, online platforms, and mobile phone applications are ubiquitous for the expression of opinion. Various research methods were recently developed to understand how people express opinions on such media, informed by principles of Actor-Network Theory and Science and Technology Studies. Interfaces are essentially multimodal as they comprise semiotic, discursive, and technological elements. A sociotechnical approach to expression of opinion on such media is based on the premise that their design is not neutral but contains certain norms that 'produce' user identities and uses, and hence affect the expression of opinion. Two methods that can be used to study interfaces critically are Discursive Interface Analysis and the Walkthrough method, combining the semiotic tradition, discourse analysis, and affordance analysis. Stanfill discusses Discursive Interface Analysis that looks at functional affordances (functionalities, i.e. what one can do), cognitive affordances (meaning-making of technological features), and sensory affordances (aesthetic aspects of features). The Walkthrough method focuses on apps, and sheds light on their intended purpose: embedded cultural meanings and implied ideal users and uses. It is based on the analysis of the environment of expected use (vision, operating model, governance) and the technical walkthrough, which includes user interface arrangements, functions and features, textual content and tone, and symbolic representation. Such methods offer valuable conceptual and methodological tools to understand how people express opinions in social media platforms and apps from a critical, interdisciplinary perspective.

Keywords: discursive interface analysis, sociotechnical approach, walkthrough

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Networked Audiences

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According to Marwick & Boyd, a networked audience refers to a mix of personal ties and broader publics connected through digital platforms, where users are not just passive recipients but an active part of a dynamic, interconnected online environment. Unlike the anonymous broadcast audience, the networked audience often includes familiar individuals, making it simultaneously personal and public with uncertainty of its full composition. The emergence of networked audiences is closely tied to the rise of social media, which has fundamentally transformed the context and characteristics of audiences, allowing for a diverse range of activities to be combined both online and offline. With the expansion of social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, or TikTok, audiences have become more fragmented and less transparent regarding who will be exposed to content shared online. Online platforms have revolutionised how individuals produce and distribute content, breaking down the traditional one-way communication model between content creators and recipients. It has resulted in a diverse range of opinions being shared among users in online networks. This transformation aligns with Jürgen Habermas' concern that digitalisation has expanded and fragmented the public sphere, giving rise to semi-public communication spaces where individuals act as authors without editorial mediation.

Social networking sites converge diverse social groups into a single communicative space, complicating also identity-building. Regarding Erving Goffman's theory of impression management, people often perform and negotiate their self-presentation for multiple audiences. For example, a political post shared online as a personal opinion may be seen by various actors, such as strangers, employers, family members, or friends, each interpreting it through their own expectations and social norms. As a result, the boundaries between various social roles become increasingly blurred, making strategic self-presentation and the construction of identities more challenging in networked online environments.

Keywords: social network sites, self-presentation

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News Avoidance

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News avoidance refers to the intentional or unintentional phenomenon, where intentional news avoidance is based on a specific distaste for news that drives an individual to deliberately steer clear of news exposure; and unintentional news avoidance is not based on a specific distaste for news, but rather stronger preferences for other types of media content.

Skovsgaard and Andersen stated that in addition to the distinction between the intentional or unintentional nature, three types of news avoidance can be identified in terms of their scope: consistent, occasional, and selective.

Palmer, Toff, and Nielsen argue that categorising news avoiders based on motivations risks misunderstanding the kind of news avoidance that matters most from a normative standpoint: that which is linked with low news consumption. Survey results show that most people who selectively avoid news consume almost as much news as those who do not, while interviews show that distinguishing types of news avoiders based solely on stated motivations poorly captures how media habits develop through a mix of deliberate choices and socially constructed preferences.

The term 'news avoidance' has thus spurred much debate, but also potential confusion, as it seems to build on foundations of 'news' as a distinct entity as something to know, and with some measure of deliberate intent, from which to shy away.

Keywords: constructive journalism, media trust

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Nomination

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In discourse studies, especially in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), *nomination* refers to the linguistic process by which social actors (individuals, groups, or institutions) are identified, labelled, or categorised in discourse. This process is central to how social actors are represented and how their roles, identities, and relationships are constructed and framed. Nomination often involves the use of proper nouns, titles, or descriptive labels that frame actors in specific ways. Through specific nominations and categorisations, speakers can subtly promote particular values, framing events, actions, or individuals to achieve broader (often manipulative) goals.

Some of the typical categories addressed in CDA when examining nominations are in-group and out-group terms. The former are used to refer to social actors with which speakers identify (usually through positive references to the group), while out-group labels distance or stigmatise others (typically through negative references such as *illegal immigrants*). Such nominations can either empower or stigmatise, victimise, and marginalise actors, depending on how they are represented in discourse. Thus, in opinion research, nomination serves as an important linguistic realisation that can be related to polarisation and ‘othering’ strategies.

The concept is primarily associated with van Leeuwen’s theory of social actors, but it is an important component of other CDA frameworks, such as Reisigl and Wodak’s approach. In their framework, the process of nomination is linked to referential strategies and is a key element of the broader discursive strategies used to construct social identities and manage social power, including predication, argumentation, perspectivation, intensification, and mitigation.

Keywords: critical discourse analysis, othering, polarisation

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Objectivation

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This concept was introduced by Theo van Leeuwen in his 1996 work ‘The Representation of Social Actors’ as part of a framework for analysing how social actors are represented in discourse. Objectivation appears when individuals or groups are depicted through references to a place or object closely linked to them or their actions. One of the typical figures employed to implement objectivation is metonymy where something associated with a person or their activity is used to represent them. Objectivation can take a form that includes spatialisation, utterance autonomisation, instrumentalisation, and somatisation. Spatialisation occurs when people are represented by a place closely connected to them. Utterance autonomisation happens when people are identified through their speech or written statements. Instrumentalisation represents people in terms of the tools they use in their actions. Somatisation reduces people to body parts rather than individuals. Objectivation in discourse serves several key functions. First, it can obscure agency and responsibility, making it unclear who is responsible for human action. Second, replacing individuals with institutions, documents, or abstract entities, objectivation can lend an impersonal, authoritative tone and contribute to the creation of (epistemic) authority. Third, it might strengthen the collective, group, or national identity through spatialisation when individuals are represented by the country, erasing the differences between them. Fourth, by referring to people as body parts or tools, objectivation can strip them of individuality or humanity. Objectivation might also contribute to reproduction of power structures by representing some phenomena as natural.

Keywords: instrumentalisation, metonymy, spatialisation, somatisation

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Objectivity

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Objectivity is the quality of being based on facts and unbiased by personal feelings or interpretations. In philosophy, objectivity is an opinion or methodology that assumes that reality exists outside of the human mind, so that people can separate their own ideas and opinions from the observations they make (knowledge).

From a philosophical perspective, the classical correspondence theory states that truth is based on facts—it corresponds to them. Objectivity, then, stems from this factual correspondence. It is often contrasted with subjectivity and is commonly associated with mind-independence and realism. For instance, Thomas Nagel describes objectivity as a ‘view from nowhere’. In logical positivism, Moritz Schlick defined (scientific) knowledge as propositions that can be verified.

As outlined above, assertions (broadly understood as opinions) are objective and represent true beliefs if they correspond to facts. For example, the statement ‘I live in Slovakia’ is a verifiable claim—its truth depends on my actual place of residence. However, if I say, ‘Slovakia is the most beautiful place on Earth’, verifying this claim would require universal, measurable criteria for beauty, which may not exist. Similarly, if I state, ‘I think Slovakia is the most beautiful place’, verification would depend on whether I am sincere and not misinterpreting my own preferences. Likewise, ‘I like Slovakia’ expresses a subjective preference, which could be verified by assessing whether I am accurately describing my mental state. Moral claims, such as ‘The government of Slovakia is not good’, present a different challenge. They could, in principle, be evaluated using objective moral criteria, though the existence of such criteria remains debated in metaethics. Alternative theories of truth, such as coherence theory, propose that truth depends on a belief’s coherence within a system, offering another perspective on objectivity.

Keywords: belief, subjectivity, truth

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Opinion

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Opinion is a viewpoint, thought(s), or attitude formed in the mind about a particular issue, but it may not be based on fact or knowledge. Once it is expressed in some manner and shared with others, it has moved beyond mere thinking. These numerous ideas (as well as opinion expression, holders, types) reflect the diversity of human thought and intellectual inquiry. In considering opinions, one should be mindful of potential subjectivity, non-factual nature, variability, and expressiveness.

Various academic disciplines use opinion in their studies, including Medical Ethics, Law, Education, Environmental Studies, Literature and Cultural Studies, History, Philosophy, Media and Communication Studies, Economics, Sociology, Psychology, and Political Science. Philosophy, for example, tends to offer views on ideals, knowledge, being, logic, and cognisance. Political Science focuses on political structures, beliefs, authority, power, control, fairness, and the state. Sociology emphasises society, organisations, relationships, inequity, civilisation, and identity, among other issues. Psychology examines comportment, awareness, and human advancement. Economics considers models, marketplaces, state involvement, and disparity. History digs into occurrences, actions, and progress over time. Literature and Cultural Studies look at textual representation as well as impact on social attitudes. Media and Communication Studies analyse public discourse and accounts. While law unearths interpretation and application of rulings and decrees. Concerns surrounding opinion include confirmation bias, subjectivity, and diverging perspectives.

Keywords: disciplines, viewpoint, subjective

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Opinion (Speech) Event

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Opinion (Speech) Event, proposed as a term by Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk et al., is a dynamic happening or occurrence, according to Gerard and Orive, centred around the formation and expression of a subjective judgment or belief about a Target (Opinion Object). It assumes the presence of an Author, i.e., opinion holder, who expresses his/her (positive or negative) judgement/evaluation of a Target to an Addressee. The Addressee may play either the role of an opinion receiver or an opinion Target, or else function in both the interactional roles. The term *speech event* is neutral as to the communicative medium - it can refer either to spoken or written communication. For Burnstein and Vinokur, this type of event assumes the presence of both a Target and an Addressee, as well as a transfer medium, together with a persuasive force present in the opinionated expression act. Effects of such an event are either positive (opinion support by the Addressee) or negative (rejection), embodied in the Addressee's raising emotionality and potential for evaluative judgment of the Target. Thus, Brown and Levinson find opinions are meant to possess *a persuasive effect* on the Addressee and exert a change: both pragmatically in terms of the face maintenance or else face threat or loss with the relevant Target, and emotionally, via their positive or negative affective (sentiment) value, both on the Addressee and on the associated Target.

Keywords: judgment, opinionated expression act, persuasive effect

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Opinion Expression

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Opinion expression is the act of conveying one's thoughts, beliefs, or judgments about a topic through words, actions, or other communication forms. It is a central concept in public opinion research, where different approaches vary in how they value public expression of opinions.

In the survey-based paradigm, opinion expression is primarily a methodological concern: to answer the questions in polls in an adequate manner, individuals must have knowledge of and understand the issue and be able to express an opinion on it. Much criticism of survey research targets the underlying assumption that respondents are informed and interested in the survey topic, while in fact people often answer survey questions even when they have no relevant opinion to give. Surveys often face criticism because people sometimes answer without having a genuine opinion, leading to 'pseudo-opinions' or 'non-attitudes', i.e., random, unstable responses rather than true, informed views.

Conversely, the deliberative paradigm places great emphasis on opinion expression. According to the public opinion as the product of a discursive interaction view, individual opinions do not count as public opinion unless they are publicly expressed. People's willingness to express their opinion publicly depends on their perception of the public opinion climate - what views are majority or socially accepted. Factors that may influence public opinion expression: fear of isolation, perception of public support, differences in power and social status, social knowledge, issue awareness, habits and opportunities of opinion expression. Social media has dramatically increased opportunities for public opinion expression. While promoting easy access and inclusiveness, digital media has also allowed perceived anonymity, perceived discussion benefits, or incivility to influence opinion expression. Social media may be used to express unrepresentative, inauthentic, ambiguous, controversial, and polarising opinions. Expression-based research has been mainly criticised for lack of demographic representativeness and selective collection of opinion statements.

Keywords: deliberative paradigm, public opinion climate

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Opinion Holder

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An opinion holder is an entity that holds an opinion about a specific topic, subject, or situation (opinion object). An opinion holder can be a person, organisation, country, or some other specific group of people expressing an opinion. The opinion could be expressed implicitly or explicitly, and when expressed explicitly, opinion holders of the propositional opinions are usually observed as agents of those opinions. Opinion holders are also called opinion sources; and they are usually explicitly mentioned in news, articles, or other formal documents; but in user-generated content such as posts, blogs, or reviews, they are the authors whose true identities may be unknown. Regarding how often opinion holders communicate about a specific topic, we can differentiate 'inactive' as those who do not seek out or receive advice from others on a specific topic; 'followers' as those whom opinion leaders influence; 'opinion leaders' who *lead* the formation of attitudes, public knowledge, and opinions; and 'mediatized opinion leaders', individuals who considerably use media for communicative exchange and information. In addition, regarding the level of opinion leadership and knowledge about a specific topic, four types of opinion holders are identified: 'informed opinion leaders' (both high opinion leadership and knowledge), 'uninformed opinion leaders' (average knowledge but high level of opinion leadership), 'silent experts' (high knowledge and low opinion leadership) and 'other' persons that possess little knowledge and leadership about a specific topic. In this line, it is valuable to mention the term 'opinionators' referring to individuals whose profession revolves around creating, disseminating, and interpreting ideas, values, and opinions in society, such as academics, journalists, artists, community activists, etc.

Keywords: opinionators, types of opinion holders

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Opinion Markers

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Opinion markers are linguistic devices that signal a speaker's or writer's subjective stance, attitude, or evaluation towards the information being conveyed. They are crucial for expressing personal viewpoints rather than presenting objective facts. These markers can take various forms, including: Adjectives and Adverbs: Words like 'good,' 'bad,' 'important,' 'sadly,' 'fortunately,' 'clearly,' or 'possibly' directly convey judgment or a degree of certainty; Verbs: Verbs such as 'believe,' 'think,' 'feel,' 'seem,' 'appear,' 'consider,' or 'doubt' indicate a mental state or an assessment; Nouns: Certain nouns, like 'opinion,' 'belief,' 'view,' or 'impression,' explicitly refer to subjective perspectives; (Introductory) Phrases and Clauses: Expressions such as 'in my opinion,' 'it seems to me,' 'I agree,' 'I disagree,' or 'from my perspective' clearly delineate the subjective nature of the statement.

Opinion markers can also take the form of the comparative and superlative degrees (*more adequate, the best, etc.*) and *emotive expressions* (*I hate it, I love it, etc.*). Evaluative terms are related to *emotional stances*, subject to the application of automatic *sentiment analysis* in discourse datasets. Besides linguistic opinion markers, one can also identify *visual opinion* markers, such as gestures and body language, and, in the case of written language, graphic design or text layout. Opinion markers are vital for effective communication, allowing for the nuanced expression of personal interpretations and fostering dialogue. They help distinguish between factual statements and subjective assessments, guiding the audience in understanding the speaker's position and the level of certainty associated with the information. Soylu et al. as well as Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk and Liebeskind (413-412) discuss opinion markers as closely related to attitude markers and various stance expressions.

Keywords: emotion, evaluation, opinion, stance

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Opinion Object

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The term ‘opinion object’ refers to the subject or entity about which someone expresses their opinion. Opinions can be expressed on anything, ranging from physical entities to abstract concepts; so an opinion object can be a person, a place, a product, an idea, an event, an organisation, a situation, a topic, or any other entity that can be a target of someone's opinion. People often express their opinions about objects through various means, including conversation, writing (such as reviews or blog posts), social media posts, surveys, or ratings. When discussing an opinion, the identification of the opinion object is crucial to provide context and clarity of the opinion itself. For example, consider the following social media post: ‘This song stands out for its rich melody and meaningful lyrics!’, where the opinion object is the song itself. Similarly, in a statement like: ‘The new government policy on renewable energy shows real commitment to sustainability’, the opinion object is the specific decision of the government. By recognising the opinion object, it becomes easier to understand and analyse the expressed opinion, shifting the focus from the opinion itself. The object can have a set of components and a set of attributes, as well as further appropriate subsets. For example, in product reviews, the object is usually the product and/or its specific attributes.

Keywords: entity, target of opinion

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Opinion Types

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‘Opinion’ is a *polysemous* lexical form constituting a *radial category* (see Radial Categories) of concepts, which refer to judgments, assessments, beliefs, emotions, and are based either on conclusions and interpretations of objective facts (knowledge), on linguistic interpretations of factual or non-factual statements, or on personal or communal judgments, or else on preferences and biases, not based on or related to evidence. Opinions can be expressed verbally or multimodally via body language, behaviour; they can be expressed directly (explicit opinions) or via indirect ways (implicit opinions).

Opinion types:

- Negative: an opinion that considers only bad aspects or properties of a person, situation, etc.
- Positive: an opinion that considers only good aspects or properties of a person, situation, etc.
- Biased: an unreasonable or unjustified preference or dislike based on one’s own or (an)other person(s)’ opinion
- Communal: an opinion shared, or used in common by members of a group or community
- Individual/Personal: an opinion expressed by one particular person rather than shared by other people
- Informed: a belief, judgment or way of thinking about something based on information
- Indirect: an opinion expressed in a way that is not obvious
- Personal (see Individual)
- Public: an aggregate of the individual views, attitudes, and beliefs about a particular topic, expressed by a significant proportion of a community. For Carey, traditional definitions of public opinion emphasised the influence of elites and those best informed in society, further on leading to the empirical analysis of public opinion in terms of opinion polls, measuring public opinion that represented the population.
- Expert: a belief or judgment about something given by an expert on the subject, ‘an individual that excels in his/her field’/Professional ‘an individual that is engaged in a particular profession’. Professional opinions are judgments/evaluations formed from data, science, evidence, principles, education, training, and/or relevant experience.
- Objective: An objective opinion is the one that sets aside one’s personal preferences or feelings about something and instead assesses it based on facts and reality.
- Subjective: A subjective opinion refers to someone’s personal opinions or feelings regarding a particular subject matter. Subjective views or opinions are not based on truth or fact. They are one person’s unique interpretation of an idea and their own thoughts, feelings, and background.

Keywords: knowledge, radial category, thought, truth

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Partisan Media Bias

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Partisan media bias refers to the tendency of news organisations to present information in a way that aligns with specific political ideologies, shaping public discourse through selective coverage, framing, and emphasis. This bias is often driven by economic incentives, audience preferences, and ideological affiliations, leading to fragmented information environments where individuals are exposed primarily to viewpoints that reinforce their preexisting beliefs. As media consumers increasingly turn to digital platforms and social media for news, algorithmic curation further amplifies partisan divides by prioritising engagement over balanced reporting. The resulting echo chambers and filter bubbles contribute to political polarisation, making it more difficult for people to engage with opposing perspectives. Understanding partisan media bias requires examining not only content production and distribution, but also audience behaviour and psychological biases that influence how individuals interpret and internalise information. By recognising these patterns, researchers and policymakers can explore strategies to promote media literacy and encourage a more informed and open public dialogue.

Several researchers involved in this field employ survey experiments, observational studies, and content analyses to discern the causal relationships between partisan media consumption and public opinion formation. Collectively, the state of the art in partisan media bias research showcases a dynamic field that integrates technological advancements, behavioural insights, and educational strategies to unravel the intricate dynamics between media bias and its societal consequences. Ongoing interdisciplinary efforts contribute to a nuanced and informed understanding of how partisan media bias shapes contemporary information landscapes.

Keywords: information landscape, partisan divide, psychological biases

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Passivisation

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Passivisation is a grammatical process in which the syntactic structure of an active sentence is rearranged so that the subject of the active sentence becomes the object of the passive sentence, e.g. when passivised, the active sentence ‘The cat chased the dog.’ is restructured into ‘The dog was chased by the cat.’ or the agentless form ‘The dog was chased.’. This structure is used to emphasise the recipient of the action (‘the dog’) rather than the doer of the action (‘the cat’).

Critical discourse analysts have suggested that passivisation (along with nominalisation) serves important ideological functions, such as deleting agency (especially by omitting the agents of negative actions), de-emphasising the doer of the action, emphasising the object or recipient of the action, expressing detachment, and diffusing responsibility (especially when used by powerful groups to shape or influence opinion climates). This category is especially important when analysing linguistic presentation of groups and their activities, especially concerning the questions of guilt or innocence. Analysis of syntactic aspects (including active versus passive sentences, among others) is also of special importance when examining negative out-group descriptions in public space.

Passivisation has recently become a subject of research in Natural Language Processing (NLP), particularly in the study of how neural language models acquire and process syntactic rules. NLP research explores the ability of language models to learn exceptions to syntactic rules, focusing on restrictions in English passivisation. Studies show that neural network-based language models can learn passive constraints similar to those observed in human language processing, suggesting that evidence for these exceptions is available in linguistic input. This highlights the potential of computational models to simulate human-like syntactic learning and provides insights into the mechanisms underlying language acquisition.

Keywords: agency deletion, critical discourse analysis, passive voice, syntactic structure

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Perspective

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The term ‘perspective’, often used interchangeably with ‘viewpoint’, is a fundamental concept in linguistics and discourse studies. It refers to the position or angle from which an individual perceives, interprets, and communicates about objects, people, or events. This concept is closely related to the notion of ‘vantage point’, which specifies the exact viewpoint from which information is conveyed. For cognitive linguists and discourse scholars, understanding vantage points is essential for exploring how language constructs meaning and shapes communication by influencing how information is presented and framed.

Perspective can be established through various linguistic mechanisms, including direct quotations and verbs of utterance and cognition, as in the following examples: ‘John said: ‘The world is going to end’’, or ‘Mary believes that the world will be fine’’. Perspectivisation attributes responsibility for information to a subject – typically the speaker, though not exclusively. This process expresses subjectivity in language and discourse, alongside subjectification. While subjectification connects information to the subject of discourse, perspectivisation links the information to a subject within the discourse itself.

Another important dimension is perspective-taking, which refers to the cognitive ability to understand and interpret situations from another person’s viewpoint. This skill is crucial for effective communication, as it enables individuals to appreciate how others perceive their environment and intentions. By aligning understandings through perspective-taking, speakers and listeners can engage in more meaningful and cooperative interactions, fostering empathy and reducing misunderstandings.

Keywords: perspectivisation, viewpoint

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Persuasion

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Persuasion is a process through which a message to which a person is exposed creates, or is intended to create, a change in their attitudes, beliefs, intentions, or behavior. The goal of persuasive attempts is to produce change. This attempt can be specific or rooted in broader ideological principles. In any case, persuasion is a daily process present in all areas of life: in education in general, in medicine, advertising, media, interpersonal relationships, politics, the workplace, and more. Scholars have approached the concept of persuasion in diverse ways, providing distinct definitions that shed light on its multifaceted nature. Among these perspectives are characterizations of persuasion as a communication process for eliciting desired responses, a conscious attempt to influence attitudes or behavior through messages, a symbolic activity for internalisation, and a successful intentional effort in situations where individuals have some measure of freedom. Combining these insights, persuasion can be defined as a symbolic process in which communicators aim to convince others to change their attitudes or behavior on a particular issue through the transmission of a message, all within an environment of free choice. In order for a message to be persuasive, it must pass through several stages, as described in the following information-processing model: Exposure to the message - Attention to the message - Comprehension of the message - Belief in the message - Retention of the message - Acting upon the message. Lately, the American Psychological Association (2018) defined it as an active attempt by one person to change another person's attitudes, beliefs, or emotions associated with some issue, person, concept, or object.

Keywords: attitudes, change, message

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Platformivity/Platformisation/Platform

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‘Platformivity’ or ‘platformisation’ refers to the process through which digital platforms, particularly online platforms like social media, influence various aspects of social, economic, and cultural life. These concepts highlight how platforms do not merely facilitate communication but actively structure interaction, visibility, and participation across various domains. ‘Platform studies’, an interdisciplinary academic field, focuses on the study of digital platforms. Scholars across disciplines investigate the roles, effects, and structures of platforms. The field provides a framework for understanding the complex nature of platforms, taking into account both their technical and algorithmic infrastructure and their broader social and political implications. It evolves alongside changes in technology and society, and includes the analysis of different types of digital platforms, such as social media.

A key area of interest is how platforms shape everyday user practices, including opinion expression and formation. The technical design of platforms, particularly their affordances and algorithmic infrastructure, affects how users access information, what content they encounter, and how they engage with it. Different platforms can foster distinct dynamics of public debate or political polarisation. For example, Yarchi et al. demonstrate how the visibility of comments, algorithmic curation, and the public or private nature of interaction lead Facebook, Twitter, and WhatsApp to promote different forms of polarisation. Other studies, such as by Humprecht et al., highlight how specific features on social media, like emotional reaction buttons, amplify polarised content and intensify emotional engagement. These findings underscore how platform-specific configurations influence not only what is visible, but also how opinions are formed, shared, and contested.

The approach also incorporates critical perspectives to examine issues such as inequality, bias, and the concentration of power within digital platforms. Platform studies contribute valuable insights to policy and regulation discussions, addressing challenges related to distrust, privacy, and misinformation. However, the field also faces criticism for a tendency toward technological determinism, limited attention to users and user agency, and insufficient focus on local and contextual variations in platform use.

Keywords: affordances, user agency, platform governance, infrastructure

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Polarisation

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Initially, the concept of polarisation was introduced to explain socio-economic inequalities, focusing on the widening gap between specific groups in terms of income distribution and opportunities. Nowadays, polarisation is understood not only in economic terms but has also become associated with the social practice of establishing a strict distinction between two antagonistic groups, the positive ‘Us’ (those who share our opinion, or the in-group) and the negative ‘Them’ (those who express an opposing opinion, or the out-group). These groups develop into incompatible opinion-based groups, where the person’s opinion defines their group membership. Polarisation can take different forms, including, for instance, positional polarisation (divergence in stances on specific issues), affective polarisation (deepening emotional hostility toward opposing groups), and interpretative polarisation (conflicting interpretations of the same events or facts).

Caused by the extreme fragmentation of the Internet into specific interest groups, polarisation corrodes social cohesion and reinforces ideological polarity, extremist behaviour, and information bias. Internet users tend to interact only with like-minded people and therefore distance themselves from alternative views and uncomfortable debates. Real-life interactions frequently require us to navigate diversity, while the virtual realm may exhibit more uniformity, not necessarily in demographic terms but in terms of shared interests and perspectives. Interest-based communities thus might replace location-based communities.

It is often argued that strong ideological polarisation fosters selective exposure and the emergence of information bubbles or ‘echo chambers’. In such bubbles, users tend to seek content that supports their opinions, contributing to misinformation and hate speech (see *Hate speech*), with homogeneity further reinforced by social media algorithms. However, this view is not universally accepted. Scholars like Axel Bruns question the impact of echo chambers, suggesting that their effects have been exaggerated and reflect a broader moral panic about the role of digital media in society.

Keywords: in-group, out-group, information bias

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Political Expression

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Political expression is a relatively young term in political communication research, one that has emerged alongside the rise of social media. Previous terms, like political debate or political dialogue, were not well-suited to capture the nature of expression on social media, where sometimes an opinion is stated without anyone responding to it or dialoguing with it, and where even a comment on an expression does not always constitute a form of discussion or dialogue. The definitions of political expression vary in the level of specificity on which they focus, with some focusing on expressing a specific opinion on current events or political processes; while others look more generally at behaviors that involve communicating one's political views, beliefs, or identities. Scholars also vary in what they see as political expression, including: on social media, these can include posts and videos, but also comments; some also see likes, shares, or reactions as potential forms of political expression. An additional distinction involves the individual versus collective aspects of political expression. Some work focuses on political expression as an intrapersonal communication process, occurring between the speaker and themselves. In this view, political expression does not require an interaction between social actors or assumes that others will speak back. Other scholars focus more on the collective dimensions, or on collective political expression, seeing it as a process that is social in nature. In this view, collective political expression involves speaking to an imagined audience and adding one's voice to an existing conversation, often by making use of shared symbolic resources. Finally, different platforms may shape the dynamics of political expression in different ways, which can be understood as the interaction between platforms' norms, affordances, and contents.

Keywords: expression, platform affordances, dialogue, political participation

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Politicisation

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Politicisation can be understood in two complementary ways: as the process by which an issue becomes the subject of political debate, or as the growing involvement of individuals or groups in political life. This notion is the subject of study among disciplines in the humanities and social sciences: for example, history, politics, or sociology. Carl Schmitt, a German political theorist with ties to Nazism, argued that politics concerns the distinction between friend and enemy. In contrast, Antonio Gramsci, an Italian Marxist theorist, posited that politics is a struggle for hegemony. The ruling class maintains its dominance by gaining the consent of subordinate classes, while politicisation refers to the process of challenging this hegemony by these subordinate classes. Max Weber, a German sociologist, stated that politicisation is the recognition that national politics affect individuals and localities as much, if not more, than local politics. Politicisation denotes the process by which individuals gain awareness of the relevance of nationwide politics.

The politicisation of issues can be analysed through various dimensions: cognitive (awareness of political issues), affective (emotional attachment to political entities), and behavioural (participation in political activities such as voting or protesting). Key actors include media organisations, civil society groups, political parties, and digital influencers. Objects of politicisation range from public policies and social issues, such as climate change and migration, to private life domains, such as gender identity. Indicators used in empirical research include survey data on political interest, media consumption, protest participation, and voting patterns. For instance, empirical studies have shown how social media platforms contribute to the politicisation of younger audiences by exposing them to contentious debates and activist content. Recent research also highlights varying degrees of politicisation in different European regions, depending on economic insecurity, institutional trust, and media ecosystems.

Keywords: digital political engagement, political awareness, social movement dynamics

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Polysemy

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Polysemy is a phenomenon whereby a single linguistic unit, most commonly a word, exhibits multiple distinct yet related meanings. For instance, the word *body* can refer to the human organism, a corpse, the trunk of a person, or the main part of an object or group, such as the *body of a car* or a *governing body*. While these meanings are distinct, they are cognitively and historically related, often extending from a central or prototypical sense through processes such as metaphor or metonymy.

Traditionally, the study of polysemy has belonged to lexical semantics, focusing on how word meanings develop and relate to each other. However, cognitive linguistics broadens this view, claiming that polysemy is not confined to the lexicon but is a fundamental characteristic of human language and cognition. According to this perspective, various 'levels' of language (for instance lexical, morphological, syntactic) are interrelated through polysemous structures.

Cognitive lexical semantics, a subfield of cognitive linguistics, investigates polysemy as a conceptual phenomenon. From this viewpoint, the multiple meanings of a word are not arbitrary or accidental, but reflect systematic patterns in mental representation. Polysemy is therefore understood to provide insights into how language users mentally structure and categorise experience.

Importantly, polysemy is distinguished from homonymy, where a single form has unrelated meanings (e.g. *bat* the animal vs. *bat* used in sports). In contrast, polysemous meanings are historically or conceptually connected. As such, the study of polysemy contributes to our understanding of meaning extension, semantic networks, and the embodied nature of language.

Keywords: cognition, word meaning, polysemous structures

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Power

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From a social sciences perspective, Power is the ability to cause or compel individuals and groups to act in a certain way or to refrain from acting in another way, usually through the use of various sanctions or the threat of such sanctions. Power can manifest as social-political power, which is expressed through threats of economic, social, or other forms of sanctions. The classical concept of power, as formulated by Max Weber, viewed power in political science and sociology as the capacity to influence, lead, dominate, or otherwise have an impact on the life and actions of others in society. He views power as a characteristic of a social actor—an individual, a group, or an institution. This actor uses power against other social actors in order to advance his/her own interests in the face of conflicting interests held by others. Social power is a key explanatory factor in sociological theories and helps to explain how norms and values are reflected in opinions, attitudes, and behaviors. A current definition of the concept of power, presented by the American Psychological Association, is the capacity to influence others, even when they try to resist it. Social power derives from several sources: control over rewards (reward power) and punishments or other force (coercive power); a right to require and demand obedience (legitimate power); others' identification with, attraction to, or respect for the power holder (referent power); others' belief that the power holder possesses superior skills and abilities (expert power); and the power holder's access to and use of informational resources. One of the topics that has attracted a great deal of attention is the evolution and diffusion of opinions on a network. People with diverse social power tend to influence opinions and shape them in complex networks in the current era.

Keywords: influence, social power, Max Weber

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Predication

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In the field of linguistics, predication refers to the grammatical relationship between a subject and its predicate within a sentence. The predicate typically contains the main verb and any accompanying elements such as objects, complements, or modifiers that express what is being said about the subject. For example, in the sentence *The protestors demanded justice*, the subject is *the protestors* and the predicate is *demanded justice*.

Beyond its grammatical definition, predication plays an important role in discourse analysis, particularly in Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). According to the analytical framework proposed by such scholars as Wodak, Reisigl, and KhosraviNik, predicational strategies are one of five key discursive strategies used to uncover implications manifested in discourse, alongside nomination, argumentation, perspectivisation, and intensification/mitigation.

In CDA, predication focuses on how social actors (often marginalised or vulnerable groups as opposed to those in positions of power) are characterised and represented through language. CDA researchers examine how individuals or groups are described, asking such questions as: *How are the social agents in a text described?* and *What qualities or characteristics are attributed to them?* For instance, in media texts, political actors may be described as *corrupt*, *heroic*, or *radical*, each of which reveals a specific ideological positioning.

Importantly, predication is not limited to overt evaluation. It also includes more subtle forms of characterisation, such as metaphors, presuppositions, and frequent collocations. Thus, examining predicational strategies can reveal how language constructs, reinforces, or challenges social stereotypes, power relations, and ideological stances across a variety of genres and contexts.

Keywords: critical discourse analysis (CDA), social actor representation, ideological positioning

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Prejudice

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Prejudice is a preconceived and typically negative attitude toward a person or group, formed without direct experience or logical reasoning. It is often based on group membership - such as race, religion, gender, or sexual orientation. Prejudices can include an affective component (e.g., nervousness, pity, hatred) and a cognitive component (assumptions and beliefs about groups).

Earlier research portrayed prejudice as the result of motivated and intentional processes. As overt forms of prejudice became socially unacceptable, researchers began to recognise that subtle behaviours might not reflect hidden negative intentions. Instead, they may result from unintentionally activated processes. This shift emphasised the role of cognitive processes and socialisation, acknowledging that prejudice often arises from everyday mental shortcuts and social influences.

Scholars also debate the scope of prejudice. Some advocate for a broad definition that encompasses any negative judgment based on group membership. Others argue against equating prejudice with any form of dislike or distrust. They point to research on prejudice since the mid-20th century, which has largely been motivated by efforts to understand and mitigate extreme expressions of unjustified group hatred.

This debate also extends to the relationship between prejudice and ideology. Proponents of the 'ideological symmetry thesis' suggest that individuals at both ends of the ideological spectrum can be equally intolerant of social groups whose values and beliefs conflict with their own. Opponents of this thesis contend that the primary goal of prejudice research has been to explain and seek to reduce intergroup violence. They maintain that available evidence indicates that conservatives' prejudice against minority groups constitutes a much more pressing social problem than liberals' prejudice against majority groups. From this perspective, any serious analysis of prejudice should take into account its real-world impacts, such as hate crimes and violent discrimination.

Keywords: cognitive processes, social groups, ideology

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Private/Public

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The differentiation between what is private and what is, or becomes, public is one of the fundamental dilemmas when describing the contemporary public sphere and opinion. The term *public* refers to a reality insofar as it is common to the general public and at the same time distinct from the individual's private place in the world. What is public is visible, open, accessible – as opposed to what is private, hidden, and concerns the individual's personal life and/or a limited group of people that are close to the individual. In the digital age, characterised by the mediatization of almost all areas of human life, the boundaries between what is public and what is private are fading. The areas of an individual's personal engagement (such as family, friends, individual interests, health, etc.) intertwine with areas of common interest (such as work, local society, social engagement, but also global issues, for instance political affairs). This is among others due to the multidimensional character of contemporary communication tools and the ways in which they are used. A systemic, political science approach to the private/public dichotomy takes into account the distinction between the activities of the state, the authorities or institutions derived from the authorities, and the area of grassroots civic activity (political community vs. civil society). In modern democracies, defining a conceptual framework for public or private affairs is only possible on a high level of generality. The domain of democracies developing in a deliberative spirit is the right of all citizens to participate in public affairs, whereas political life encompasses all systems of power, understood as the ability to make transformations.

Keywords: dichotomy, personal engagement, public sphere

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Prototype

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Prototype in Cognitive Linguistics is a concept in any given language, corresponding to a person, animal, thing, property, or event that best represents this concept. For example, when asked to give an example of the concept of furniture, *a chair* is more frequently cited than, say, a wardrobe. Prototype theory has been applied in linguistics as part of the mapping from phonological structure to semantics. The term *prototype*, as defined in psychology and later transferred to linguistics, was first proposed in Eleanor Rosch's study 'Natural Categories' (1973). Prototype analysis has become a key research tool in recent years in Cognitive Linguistics and in a cognitive psychological theory that suggests that when people categorise objects, they do so based on how similar the object is to a prototypical (ideal or the best) example of that category. The essential properties of prototypes are that they are *central, representative examples of categories*. For instance, when thinking of 'bird,' a robin or a sparrow is likely a more prototypical example than a penguin or an ostrich. Then, unlike the classical view, prototype theory proposes that category membership is not all-or-none. Instead, it is a matter of *degree*. Some members are more central or typical (closer to the prototype), while others are more peripheral or less typical. Because membership is graded, the boundaries between categories are often *fuzzy* rather than rigid. For Wittgenstein, categories are often structured around *family resemblances*. (This means that members of a category may share a network of overlapping features, without any single feature being common to *all* members. Furthermore, prototypes function as *cognitive reference points*, i.e., they help us organise, understand, and recall information about related concepts. The soundness of the prototype paradigm, according to van Brakel, in particular its basic assumptions relating to such core meanings in basic-level natural kinds, is one of the ways of explaining why human communication and learning are successful.

Keywords: basic-level natural kinds, categorisation, communication, learning

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Public Opinion

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Public Opinion describes the content and distribution of opinions toward an issue expressed and shared by members of a public. In a narrower sense, it refers to any stances that are supported by a majority or plurality (relying on an electoral metaphor); in a wider sense, it also includes a latitude of common stances that are recognised as legitimate, and can be expressed in public discourse without fear of being sanctioned. Accordingly, public opinion foregrounds the (actual or perceived) common ground or mainstream of opinions, discounting fringe, rare, and contested ones. Public opinion is said to be divided on an issue if no one stance is widely accepted as preferable or legitimate. It necessarily pertains to issues that are widely recognised as relevant to the public as a whole - most commonly, issues that are negotiated, or demanded to be negotiated, by political institutions. Public opinion presupposes the presence of a freely accessible public discourse enabling and synchronising public engagement and opinion formation toward these issues.

In social science research, public opinion is studied primarily as the outcome of public communication processes (from socialisation to cultural myth making to news and strategic communication), and as an antecedent of various forms of collective and mass behavior (e.g., political participation, consumer choices).

Within the study of public opinion, there are two competing paradigmatic views: One tradition, which has been dominant since the 1970s, understands public opinion as the statistical distribution of preferences held among members of the public, relying on quantitative survey methods for measurement; the other tradition, which dominated up to the 1950s, but is gradually resurfacing in the wake of agenda setting, framing, and digital media research, understands public opinion as a discursive process, and relies heavily on text analytic approaches.

Keywords: issues, collective preferences, public sphere

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Public Opinion as a Statistical Distribution

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Public Opinion as a Statistical Distribution conceives of public opinion as the distribution of evaluative stances regarding a given issue within a given public. This conceptualisation follows an electoral metaphor, wherein every member of the public is equally considered once, such that the count distribution of all opinions over a set of categories expresses the preferences of the public as a whole. Public opinion is said to support a certain idea if a majority of members of the public do so. Everyone's opinion counts the same, regardless of the identity of the opinion holder, the intensity or foundedness of the opinion, or other possible differences. Public opinion is typically understood as predictive of individuals' behavioral choices.

Public Opinion as a Statistical Distribution is closely related to a quantitative methodological perspective wherein opinions are elicited by means of standardised survey questions from a population statistically representative of the considered public. Operationally, this approach presumes that people hold attitudes toward an issue and are capable of mapping their preferences upon a given set of categories or dimensions, which must be defined by the investigator. Using standardised scales, public opinion dynamics can be measured as over-time changes in the distribution of opinions. Public opinion as statistical distribution is most commonly studied as an antecedent and predictor of collective choices and mass behavior, such as electoral votes, health behavior, consumer selection, or other life choices. Other applications, which often complement survey methods with experimental designs, seek to explain the distribution of opinions based on personal traits, experiences, and exposure to various forms of information available in public discourse. A key limitation of this conceptualisation is that recorded opinions may be more or less deep-rooted and thus differentially relevant for predicting behavior, or shaping others' views, by means of being expressed in public discourse.

Keywords: aggregation, public opinion polls, majority

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Public Opinion as a Discursive Process

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Public Opinion as a Discursive Process conceives of public opinion as an outcome of the public debate about an issue. It circumscribes the range of interpretations and stances toward an issue that prevail in the public debate among members of the public: Positions are inserted into the public debate by any speaker with access to the public arena, where they are endorsed, elaborated, challenged, or re-negotiated by other speakers in a dynamic process. Participants continuously renegotiate what issues are of public relevance, how they can be conceptualised, and how they should be evaluated. In the course of this process, some ideas and opinions emerge as widely-agreed upon or recognised as legitimate within an accepted corridor of opinions or opinion climate, while others are demarcated as contested or face delegitimation. Accordingly, public opinion appears as a collaborative social construction that is directly accessible to researchers and members of the public alike by means of studying the contents of public discourse, or indirectly via people's subjective perceptions of public opinion negotiations in public discourse (as perceived public opinion climates).

A key challenge in this conceptualisation of public opinion concerns the need to determine which contributions to the public debate matter, and how much weight to attribute to them. If earlier scholarship could focus on key institutional arenas (notably, parliamentary discourse, legacy mass media), the growth of digital media has blurred the lines between salient, widely influential sites and voices ('opinion leaders'), and others whose impact upon public opinion is less certain.

Public Opinion as a Discursive Process is typically studied using qualitative discourse, and quantitative content-analytic methods, and increasingly also computational methods. A key limitation, especially of computational approaches, is their strong sensitivity to uneven content availability and strategic manipulations of the visibility of certain opinions. Also, the approach permits no conclusions about the statistical distribution of opinions, as held opinions are likely to be expressed in public differently.

Keywords: negotiation, public discourse, public opinion climate

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Publics/Mainstream Publics/Counter-Publics

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Works on counter-publics critically engage with classical public sphere theory and its inherent notion that there is a single, overarching public sphere for civic deliberation on state activities. Inspired by Nancy Fraser, the following understanding of counter-publics is widely held in the literature: (1) subaltern publics or publics aware of their subordinate status; (2) that stand in a conflictual relationship; (3) with dominant or mainstream publics; (4) that criticise discursive mechanisms of exclusion related to participation, topics/issues, and styles of speech. Counter-publics (5) seek to overcome these exclusions in the hope that power structures can be changed, thereby (6) expanding discursive space.

Critical thinkers argue that political deliberation and public opinion formation are permeated by societal hierarchies and power structures, and that even democratic decisions are inevitably shaped by majority consensus, often favoring dominant groups in society. Counter-publics advocate alternative positions with divergent terminology, communication styles, and norms.

According to Fraser, counter-publics function, on the one hand, as spaces of refuge and reorganisation, and on the other hand, as hubs and preparation sites for activist efforts targeting wider audiences. In this way, counter-publics serve both inward-looking goals as safe spaces for developing and cultivating alternative identities and objectives; and outward-looking goals, aiming to challenge, disrupt, and reshape dominant public consensus by reaching out to and connecting with larger segments of the audience. Intersections for such outward-looking activities, e.g., to influence public opinion, can be found on social media or in commenting spaces on news sites. Although originally conceived as discursive arenas for marginalised groups, recent research also applies the concept to nationalistic and populist discourses.

Keywords: discursive space, power structures, mechanisms of exclusion

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Relativism

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Relativism is the philosophical position that all points of view are equally valid, often applied to moral and cultural values. It asserts that all assignments of truth values to individual propositional variables are relative to the perspective of an observer or the context in which they are assessed (e.g., local cultural norms, individual standards). In a philosophical sense relativism asserts that the truth of claims holds when the relevant framework of assessment is specified or supplied. Furthermore, there can be no framework-independent vantage point from which the matter of whether the thing in question is can be established.

Forms of relativism can be distinguished in terms of their objects (e.g., truth, goodness, beauty) and their subject matters (e.g., science, law, religion). There are forms of relativism identified by Swoyer in terms of their domains or frames of reference—e.g., conceptual frameworks, cultures, historical periods, etc. Relativism is most often confronted with *objectivism* and *realism*. Objectivism is the position that cognitive, ethical and aesthetic norms and values, including truth, are independent of judgments and beliefs. For Baghramian and Carter, Realism entails both the objectivity and singularity of truth. Cultural relativism (*cultural determinism*), on the other hand, proposes that cultural practices of groups should be perceived in terms of their own cultural contexts. The sources of cultural relativism can also be found in anthropological linguistics with theses put forward by Franz Boas, Edward Sapir, as well as in Benjamin Lee Whorf's linguistic relativity theory).

Keywords: beliefs, culture, judgment, objectivity, truth

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Resonance

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Resonance is commonly used as a conceptual metaphor to describe the process by which verbalised opinions (including related notions such as factual claims, frames, and interpretations) come to be accepted and adopted by other members of a public. Among the available explanations of persuasiveness, resonance distinctly focuses on the adoption of opinions owing to their fit within a context of socialised cultural norms, experiences, and beliefs, foregrounding socio-cognitive, shared heuristics - notably, relevance, plausibility, appropriateness. Resonance is primarily reflected in others' self-directed, common re-use of the same or similar opinion statements; however, wider usages have also considered lesser responses (e.g., clicking Like), or even no response at all, as capable of expressing resonance, so long as it can be inferred that the proposed ideas have been widely adopted. Resonance is used to describe two somewhat distinct meanings: On the one hand, resonance describes the seamless adoption of ideas into people's existing ways of thinking, emphasising their so-perceived plausibility and appropriateness. On the other hand, resonance also describes the frequent re-use of ideas primarily that are perceived as plausible and relevant, but raise normative conflicts, raising wide-spread controversial engagement with these ideas (e.g., eliciting large amounts of responses). Critics have pointed out that resonance remains an under-theorised construct, with few underlying mechanisms adequately established, which is therefore too commonly used in a vague, metaphorical sense only.

Keywords: appropriateness, plausibility, relevance

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Sarcasm

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The scientific literature helps to distinguish sarcasm from similar forms such as irony. These forms are so regularly confused that they have become - wrongly - synonymous. Although Morell states they are both based on an intentional lack of sincerity, the two phenomena do not behave in the same way, either in terms of intention or the relationship between what is said and thought. Firstly, Haiman finds irony can be unintentional and qualify a situation, which is never the case with sarcasm. Secondly, for Charaudeau irony is based on an inversion of meaning between what is said and what is thought, whereas sarcasm hyperbolises the negative aspect of the flaw it points out in its target without there being, strictly speaking, any discrepancy between what is said and what is thought.

Unlike irony, sarcasm does not necessarily rely on figurative language, but on an amplification of Face Threatening Acts (FTAs). Irony and sarcasm are both an attack on the principles of politeness theorised by Brown and Levinson, according to which communication can only take place properly if each speaker respects the other 'faces'. Sarcasm takes different forms, but it always has a perlocutionary intention that runs counter to the relational management of communication, since it always aims to harm the positive side of its target, claims Lombart. There is therefore no such thing as 'positive' sarcasm, although there are forms of positive irony - albeit rather rare - which do not intend to attack the faces of their target. When the object of sarcasm is a third party (person, concept, institution, etc.), the speaker seeks the audience's complicity in the denigration, resembling gossip. When it targets the interlocutor, it becomes a direct provocation, as sarcasm leaves no ambiguity and compels the other to respond.

To illustrate the concepts of sarcasm and irony, consider the following examples. The statement 'crazy to have an ugly face like yours'; can be interpreted as sarcasm, as it attacks the other person's appearance without using a common trope. On the other hand, the statement 'You look really good this morning'; made to someone who is ill, can be seen as a form of irony, as it employs an antinomic trope to convey the opposite meaning of the words used. It is evident that the speaker's face is under threat; however, the intensity of the attack is comparatively lower than the previous example.

Keywords: face-threatening acts, pragmatics, politeness theory

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Schema

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A schema is a cognitive structure or mental representation that organises and categorises our knowledge about the world. Schemas function as internal templates that guide our perception, interpretation, and understanding of both linguistic and non-linguistic stimuli. They help us make sense of new experiences by relating them to existing knowledge and expectations. In the framework of Cognitive Grammar, schemas are viewed as dynamic, context-sensitive constructs that shape our conceptualisation of reality. Rather than being fixed or static, schemas are continuously updated through interaction, experience, and language use. They are conceived as networks of interconnected elements (including concepts, relationships, and cognitive operations) which support both linguistic competence and broader cognitive processes. Schemas operate across different levels of abstraction. At the lower end, perceptual schemas organise basic sensory-motor experiences, such as motion, shape, or spatial orientation. At higher levels, conceptual schemas structure more abstract knowledge, such as categories, event types, or social roles. This gradation allows schemas to bridge concrete bodily experience with complex thought. Linguistic expressions evoke or activate schemas. For example, understanding a sentence requires drawing on schematic knowledge of grammar, event structure, and meaning. Thus, schemas play a vital role in the construction of meaning during communication. Moreover, schemas are also embodied. They are grounded in our physical and sensory-motor experiences. This embodied dimension allows for the integration of perceptual, motor, and affective information into conceptual representations, reflecting the close connection between language, thought, and bodily experience. Schemas are therefore not only linguistic tools but also fundamental to human cognition, enabling flexible yet structured conceptualisation across contexts.

Keywords: cognitive structure, mental representation, categorisation

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Semantics

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For Saeed as well as Riemer, Semantics is a core subfield of linguistics concerned with the study of meaning in language. It focuses on how linguistic elements such as words, phrases, and sentences convey meaning, both individually and in combination. Central to semantic analysis is the relationship between linguistic expressions and the entities or concepts to which they refer. This includes investigating how meaning is encoded in linguistic forms and how it is interpreted by speakers and listeners in various contexts.

Both Pulman and Leech find that Semantics is traditionally distinguished from pragmatics. While semantics addresses the literal, context-independent meaning of expressions—often as part of an abstract language system—pragmatics deals with how language is used in context, including aspects such as speaker intention, irony, metaphor, and conversational implicature. In other words, semantics concerns what utterances mean in isolation, whereas pragmatics explores what speakers mean when they use those utterances in real communicative settings.

Historically, Ferdinand de Saussure defined semantics as the study of the relationship between the signifier (form) and the signified (concept). Charles Morris offered a semiotic perspective, defining semantics as the study of the relation between signs and the things they designate. These foundational views highlight the interdisciplinary nature of semantics, bridging linguistic form, logic, and meaning.

Although semantics covers a wide range of phenomena, it typically excludes context-sensitive or non-literal uses of language, such as irony or metaphor, which are the domain of pragmatics.

Keywords: meaning, linguistic signs, literal meaning, pragmatics

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Sentiment

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In a communication context, sentiment is the individual's subjective attitude or point of view regarding a particular subject. It demonstrates how a person perceives and evaluates the topic of their communication. A statement's general orientation and tone are included in its sentiment, which primarily categorises it as neutral, negative, or positive. Understanding the nuances of opinions and interpersonal interactions requires this subjectivity. Sentiment enables people to voice their thoughts on a range of topics, such as political issues, social trends, and individual experiences. For instance, when someone comments on a new environmental policy, they might say that it is 'beneficial for future generations,' which shows their values and beliefs, or that it is 'ineffective and poorly planned,' which shows their disapproval. Sentiment can be measured by observing linguistic cues such as word choice and phrasing that reveal the speaker's point of view. Indicators of sentiment often include specific words (e.g., good, amazing, wonderful for positive sentiments; and bad, poor, terrible for negative ones). Phrases and idioms also convey sentiment and, together with sentiment words, form what is known as a sentiment lexicon. For example, when reviewing a product, one customer might write, 'This smartphone has an excellent battery life,' while another might write, 'The camera quality is disappointing.' Neutral sentiment may be evoked by objective statements that do not use strong evaluative language, such as 'The meeting starts at 10 AM.' In many fields, including marketing, communication, and the social sciences, an understanding of sentiment is essential because it helps practitioners and researchers evaluate attitudes, predict behaviours, and appropriately adjust messages. Sentiment analysis can reveal crucial information about people's attitudes towards specific subjects and the underlying causes of their opinions and actions. For instance, examining voter sentiment can assist political campaigns in creating plans that successfully engage their supporters.

Keywords: expressivity, sentiment analysis

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Sentiment Analysis

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Sentiment analysis (or opinion mining) refers to the process of analysing digital texts to understand how language is used to evaluate, express opinions, attitudes, and emotions. By combining natural language processing, machine learning, and computational linguistics, sentiment analysis contributes to understanding opinion dynamics by measuring the sentiment or tone of communication in large datasets, such as social media posts or online reviews. Using text classifiers, sentiment analysis typically assigns a positive or a negative viewpoint to a text, predicting its polarity. This technique is widely used in market and communication research to gauge consumer satisfaction and analyse media coverage of various political, economic, and social topics.

Sentiment analysis can be conducted manually (expensive, time-consuming) or automatically using sentiment analysis tools (cost-effective, timesaving). There are two common types of automated sentiment analysis: dictionaries-based and supervised machine learning approaches. Despite its popularity, the efficiency, validity, and reliability of automated sentiment analysis in accurately determining sentiment has been questioned. The validation of sentiment measurements derived from automated sentiment analysis in communication and social sciences research has been under scrutiny. Studies have shown that automated sentiment analysis methods, whether using dictionaries or supervised machine learning, are generally less reliable and are always outperformed by manual (human) coding.

Automated sentiment analysis, despite its increasing sophistication, still faces significant challenges in accurately capturing the sentiment of opinion expressions. These challenges stem from linguistic phenomena such as irony, sarcasm, context-dependent expressions, as well as the inherent emotionality and subjectivity of language use. While automated sentiment analysis can provide useful insights, its validity for research purposes is limited, and, therefore, the results should be carefully reviewed and validated by human annotators to ensure accuracy and reliability.

Keywords: computational linguistics, sentiment, opinion expression

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Slurs

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Slurs are a specific type of derogatory expressions that convey a negative attitude of the speaker towards the target (typically the addressee) or the targets (addressees) seen as a demographic group. The object of attack refers to such demographic aspects as: nationality, age, religion, race, sexual orientation, profession, or ability. Slurs are often understood as expressive terms that both describe and denigrate, carrying not only propositional content but also strong evaluative and affective force.

Slurs differ from slander in that slander typically involves truth-conditional claims intended to damage someone's reputation, whereas slurs are not truth-conditional but are used to denigrate individuals based on their perceived membership in a social group (e.g. *immigrants, Islamists, Nigga, slut, gays*, etc.). Slurs also differ from insults, which usually target personal traits or behaviour, while slurs refer to characteristics associated with a group identity. Also, unlike general insults, slurs derive their offensive power from their historical, ideological, and social embedding within systems of discrimination and marginalisation.

Slurs can be reappropriated by the targeted communities for non-derogatory purposes, although this process is highly context-sensitive and not universally accepted. Such reclaimed uses typically involve so-called *in-group* usage; that is, instances where terms generally regarded as slurs are appropriated by members of the respective target group with non-derogatory, often ironic or subversive, intent (e.g. *nigger/nigga* as used by some African-Americans).

In digital contexts, slurs are often embedded in coded language, creative respellings, or some other novel formations, often used to evade moderation or for narcissistic purposes. In research on public discourse and opinion, slurs provide insight into how language reflects and reinforces social hierarchies and hostilities, especially in relation to hate speech, othering, and dehumanisation.

Keywords: derogatory expression, demographic group, insults, hate speech

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Social Media

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Social media are digital platforms that enable interactive communication and user-generated content creation. Rooted in Web 2.0 technologies, they have transformed communication from linear, one-way messaging to dynamic, participatory exchange. Social media include a wide variety of tools and applications such as blogs, forums, social networking sites (SNS), microblogs (e.g., X), media-sharing services (e.g., YouTube, Instagram), and instant messaging platforms (e.g., WhatsApp, Skype). These technologies facilitate rapid dissemination of information and support the formation of digital communities.

Social media are distinguished by interactivity, real-time feedback, and the convergence of producer and consumer roles in the figure of the ‘prosumer’. Users not only consume media but also actively contribute by posting, commenting, and sharing. Communication is multidirectional and often public, which increases the visibility and potential virality of messages.

A core aspect of social media is algorithmic content curation, which personalises user experience while shaping exposure to information, potentially reinforcing filter bubbles and echo chambers. These algorithmic dynamics, combined with the speed of communication, influence how opinions form, evolve, and spread online. Emotionally charged content tends to achieve greater engagement, which has significant implications for political discourse, misinformation, and polarisation. From a pragmatic perspective, social media reshape language use and discourse practices. They introduce new registers, abbreviated forms, memes, and multimodal strategies. In opinion research, social media serve as rich data sources for analysing public sentiment, discourse dynamics, and digital activism.

Keywords: digital platforms, user-generated content

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Sources of Opinion

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Sources of opinion identification can be manifold, according to Lewandowska-Tomaszczyk et al, - from linguistic verbal signals of various kinds to multimodal resources (gestures, facial expression, eye contact, body posture and movement, etc. and prosodic features). More generally, the sources of opinions as different from evidence-based knowledge can be found in gossip, hearsay, in which no evidence needs to be present, those with uncertain evidence such as beliefs, or else opinions stemming from logical fallacies or conspiracy theories, fake news, together with myths, stereotypes, ideology, etc. (456).

Opinions can also originate from deeper psychological and social roots. Factors such as upbringing, family environment, education, and cultural background often shape the way individuals form opinions, even before they are expressed through language. Similarly, exposure to art, nature, or emotional experiences may also influence opinion formation in less direct but meaningful ways. On the other hand, Stefkovics and Dömötör, for example, find that *public opinion*, derived from the polling data, can be influenced by public relations and the political media. Additionally, mass media utilises a wide variety of advertising techniques to get their message out and change the minds of people.

It should also be mentioned that computational methods view opinion source identification as an *information extraction task* and tackle the problem using sequence tagging and pattern matching techniques simultaneously with reference to syntactic, semantic, and orthographic lexical features, dependency parse features, and opinion recognition features. In addition, Choi et al see features based on automatically learned extraction patterns are used, performing feature induction on models.

Keywords: information extraction, verbal signals, multimodal resources, uncertain evidence

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Sourcing

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Sourcing describes one out of a range of potential foundations of an opinion, alongside others such as evidence or the epistemic quality of the belief. An opinion based on sourcing reflects a belief about an object, person, or event that is linked to a specific external point of reference (source). Sources can function as origins (where an opinion comes from) and as warrants (why an opinion is considered justified), depending on how they are invoked in a discourse. Sources can also take various forms, ranging from eye-witness accounts to expert statements, documents, or databases. Providing sources for an opinion is typically associated with increased validity of connected statements about a part of reality and may, therefore, enhance the persuasiveness of a factual statement. Different types of sources are oftentimes ascribed different levels of credibility or trustworthiness, which, in turn, also increase the persuasiveness of the connected statement.

Research that focuses on opinion discourses often revolves around the question of what sources are provided to back up seemingly factual statements. Journalism research, for instance, is concerned with what sources journalists use to report on ongoing events or issues and how journalists transform available source material into news articles. Similarly, scholars have also focused on how opinions in online discourses are backed up by different forms of sources and how the usage of sources with a different credibility shapes the persuasiveness of these statements. A central concern in this is the increasing usage of manufactured or artificially modified source material, for instance, in the form of so-called deep fakes.

Research focused on opinion formation processes often explores how various forms of sources can impact the opinion formation and information processing of individuals. In this context, credibility and trustworthiness have been identified as key determinants influencing opinions based on sourcing.

Keywords: opinion-formation, foundedness

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Speech Act/Speech Event

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Speech Acts are goal-directed actions performed with words in interpersonal communication, defined primarily with reference to the speaker's intentions and the effects on the listener(s). Whereas, a speech event is an occasion on which a speech is made, especially a formal or public one. It can also refer to the act or process of speaking, especially in a formal or public setting. Speech events are typically goal-oriented, interactive, and shaped by the social and cultural context in which they occur.

Referring to Austin, Speech acts are utterances which perform various social functions such as requesting, greeting, advising, complaining, warning, and so on (see also Speech Act Theory). Austin classified three types of speech act: 1. Locutionary act - the actual utterance and its ostensible meaning; 2. Illocutionary act - the real meaning that the speaker intended; 3. Perlocutionary act - the actual effect of the speech act, whether it was intended by the speaker or not.

Searle classified illocutionary speech acts into the following taxonomy: 1. Assertives - acts that commit the speaker to the truth of a proposition; 2. Directives - acts that cause the hearer to do something; 3. Commissive - acts that commit the speaker to do something in the future; 4. Expressives - acts that express the speaker's feelings towards something; 5. Declarations - acts that change reality (such as baptising, pronouncing someone guilty, etc.)

Speech act theory has been influential in a wide range of fields, including linguistics, philosophy, communication studies, and law. It has also been used to develop new approaches to understanding social interaction and human behaviour.

Keywords: illocutionary, locutionary, perlocutionary

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Stance

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Stance, evaluation, and, with the advent of social media, sentiment are concepts describing people's opinions (judgements) about an issue, which are often interchangeably used in public opinion research. Individual opinions emerge from the interaction between individuals and the world in which they live. Such opinions are judgements (evaluative stances) of issues made by individuals based on their psychological and cognitive predispositions. To form an opinion about an issue implies to have taken a stance on that particular issue. However, unless their opinion is publicly expressed (via language, usually) one cannot have access to the stance that an individual has taken on an issue on which they have an opinion. Expressing an evaluative stance means participating in a dialogic process where meanings are collaboratively constructed and negotiated in and through interaction in various contexts.

Linguistic approaches to opinionated communication distinguish between stance and evaluation: stance is a more abstract concept, whereas evaluation is the linguistic realisation of stance; the display and manifestation of stance in discursive interaction. From a linguistic perspective, stance is defined as the expression of speaker's or writer's opinions and assessments encoded in language they produce. Speakers/writers may convey assessments of the certainty or doubt (epistemic stance) or personal attitudes, judgements, emotions about the propositions they express (attitudinal stance or affect), or they may even assess the style of the communication (style stance, per Gray and Biber).

Research on the evaluative function of language has inventoried the linguistic markers of stance and grouped them into parameters of evaluation (e.g., (in)comprehensibility, emotivity, (un)expectedness, (im)possibility, reliability, evidentiality, per Bednarek) which may be used to examine opinions in a more nuanced way than simply as positive or negative attitudes or feelings about an issue held by an individual at a certain moment and in a particular context.

Keywords: evaluation, sentiment, opinion, judgements

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Stereotype (1)

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The concept of stereotypes was introduced in a social context by Walter Lippmann, he described them as Images that form in people's minds. Stereotypes are simplified, rigid, and often distorted mental images people hold about social groups. Contemporary definitions emphasize that stereotypes encompass beliefs and opinions regarding the traits, attributes, and behaviors associated with members of various social groups. They are understood as cognitive generalisations—mental shortcuts that include expectations and assumptions about a particular group or category. Stereotypes are conceptualised as a specific type of social concept, functioning similarly to other cognitive categories. Stereotypes are not merely individual biases but are shaped and reinforced through social interactions and cultural norms. This perspective highlights the role of societal structures in the formation and maintenance of stereotypes. Moreover, stereotypes serve as tools for social orientation, helping individuals navigate complex social environments by providing simplified representations of groups providing quick cognitive shortcuts. However, such simplifications can lead to misunderstandings and perpetuate social inequalities, bias, and misjudgment, especially when these representations fail to reflect individual variation.

Functionally, stereotypes resemble schemas in that they serve to streamline and expedite the processes of perception and judgment. Yet, their utility comes at a cost. Stereotypes are often exaggerated, skewed toward negativity, and remarkably resistant to change, even when individuals encounter people who contradict these generalised expectations.

The connection between stereotypes and opinions is significant: stereotypes form the cognitive basis for attitudes, shaping the emotional and evaluative responses people have toward outgroup members. As such, stereotypes do not exist in isolation but play a central role in the formation of prejudice and intergroup bias, influencing social behavior in subtle and persistent ways.

Keywords: bias, cognitive shortcuts, social groups, schemas

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Stereotype (2)

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Lippmann states stereotypes are a cognitive process through which individuals are ascribed specific characteristics based on their perceived membership in a particular social group, such as an ethnic, national, religious, or gender group. These fixed habits of cognition are not set in stone and can be reshaped by new experiences that challenge preconceived notions. It is a mental shortcut used to make sense of the world, which does not necessarily falsify reality, even though it is often the case. Stereotypes are typically adopted during the process of socialisation via cultural norms and unwritten expectations. Stereotypes can also affect perceptions, attitudes, and actions towards others, leading to negative consequences, such as prejudice and discrimination. Krook and Restrepo Sanín provide an example of a stereotype as the perception that women are less effective political leaders due to being seen as more emotional and less rational. These stereotypical assumptions, tied to traditional expectations of women as caring and family-oriented, could potentially lead to harsher judgement, for instance, in media coverage, where women are frequently questioned about balancing personal and professional life, scrutiny that their male counterparts typically do not face. Consequently, this may lead to discouragement from political participation or discriminatory behavior that excludes women from decision-making. Adopting the perspective of individuals targeted by stereotypes can help reduce their spread. Skorinko and Sinclair emphasise that if those individuals display traits consistent with the stereotype, perspective-taking may actually reinforce the stereotype. Blair counters that personal characteristics or a motivation to foster positive relationships with others can play a crucial role in reducing the automatic activation of stereotypes. Nevertheless, stereotypical frameworks can profoundly affect society's deliberative functioning by reinforcing biased attitudes and fostering intolerant behaviours.

Keywords: prejudice, discrimination

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Subjectivity

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Subjectivity and subjectivism, in a broad sense, relate to the subject, that is individual person, and are often linked to relativism. Relativism, based on the idea of relation, holds that truth is relative to the individual. Its notable proponents in philosophical history were, for example, the Sophists. Even nowadays, the term ‘sophism’ refers, however in a pejorative sense, to misleading arguments intended to manipulate opponents or audiences, as according to this approach the truth is relative.

Subjectivism is often seen as the opposite of objectivism, but in some contexts, they intersect in the idea of intersubjectivity. For example, agreement among multiple individuals on certain matters may bring us closer to truth, but some philosophers argue this does not guarantee infallibility. Subjectivism can take extreme forms, such as subjective idealism, which asserts that reality depends on perception, or solipsism, which claims that only our own mind exists and everything depends on it.

In the realm of morality, subjectivism or anti-realism suggests that moral claims are mere subjective opinions, making their truth dependent solely on the individual expressing them. According to this view, saying for instance ‘War is bad.’ expresses only personal emotions rather than a verifiable objective claim—similar to saying, ‘I like chocolate ice cream.’ Which can be true or false only in relation to the speaker. A. J. Ayer was a well-known advocate of this perspective. However, the nature of moral judgments and moral facts, as well as objectivity and subjectivity in general, remain a subject of ongoing debate in philosophy and metaethics.

Keywords: antirealism, subjectivism, sophism

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Thought

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Thought is the act or process of thinking; cogitation. A product of thinking; idea; notion. Opinion is a thought or belief about something or someone. The thought, on the other hand, is an idea or opinion produced by thinking, or occurring suddenly in the mind. Questions concerning the nature of thought are as old as history itself. Thinking is a material process that fuels scientific investigation into the nature of thought. Thought is so often based on analogy and metaphor—mind invokes one of these subroutines to understand a new context. Theoretical physicist David Bohm (ix) says that the role of thought and knowledge at every level of human affairs, from our private reflections on personal identity to our collective efforts to fashion a tolerable civilisation, leave behind a sediment of ‘common sense’; this is the document of its historical effectiveness. Common sense is not rigid and immobile but is continually transforming itself, enriching itself with scientific ideas and with philosophical opinions which have entered ordinary life.

To begin with, thought is not fresh, direct perception. It is literally that which has been ‘thought’ -the past, carried forward into the present. Thought is also inclusive of feelings, in the form of latent emotional experiences. Not only negative, painful emotions are folded into thought, but pleasurable ones as well. The mind is an evolved computer program, and the contents of the messages vary from personal thoughts to public statements. Public opinion can provide useful perspectives on an influential work of political thought. Lippmann wrote that ‘the ideal of democracy’ involved a particular mode of opinion formation: ‘self-conscious people forming judgments on weight of evidence, and initiating from their own thoughts.’. He thought improving public opinion meant elevating chat from gossip to debate, so that it governed even better as a general political force.

Keywords: cognitive process, public opinion, philosophical inquiry

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Trust

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Trust is a fundamental element in communication that fosters effective collaboration by promoting honesty, transparency, and reliability. When trust is established, information flows more openly, reducing misunderstandings and enhancing teamwork and productivity. Building and maintaining trust requires consistent demonstrations of competence, integrity, and compassion—essential components of strong interpersonal relationships. Trust enables individuals to express ideas, concerns, and opinions freely, particularly in intercultural settings where sensitivity and openness are crucial. High-trust cultures encourage knowledge sharing, innovation, and structured, cohesive work environments. Trust has a key role in effective communication, also in intercultural and cross-cultural contexts.

Scholars and professionals in communication emphasise that trust is both complex and essential. It has been defined as a willingness to rely on another's reliability or virtue, a confident expectation of integrity, or a belief in trustworthy behavior. However, broad definitions of trust provide little guidance on how to cultivate it in communication. Trust is also a fundamental interpersonal relationship in which one party (the truster) engages with another (the trustee) based on the expectation that the trustee will act in a manner beneficial to the truster, thereby demonstrating trustworthiness or credibility. Given that the trustee's response is never entirely certain, trust inherently involves risk, rendering the truster vulnerable. Consequently, trust can be understood as a forward-looking assessment of another's contingent behavior. Trust plays a crucial role in the formation of social capital, contributing to greater life satisfaction and a sense of existential security at the individual level. Additionally, at the societal level, trust fosters political stability and economic growth by facilitating cooperation and reducing transaction costs.

Keywords: communication, consonant, truth

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Truth

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That which is true or in accordance with fact or reality or a fact or belief that is accepted as true. In metaphysics and the philosophy of language, truth is the property of sentences, assertions, beliefs, thoughts, or propositions that, in ordinary discourse, are to agree with the facts or to state what is the case. The question concerning the nature of truth has been asked by philosophers and semanticists for millennia.

The contemporary theories of truth are the *correspondence* theory, *coherence*, and *pragmatist* theories of truth. Wittgenstein via the correspondence theory assumes that what we believe as true corresponds to the way things actually are - to the facts. This theory is connected with an assumption that belief is true if there exists an appropriate entity - a fact - to which it corresponds. Otherwise - the belief is false. In John Austin's correspondence relations, on the other hand, facts (or so-called states of affairs) are entirely conventional. Modern correspondence theories of truth draw from the ideas developed by Alfred Tarski and his *semantic conception of truth* for sentences in terms of concepts like reference and satisfaction, related to the basic semantic functions of names and predicates with language as 'a bearer of truth'. The coherence theory of truth in its modern form, connected with British idealism for Walker, is related to a statement that a belief is true if and only if it is part of a coherent system of beliefs claims Glanzberg. American pragmatist theories of truth per Charles Sanders Peirce and William James in terms of utility (in James's case) and as the result of inquiry (for Peirce), on the other hand, assume that truth is what is verifiable.

Keywords: correspondence, idealism, pragmatism, satisfaction, verification

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Types of Participants in Social Media Audience

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Due to the nature of computer-mediated communication, the participants of online interaction are mostly anonymous, and the audience is collective. Since it is undefined, it is sometimes dubbed the imagined audience, i.e., a conceptualisation of potential interactants. Ede and Lunsford distinguish between invoked audience, which is one imagined by the writer of a message, and addressed audience, which comprises the actual readers of the message. A writer of a message is not always the author of the message. If the author does not want to type and post a message themselves, they can relegate it to a writer. Similarly, on the reception end, the addressee is not necessarily the target of a message. The former is the person one talks/writes to, while the latter is the person at whom the message is actually targeted. The posted message reaches not only the addressee to whom the message is sent, but anyone out there who happens to see the post and decides to read it (i.e., originally unrati ed participants, but due to the nature of social media which host open access to posted messages, they automatically become ratified participants) or those recipients the producer ratifies him/herself (friends on Facebook, subscribers on YouTube, etc.). Thus, the addressee and the target may, but need not, coincide. The notion of ratified versus unrati ed addresses, originally proposed by Goffman, is substantially modified in the context of social media, since addressees change their status from overhearers, or unrati ed participants, to ratified participants who are not addressees/targets. Both ratified and unrati ed participants on social media can freely express their opinion by posting their message or by adding their opinions to existing posts, whether or not they are the addressees/targets of the message.

Keywords: addressed audience, imagined audience, invoked audience

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Types of Public Opinion

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On the basis of the meta-analysis of various definitions of public opinion, S. Herbst enlisted a number of types of public opinion: aggregate public opinion, majoritarian public opinion, discursive public opinion, reified public opinion. Aggregate public opinion can be understood as the sum of opinions expressed through polls, surveys, elections, referenda based on the assumption that the public is an atomised group of individuals holding opinions on a plethora of specific issues. Majoritarian public opinion are based on the aggregation of voices of the people who are able to express themselves, and their voice is widely heard in a society. The discursive public opinion assumes that the opinions are not stable, they evolve as a result of the publicly held discursive communication based on exchange of arguments. The reified public opinion refers to the public opinion as a fictional entity constructed by symbolic elites (political, media, academic, etc.), and it is used rhetorically to various political aims, including self-legitimation and de-legitimation of the opponents.

The most recent framework developed in 'critical algorithm studies' distinguished so called algorithmic public opinion, a concept which captures how social media algorithms contribute to shape public opinion both as a process and a product. As a process it is shaped by interactions between users and algorithmic systems. On the one hand social media platforms act as new type of gatekeepers through, for example, content prioritisation, removal, or labelling. On the other hand, various actors (users, groups, or organisations) attempt to affect content circulation and promote the visibility of their messages using legitimate (optimisation, algorithmic activism) or illegitimate techniques (trolling). As a product, algorithmic public opinion is the outcome of the interplay of technological mediation and user agency.

Keywords: aggregate public opinion, majoritarian public opinion, discursive public opinion, reified public opinion, algorithmic public opinion

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Vagueness

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Opinions can be expressed in different degrees of specificity, some of them being more or less vague. Vagueness is often used interchangeably and/or is associated with indefiniteness, generality, evasiveness, fuzziness, often leading to miscommunication. Therefore, the term used to have (and still sometimes has) negative connotations. As such, it has been long treated as an unwanted feature of communication, used mainly for manipulative purposes when veiling opinions and deliberately masking the speaker's intentions. However, since Joanna Channell's seminal work *Vague Language*, the term 'vague language' has evolved to mean a repertoire of linguistic categories, which have a highly non-specific meaning but can be used as a useful strategy to make communication more effective.

The taxonomies of vague language vary in different works, but the most typical categories include (1) quantifiers, (2) approximators, (3) placeholders, and (4) vague references to categories (also called 'summarising lexical items' or 'general extenders'). The meaning and functions of vague lexemes depend on the context and discourse type where they are used. By appropriately using vague language in appropriate situations the following functions can be performed: (1) give the right amount of information and deliberately withhold information; (2) use language persuasively; (3) display power; (4) use it as a strategy of politeness and as a means of self-protection; (5) use it as a means to demonstrate informality; and (6) fill in lexical gaps and missing information.

Though vagueness is widely observed in spoken discourse, where spontaneity and informality are common, it is also used in written domains such as journalism, advertising, and academic writing, where it can help hedge claims, create inclusivity, or appeal to broader audiences. In more formal writing, the use of vagueness must be carefully balanced to avoid ambiguity and to maintain an appropriate level of formality.

Keywords: communication strategies, pragmatics, indefiniteness

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View

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View refers to a mental perspective, interpretation, or evaluative stance that an individual or group holds regarding a particular subject. It shapes how one perceives, understands, and assesses phenomena, informed by cognitive processes and contextual factors. Goffman as well as Habermas find a view is not merely a momentary opinion but a structured, dynamic framework influenced by both individual cognition and collective social norms. It functions as a lens through which individuals and societies interpret, evaluate, and respond to the world.

When analysing an author's view, claims Zaller, it is essential to consider their perspective or evaluative stance toward the subject. This can be inferred from rhetorical and stylistic choices such as diction, syntax, and the selection of evidence, all of which convey implicit or explicit evaluations. An author's view extends beyond explicit statements to include patterns of reasoning, descriptive detail, and emphasis, revealing the underlying attitudes and assumptions shaping their representation of the topic, states Noelle-Neumann.

In the realm of political opinion, a view encompasses an individual or collective orientation toward political issues, ideologies, or policies. Political views are shaped by personal experiences, core values, socio-cultural influences, and exposure to diverse information sources per Zaller. For Noelle-Neumann these views are expressed across dimensions such as political ideologies, economic policies, social justice, governance, and foreign relations. The formation and evolution of political views reflect both individual cognition and broader societal discourse, often shaped by historical context, media, and social interactions says Habermas.

In sum, a view is a dynamic interpretive framework that integrates personal cognition, cultural norms, rhetorical strategies, and social dynamics, making it central to both individual and collective meaning-making, concludes Goffman.

Keywords: interpretive framework, cognitive perspective, social norms

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Vulgarism

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A vulgarism is a word or expression that makes explicit and offensive reference to sex, bodily functions, or other taboo subjects. Vulgarity, also referred to as profanity or use of swear/curse words, is considered crude, offensive, or impolite, often contains strong language, and is explicit. Thus, vulgarisms are generally not appropriate in formal or polite language. They are often used to express strong emotions, frustration, anger, or emphasis, but they can also be offensive, disrespectful, or inappropriate in certain contexts. On the other hand, vulgarisms can function as powerful linguistic tools that can convey solidarity or group identity within informal settings, such as among close friends or within certain subcultures. Depending on the social context, the pragmatic use of vulgar language can signal intimacy, rebellion, or humour.

Vulgarity may serve as an intensifier to emphasise subjective opinions, as a means to offend or convey hate speech towards others, to describe vulgar activities, or to indicate an informal tone in conversation. As such, vulgar language is frequently included in widely used sentiment and emotion analysis lexicons.

The use of vulgar language is influenced by pragmatic or contextual factors, including the interpersonal relationship between speakers or their social characteristics such as gender, occupation, religiosity, culture, or social status, which reflect differing norms about politeness and taboo language. For instance, some research indicates that males tend to employ profanity more frequently than females. In research on social media, certain vulgar words were identified as indicative of demographic traits such as political ideology, age group, or regional background.

Keywords: impoliteness, offensive language, taboo language

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World Knowledge/Extralinguistic Knowledge

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In linguistics world knowledge is the non-linguistic information that helps a reader or listener interpret the meanings of words and sentences. The linguistic knowledge, referred to also as *word knowledge*, *semantic knowledge* by Dascal, or *language knowledge* by Dudschig et al, is juxtaposed to *world knowledge* by Dudschig et al., Martin et al., and Gile, called also *encyclopedic knowledge* by Setton, *non-linguistic knowledge* by Dudschig et al. as well as Setton or *extralinguistic knowledge*, which is used to refer to people, animals, objects, their properties, or events, which form the language user's experience with the phenomena of the outside world.

The knowledge of the world is indispensable to properly produce language and interpret it in varying contexts. It is also a vital factor in translation and interpreting, which decides about the semantic and pragmatic interpretation of the language used. The concept of *knowledge* in these definitions corresponds to the traditional ('tripartite') analysis of knowledge understood as justified, true belief treated as a set of necessary and sufficient conditions for its definition state Jenkins and Steup. World knowledge is closely linked to the concept of Worldview.

Keywords: knowledge, language, outside world, pragmatic interpretation, semantic interpretation

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Worldview

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Worldview is a comprehensive perspective through which individuals interpret and understand the world around them. For Koltko-Rivera, for example, Worldview has been named with different labels through its use in philosophy, psychology, sociology, or culture. It is a particularly polysemous and rich concept. In an attempt to define its multilevel nature Koltko-Rivera proposes that worldview is ‘a way of describing the universe and life within it, both in terms of what is and what ought to be. [It is] is a set of beliefs that includes limiting statements and assumptions regarding what exists and what does not (either in actuality, or in principle), what objects or experiences are good or bad, and what objectives, behaviours, and relationships are desirable or undesirable. A worldview defines what can be known or done in the world, and how it can be known or done. In addition to defining what goals can be sought in life, a worldview defines what goals should be pursued. Worldviews include assumptions that may be unproven, and even unprovable, but these assumptions are superordinate, in that they provide the epistemic and ontological foundations for other beliefs within a belief system’.

In some philosophical approaches language is not considered a *neutral* system for expressing perception and conception, but rather as a factor that directly shapes them, the hypothesis known as *language determinism and relativity, or as a Sapir-Whorf Hypothesis*. In other words, the language we acquire influences the way we construct our vision of the world (hence, language determinism). And if this is so, then most probably different languages provide different visions of that same world (language relativity), i.e., distinct worldviews. The linguist who specifically rejected these ideas was Noam Chomsky, who posits instead a theory of Universal Grammar, shared as a common grammar, driven by a human faculty of language acquisition.

Keywords: language acquisition, language determinism, language relativity, Sapir/Whorf hypothesis, universal grammar

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